

**THE INFLUENCE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY
ON NONFINANCIAL ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE
IN FOR-PROFIT PUBLIC AND PRIVATE
ENTERPRISES IN YEMEN**

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A Master's Project submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for
the degree of Master of Business Administration

Center for Graduate Studies
Open University Malaysia

2013

ABSTRACT

Although corporate social responsibility (CSR) has been considerably tackled by many scholars in the literature, the influence of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) has been given less remarkable attention. This study examines the influence of the four components comprising CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities of enterprises) on the NFOP in for-profit public and private enterprises operating in the Yemeni economic sectors. It reviews the literature concerning CSR with its components, CSR in for-profit public enterprises (i.e., state-owned enterprises or SOEs), organizational performance with its two types, and CSR initiatives in Yemen. The framework and the hypotheses of the study are postulated to examine empirically the impact of CSR on NFOP and to measure the significant difference in the overall adoption of CSR between SOEs and private enterprises. The questionnaires were disseminated among 255 for-profit enterprises in Yemen and only 103 valid questionnaires were analyzed as the final sample size using both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses.

Obtained results revealed that the four components of CSR have positive significant relationships with the NFOP when measured separately in private enterprises and in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity. Conversely, there was insignificant influence of CSR on the NFOP when examined separately in only SOEs. Moreover, the most influential component of CSR on the NFOP is the economic component followed by the philanthropic component. Furthermore, there was no statistically significant difference between SOEs and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting periodically the concept of CSR.

Keywords:

Corporate social responsibility, business ethics, state-owned enterprises, organizational performance, business and society.

ABSTRAK (BAHASA MELAYU)

Walaupun tanggungjawab sosial korporat (*Corporate Social Responsibility* atau *CSR*) telah banyak ditangani oleh ramai penyelidik dalam literatur, pengaruh CSR pada prestasi organisasi bukan kewangan (*Nonfinancial Organizational Performance* atau *NFOP*) kurang di beri perhatian yang sewajarnya. Kajian ini mengkaji pengaruh empat komponen CSR (ekonomi, undang-undang, etika, dan tanggungjawab dermawan perusahaan) pada NFOP untuk perusahaan yang berorientasi keuntungan awam dan swasta yang beroperasi di sektor ekonomi Yaman. Ianya mengkaji mengenai literatur CSR dan komponennya, CSR pada perusahaan awam yang berorientasi keuntungan (*perusahaan milik negara* atau *SOE*), prestasi organisasi kepada dua jenis, dan insentif CSR di Yaman. Rangka kerja dan hipotesis kajian ini diandaikan untuk memeriksa secara empiric, kesan CSR pada NFOP dan untuk mengukur perbezaan yang ketara dalam penerimaan keseluruhan CSR antara SOE dan syarikat swasta. Borang soal selidik telah diagih ke 255 perusahaan yang berorientasi di Yaman dan hanya 103 soal selidik yang sah telah dianalisis sebagai saiz sampel akhir yang menggunakan menggunakan analisis statistik deskriptif dan inferens.

Keputusan yang diperolehi menunjukkan bahawa empat komponen CSR mempunyai hubungan yang signifikan positif dengan NFOP apabila diukur secara berasingan untuk perusahaan swasta dan kedua-dua SOE dan syarikat swasta sebagai satu entiti keseluruhan. Sebaliknya, terdapat pengaruh CSR yang tidak ketara di NFOP apabila diperiksa secara berasingan untuk SOE. Selain itu, komponen CSR yang paling berpengaruh di NFOP adalah komponen ekonomi diikuti dengan komponen dermawan. Tambahan pula, tidak ada perbezaan statistik yang ketara antara SOE dan syarikat swasta mengenai tahap penggunaan secara berkala konsep CSR.

Kata Kunci:

Tanggungjawab sosial korporat, etika perniagaan, perusahaan milik negara, prestasi organisasi, perniagaan dan masyarakat.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Before everything else, all praise and extolment are truthfully dedicated to *Allah (our God, The Exalted)* for helping and supporting me during the long days and hours spent for conducting and achieving this Master's project.

Then, I would like to profoundly acknowledge *Dr. Murad Al-Nashmi*, rector of the Administrative Science College affiliated with the University of Science and Technology in Yemen, who dedicatedly and patiently supervised my project from scratch as well as persistently guided and encouraged me to properly fulfill this study. For me, *Dr. Al-Nashmi* is a role model, both as an academic and as a person, and I am actually lucky that I have worked academically with him to achieve this study.

In the academia, I do certainly express my profound gratitude for *Prof. Archie B. Carroll*, a Robert W. Scherer professor of management at University of Georgia in Athens, for his personal appreciated assistance in providing me with the required study's instrument concerning Carroll's CSR four-part model. In addition, I do certainly express my profound gratitude for *Prof. Mark A. Huselid*, a professor of human resource strategy in the School of Management and Labor Relations (SMLR) at Rutgers University, for his valuable comments and clarifications concerning the study's instrument used for measuring the organizational performance.

My great and warm appreciation is also dedicated to *Prof. Muhammad Al-Mansoob*, Professor of Applied Statistics in Sana'a University, who dedicated part of his valuable time for helping me in statistically analyzing and theoretically discussing the obtained data. I should also direct my deep gratitude to other professors from Open University Malaysia (OUM), Sana'a University, and University of Science and Technology (UST) for their appreciated reviews to the study's instrument and for their support and guidance in other theoretical issues related to the study. Among those professors are *Prof. Dawood Al-Hidabi*, *Dr. Fadhl Al-Shua'aibi*, *Dr. Ali Al-Arusi*, *Dr. Saleh Al-Hamasy*, *Dr. Abdul-Hakim Nashir*, and *Dr. Arif Al-Qadasi*. Other thankworthy scholars who helped me from Malaysia concerning the translations of the 'ABSTRACT' into Malay include *Dr. Yuhainis Yusoff* and *Dr. Mohammed Al-Jifri*. I am also deeply appreciative for the thankworthy efforts made by several specific officials and colleagues at the Ministry of Finance, Yemen, for supporting me with different means in the long process of fulfillment this study.

A special acknowledgment is overwhelmingly expressed to *Dr. Anna L. Cates*, the adjunct professor of graduate education and English for Liberty University and Southern New Hampshire University, for her thankworthy guidance and valuable resources provided for me concerning research methodology, theses submissions, and other provided linguistic and academic explanations. I should also mention here a great Canadian colleague who supported me—and always supports me—during the whole

period of my Master's study. This colleague is *James D. Thwaites*, a lecturer at W. L. McLeod Elementary School in Vanderhoof in British Columbia of Canada, who I do have a deep appreciation for him and for his considerable thoughts and opinions concerning life and academia. I should also refer to another close friend who helped me a lot in searching for the academic resources needed in this project and who should be profoundly thanked. This German colleague is Rami Al-Kubaty from the University Duisburg-Essen (Universität Duisburg-Essen) located in North Rhine-Westphalia State, Germany.

I should here not forget to sincerely acknowledge those highly supportive people belonging to Concordia University in Montréal of Canada who emotionally represent a strong motivation for me to study my Master's degree in Business Administration (MBA). Among those special and good-nature individuals are *Anna Nigoghosian, Kelly Collins, Diane Moffat, Penny-Anne Soper, and Landry Houndolo*. I should also not forget to deeply thank my close Canadian friend from Montréal, *Sameer Abban*, who was a real and supportive friend indeed during my Master's study. I do adore Concordia University and everything in Montréal because of those amiable and sociable people and certainly I could not achieve my MBA without their appreciated sincere and spiritual support. Thank you all in the Great Canada.

Within this acknowledgment I should also greatly thank those people—either female or male respondents and other subordinates—from different for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen who faithfully and modestly helped me during the process of disseminating and collecting back the survey. Also, I should thank all other people who assisted me during this project and who I could not mention them in these two papers of acknowledgment.

Finally yet importantly, special acknowledgements are granted to *my loyal and patient wife and my cute son, Nasser*, who without their great supports I would not be able to achieve and complete this Master's project at all. Among other thankworthy close relatives who supported and encouraged me to study my Masters' degree are *my sisters, my brothers, Uncle Ahmed Al-Samman, Uncle Abdul-Wli Al-Qadi, and Uncles Saleem and Fathi Al-Arami*. Also these acknowledgements are importantly dedicated to the special members of my family including *my great mother and to the soul of my ideal, my great father*, who exceptionally taught me how to adore reading and writing in the English language. Thank you so much my cherished late father and may Allah will mercy you.

DECLARATION

Name: Eyad Nasser Al-Samman

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I hereby declare that this Master's Project is the result of my own work, except for quotations and summaries which have been duly acknowledged.

Signature:

Date: ..20 December 2013

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BRIICS: Brazil, Russia, India, Indonesia, China, and South Africa
CEO: Chief executive officer
CFO: Chief financial officer
CFP: Corporate financial performance
CSP: Corporate social performance
CSR: Corporate social responsibility
CSRO: Corporate social responsibility orientation
Eco_CSR: CSR's component of economic responsibilities
EPS: Earnings per share
Eth_CSR: CSR's component of ethical responsibilities
CED: Committee for Economic Development
GOC: Government-owned corporation
KMO: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
Leg_CSR: CSR's component of legal responsibilities
MBA: Master of business administration
MNC: Multinational corporation
NFOP: Nonfinancial organizational performance
NGO: Nongovernmental organization
OECD: Organization for economic cooperation and development
OP: Organizational performance
Phi_CSR: CSR's component of philanthropic responsibilities
ROA: Return on assets
ROE: Return on equity
ROI: Return on investment
ROS: Return on sales
SIM: Social Issues in Management
SME: Small and medium-sized Enterprise
SMLR: School of Management and Labor Relations
S.D.: Standard Deviation
SOE: State-owned enterprise
SPP: Stock price performance
SPSS: Statistical package for the social sciences
TBL: Triple-bottom line
UMI: University Microfilms International
U.N.: United Nations
U.S.: United States
U.S.A: United States of America

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

The reciprocal relationship between business and society is one of the most essential and immortal relationships in this life. Society is the intangible place where different businesses operate and invest in. According to Brigham *et al.* (2005), the main goal of most businesses is to maximize shareholders' wealth. This essential objective is achieved only with the help and blessing of the society in which these businesses exist in. At the same time, this primary objective clearly reveals the real and vital aspects of the relationship between society and business. This relationship should be ethically considered which results in having a concept that properly rules different components of the two sides of the relationship. Consequently, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is the ethical concept that can expound and reinforce this relationship through serious adoptions followed by various businesses operating in any modern society.

The concept of CSR is not a modern or new trend in management. Several incidents concerned with social responsibility's issues had occurred in Europe and the United States of America during the 19th century (Forester, 2009). During the early 1900s, the CSR concept was framed and outlined theoretically by numerous researchers. The concept itself has been researched from different sides, through different periods, and in different industries in the world. Several definitions, dimensions, theories, models, and

principles have been posited concerning CSR which describe and address it more and more. This contributed in evolving CSR concept into new interrelated concepts which tackle in detail the new aspects of the modern social management such as corporate social performance (CSP), social responsiveness, and corporate citizenship. This can be perceived through the saying of Carroll *et al.* (2009) when they argue that “CSR is a front-burner issue within the business community and continues to grow each year” (p. 34).

Among the most acceptable definitions existed in the literature and in academia about CSR is the one posited by Archie B. Carroll during the late 1970s. This scholar found that “The social responsibility of business encompasses the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations that society has of organizations at a given point in time” (Carroll, 1979, p. 500). This definition has an inclusive framework for the main four components or responsibilities that constitute the concept of CSR which was made as a principal implied component of the corporate social performance (CSP). The four-part definition of CSR suggested by the American professor Archie Carroll in the late 1970s included economic and legal responsibilities of a business in context with other two more socially oriented responsibilities of business which are ethical and discretionary or philanthropic responsibilities (Carroll *et al.*, 2009).

The CSR has been a matter of concern all the same for researchers and managers in various developed and developing countries. Researchers know that this concept is essential for developing societies and has not been given the required and sufficient academic attention and investigation yet. Managers of businesses are aware that CSR contributes affirmatively in increasing profitability. They realize that CSR is a strategic tool needed for fulfilling their objectives and policies even with a partial but safe

success. Porter *et al.* (2006, p. 2) squarely point out: “CSR can be much more than a cost, a constraint, or a charitable deed—it can be a source of opportunity, innovation, and competitive advantage.” They add that “it is through the strategic CSR that the company will make the most significant social impact and reap the greatest business benefits” (p. 7).

On the other hand, the existence of any organization operating in public, private, or nongovernmental sector is primarily related with its level of organizational performance. The main point of the organizational performance is to measure effectively and efficiently the levels of applied functions related to different departments comprising the organization. The organizational performance is expressed in the literature based on two main approaches; the objective and subjective. In brief, the objective organizational performance is related to financial indicators and aspects related to the organization which are determined through financial ratios, and accounting and financial reports. However, the subjective organizational performance is about nonfinancial or perceptual aspects that are subjectively measured and assessed. To have a comprehensive vision about the overall organizational performance, both subjective and objective measures of organizational performance should be integrated and adopted. Carton *et al.* (2006) contend that a better understanding of relative and incremental information contents concerning financial performance can be helpful for managers in selecting nonfinancial metrics to fill the gaps about the overall organizational performance.

A significant portion of the published researches existing in the literature has studied the relationship between corporate financial performance (CFP) and CSR (Akanbi & Ofoegbu, 2012; Aupperle, Carroll, & Hatfield, 1985; Becchetti, Di Giacomo, &

Pinnacchio, 2005; Bird, Casavecchia, & Reggianib, 2006; Griffin & Mahon, 1997; McGuire, Sundgren, & Schneeweis, 1988; Park, 2010; Paskert, 2008; Quazi & Richardson, 2012; Roman, Hayibor, & Agle, 1999; Vollono, 2010). The majority of these studies found this relationship to be positive. These and other studies significantly focused on the financial organizational performance as a major criterion for measuring the overall organizational performance of organizations. The majority of these studies mainly neglected the subjective or nonfinancial measures used for determining the organizational performance. Consequently, the paucity of studies in the literature that measure the effect of CSR on subjective organizational performance was a reason that initiated the idea for carrying out this study. Hence, in this study the subjective or nonfinancial organizational performance is treated as the dependent variable whereas CSR with its four components is treated as the independent variable. Other society-related themes such as CSP, social responsiveness, and corporate citizenship are not explored in depth in this study and only the main focus is directed to the independent variable and its four dimensions, namely, CSR.

The concept of CSR in Yemen is still nascent and adopted only by the minority of organizations in both public and private sectors. The public organizations mentioned in this study are those known as the state-owned enterprises (SOEs) which are profitmaking enterprises created and managed by the Yemeni government per se to assume commercial profitable activities. The reviewed studies concerning CSR in Yemen discuss this phenomenon from different sides. A small portion of these studies is concerned about CSR and its influences on government organizations and their members (Al-Kumaim, 2006; Sharhan, 2009). Other studies tackle CSR and other related activities (i.e., marketing, perception, and accountability) in the private sector (Al-Abbasi, 2011; Al-Hamdi, 2003; Al-Hamdi & Ja'abil, 2008; Naji, 2010; Said, 2011).

The CSR in Yemen is still viewed by some enterprises—especially those operating in the private sector—as a charitable contribution towards society that is not obliged but majorly optional in its nature.

This chapter discusses the introduction to this study that has been conducted about studying the influence of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance in for-profit public and private enterprises operating in Yemen. The term ‘organization’ used in this study refers to either a for-profit public enterprise (SOE) or a private enterprise operating in different economic sectors in Yemen. The following sections of this chapter give overviews about problem statement, research questions, research objectives, the significance of the study as well as organization of the chapters, followed by the definition of the key terms pertaining to the study's dependent and independent variables (i.e., the organizational performance and CSR).

1.2. Problem Statement

There is a necessity for organizations in public and private sectors to adopt more social actions and responsibilities towards their stakeholders in Yemen. The CSR is considered as a global and strategic method which creates a competitive advantage needed for continuity and prosperity of organizations. The significance of having a well-organized and well-applied CSR in organizations is an equivalence to the desired success by these organizations. Porter *et al.* (2006) argue that “the more closely tied a social issue is to the company’s business, the greater the opportunity to leverage the firm’s resources and capabilities, and benefit society” (p. 10).

According to the literature, the majority of studies have shown that CSR is positively related with the organizational financial performance. However, the literature has a scant and limited portion which has empirically analyzed the relationship between CSR

and organizational subjective or nonfinancial performance in private and public organizations. The organizational performance per se is a matter which interests both stakeholders and businesses. Subjective aspects of the organizational performance are essential for the success of different businesses in public and private sectors. This important branch of organizational performance (i.e., subjective, perceptual, or nonfinancial) has the same importance which the other branch could have for the businesses, namely, the organizational financial or objective performance. Accordingly, in this study the terms ‘perceptual’, ‘nonfinancial’, and ‘subjective’ are used interchangeably.

The intention of this study is to review the influence of CSR on organizational subjective performance in for-profit public and private enterprises operating in Yemen within different industries and economic sectors (i.e., primary, secondary, and tertiary). This study also intends to determine any significant differences for the adopted levels of CSR in general between for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen and defining possible causes for such distinction if it would be existent. Other intentions of this study include how to better use the four dimensions of CSR to improve the subjective organizational performance in public and private sectors and whether the CSR four-part model (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities of for-profit enterprises) is associated with the nonfinancial organizational performance.

1.3. Research Questions

There are many previous studies on the relationship between CSR and organizational performance with its two main types, namely, objective and subjective. Accordingly, this study was conducted to find the relationship of the independent variables (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities that an enterprise has) with

the dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance, in for-profit public and private enterprises operating in different economic sectors in Yemen.

The purposes of this study were tackled by answering the following questions:

- i. Does CSR adopted in for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) have relationship with the nonfinancial organizational performance?
- ii. Does CSR adopted in private organizations have relationship with the nonfinancial organizational performance?
- iii. Does CSR adopted in both SOEs and private organizations as a whole entity have relationship with the nonfinancial organizational performance of these organizations?
- iv. Which of the CSR's components have more influences on the nonfinancial organizational performance of for-profit organizations as a whole entity?

1.4. Objectives of the Research

The objectives of this study are twofold: (i) to investigate the relationship between CSR and the nonfinancial organizational performance in for-profit public organizations, namely, SOEs, and private organizations; and (ii) to compare the level of adopted CSR in various SOEs and private enterprises operating in Yemen. Hence, research objectives of this study are to determine the following:

- i. Whether the level of adopted corporate social responsibility is significantly different between for-profit public and private organizations as a whole entity operating in Yemen.
- ii. Whether the CSR's economic component in for-profit public organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- iii. Whether the CSR's legal component in for-profit public organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.

- iv. Whether the CSR's ethical component in for-profit public organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- v. Whether the CSR's philanthropic component in for-profit public organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- vi. Whether the CSR's economic component in private organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- vii. Whether the CSR's legal component in private organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- viii. Whether the CSR's ethical component in private organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- ix. Whether the CSR's philanthropic component in private organizations in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- x. Whether the CSR's economic component in both for-profit public and private organizations as a whole entity in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- xi. Whether the CSR's legal component in both for-profit public and private organizations as a whole entity in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- xii. Whether the CSR's ethical component in both for-profit public and private organizations as a whole entity in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.
- xiii. Whether the CSR's philanthropic component in both for-profit public and private organizations as a whole entity in Yemen is significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance.

- xiv. Which components of CSR do influence the nonfinancial organizational performance the most in for-profit enterprises in Yemen.

1.5. Significance of the Study

During the last decades and up to now, the concept of CSR has had a major concern from individuals and organizations belonging to academia, businesses, governments, and diverse developed and developing societies. Carroll (2008) maintains that during the 21st century, the CSR movement impressively has been a global phenomenon. Executives, scholars, policy makers, and even politicians relate the significance of the CSR concept to the strategic management, globalization, and corporate governance. The pressure of global competition will continue and this makes business case for the CSR to be always at the center of attention (Carroll, 2008). On the other hand, the significance of CSR is impressive on the organizations' profitability. This significance is shown through the thorough analysis that Roman *et al.* (1999) have done in their research to find out the relationship between social and financial performance. They concluded that a massive portion of studies in the literature about social and financial performance supports the idea that, at the very least, good social performance does not lead to poor financial performance.

This study is an attempt to empirically explore the influence that CSR could have on the nonfinancial organizational performance of diverse for-profit enterprises in Yemen. Available researches and studies which tackled the relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance (CFP) are copious whereas those researches which have studied the relationship between CSR and nonfinancial organizational performance are very limited and scarce. This issue causes a wide gap in the literature that needs to

be filled by the researchers and their academic contributions about this type of relationship.

Typically, the focus when studying the organizational performance is principally directed towards profitability and financial ratios (i.e., objective organizational performance) whereas the second type of organizational performance, namely, organizational perceptual performance, is purposely or accidentally ignored by researchers, scholars, and managers. This study is an initiative for paying the attention of scholars and executives to the importance and efficiency of perceptual or subjective organizational performance and the magnitude of impact that it could result through applying and adopting social responsibilities by diverse for-profit public and private organizations operating in Yemen.

The Yemeni government stresses on the significance of the social responsibilities of different for-profit public and private organizations operating in Yemen and this act was shown through organizing three conferences on CSR issues in Yemen during the 2000s (i.e., 2008, 2009, and 2010). The outcomes of the current study could be a starting point for diverting the deep-rooted perception of CSR among Yemeni and other foreign executives and managers working in Yemen who consider that CSR is no more than a charitable contribution towards society. The expected results of this study could support the fact that CSR is more than a benevolent activity and that it is a strategic concept and a legitimate method for measuring and applying corporate governance of various for-profit public and private organizations in Yemen (i.e., SOEs and private enterprises).

Most of the articles, books, and academic dissertations in the literature about CSR discuss this concept in the private sector and exclude the activities of CSR in for-profit public or government organizations. Thus and for some extent, this study could

contribute in enhancing the organizations' practices by enriching the existing literature on public cooperative CSR engagement, and more notably, by providing a necessary empirical study supporting the existent thoughts that could influence more the public or government CSR engagement in Yemen. On the other hand, by trying to define CSR perceptive thoughts in public organizations in Yemen, the findings of the current study could assist private and public organizations to establish the needed cooperation and integrity in the CSR-related initiatives towards benefiting the entire society of Yemen.

This study also could be instrumental for prospective researchers who have interests in finding an empirical study about CSR in Yemen from one side and about the impact that CSR could have on the nonfinancial organizational performance of various for-profit public and private enterprises operating in a unique developing country like Yemen from the other side. It is almost clear that the area of CSR in Yemen is still less researched and discussed by many researchers for many societal and administrative reasons. That is why it is hoped that by presenting this study in such environment with stressing on its academic outcomes, prospective researchers would have the opportunity to build their researches on the expected empirical outcomes obtained from this study which emphasize the positive and essential roles of CSR on enhancing and developing the Yemeni society at large in the future.

1.6. Definitions of the Key Terms

For the academic purposes of the current study, the following operational definitions of terms obtained from the literature are used.

- *Corporate social responsibility (CSR)*: There is no unique definition that was specified during the last decades for CSR which can be used for all purposes (Rahman, 2011). The definition of the CSR adopted in this study is the one that

posited by Carroll (1979) in which he stated: “The social responsibility of business encompasses the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations that society has of organizations at a given point in time” (p. 500). Later, the same scholar suggested that for the CSR to be more accepted by responsible businesspersons, it should be framed to include the four kinds of social responsibilities constituting the total CSR that a business has (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic instead of discretionary) and that these four components of CSR could be illustratively shown as a pyramid (Carroll, 1991).

- *Economic component of CSR:* Economic responsibilities are required of organizations by society. Organizations should be profitable, maximize sales, minimize costs, make sound strategic decisions, be attentive to dividend policy, and provide investors with adequate and attractive returns on their investments (Carroll *et al.*, 2009).
- *Legal component of CSR:* Legal responsibilities are also required of organizations by society. According to Carroll *et al.* (2009), organizations should obey the laws, adhere to all regulations, comply with Sarbanes-Oxley Act, fulfill all contractual obligations, and honor warranties and guarantees.
- *Ethical component of CSR:* Ethical responsibilities are expected of organizations by society. Carroll *et al.* (2009) contend that among the ethical responsibilities that organizations should include are avoiding questionable practices, responding to spirit as well as letter of law, doing what is right, fair, and just, and asserting ethical leadership.

- *Philanthropic component of CSR*: Philanthropic responsibilities are desired or expected of organizations by society. This component was known as discretionary in the published article by Archie B. Carroll in 1979 and then was renamed philanthropic component in 1991 by the same scholar. Philanthropic responsibilities entail organizations to be good corporate citizens. These organizations should give back, make corporate contributions, provide for community betterment, and engage in volunteerism (Carroll and Buchholtz, 2009).

- *Corporate social performance (CSP)*: Wood (1991) posited a definition for the CSP by stating that it is “a business organization’s configuration of principles of social responsibility, processes of social responsiveness, and policies, programs, and observable outcomes as they relate to the firm’s societal relationships” (p. 693).

- *Corporate social responsiveness*: The scholar Donna Wood defined corporate social responsiveness as “a set of boundary-spanning behaviors by which firms link social responsibility principles to behavioral outcomes” (Visser *et al.*, 2010, p. 113). Carroll (1979) described corporate social responsiveness as “the philosophy, mode, or strategy behind business (managerial) response to social responsibility and social issues” (p. 501). The social responsiveness movement, therefore, emphasized corporate action, pro-action, and implementation of a social role (Carroll, 1991). Processes of corporate social responsiveness include environmental assessment, stakeholder management, and issues or public affairs management (Wood, 2010).

- *State-owned enterprise (SOE):* Kowalski *et al.* (2013) maintain that countries apply multiple definitions of SOE which complicates formulation of a meaningful uniform definition of SOE. The most accepted definition in the literature is the one posited by MacCarthaigh (2009) in which he states that the SOE is “an entity in which the state has a majority or complete shareholding, and which is principally involved in commercial activity in a market environment” (p. 5). State or government enterprises can be controlled towards achieving particular social and environmental objectives according to the government’s determined national priorities (MacCarthaigh, 2009). For the purpose of this study, SOEs refer to the public for-profit economic enterprises or units that administered by the Yemeni government operating in different economic sectors in Yemen including raw materials, manufacturing, trade, and services sectors.

- *Private Enterprise:* It is undertaken by private individuals who hope to realize a profit from their activities and who bear any risk associated with those activities. (Private Enterprise, 2007). For the purpose of this study, enterprises refer to the private firms, companies, businesses, or other for-profit organizations that operate in different private sectors in Yemen including raw materials, manufacturing, trade, and services sectors.

- *The Stakeholders:* The definition of the stakeholder is the one posited by Freeman *et al.* (2010) in which they maintain that “a stakeholder in an organization is (by definition) any group or individual who can affect or is affected by achievement of the organization’s objectives” (p. 207). The wide view of stakeholders contains common, generic, and other groups that include

managers, employees, customers, investors, shareholders, suppliers, government, society at large, local community, environment, and future (Crowther *et al.*, 2008). Among the other corporate stakeholders are media, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), and the communities and markets in which these corporates operate in (Visser *et al.*, 2010).

- *Stakeholder Theory*: The concise description of the stakeholder theory is provided by Carroll *et al.* (2009) in which they state that “stakeholder theory is managerial in the broad sense of the term in that it does not simply describe or predict but also recommends attitudes, structures, and practices that constitute stakeholder management” (p. 93). To relate the stakeholder approach with the CSR activities achieved by the corporate's managers, Carroll and Buchholtz (2009) add that “In a balanced perspective, managers are concerned with both goal achievement and ethical treatment of stakeholders” (p. 114).
- *Organizational performance*: The definition of the organizational performance—posited by several researchers—includes that it is an indicator which measures how well an organization achieves its objectives (Hamon, 2003; Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986a). Other researchers found out that the organizational performance is a multidimensional construct (Carton *et al.*, 2006). Venkatraman *et al.* (1986a) maintain that the mode of performance assessment is either objective (e.g., for example based on a system such as internal accounting) or perceptual (e.g., judgments by executives).

1.7. Organization of the Chapters

This study comprises five chapters which have several sections within each chapter. The first chapter, namely, *Chapter I*, provides a background of the study, problem statement,

research questions, research objectives, significance of the study, and operational definitions in use for the key terms used in this study. *Chapter II* presents a review of the literature concerning CSR and organizational performance achieved by other researchers. The focus of the CSR concept in this study is directed to the efforts made by the scholar 'Archie B. Carroll' and his models of CSR postulated in 1979 and 1991. *Chapter III* introduces the methodology used in this study. The chapter consists of several sections including research design, unit of analysis, population, sample and sampling technique, instrumentation, questionnaire design, collection of data, and the techniques used for analyzing collected data. The obtained results and findings concerning the study are discussed in *Chapter IV* using descriptive and inferential statistical analyses. Moreover, the statistical obtained results are summarized in different tables within the same chapter. The final chapter of this study is *Chapter V* which provides a discussion of the obtained findings and results, conclusions, recommendations for future researches, and the limitations of the current study.

1.8. Summary

This chapter provides an introduction to the main problem that this study tackles concerning the influence of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance in Yemeni for-profit public (i.e., SOEs) and private enterprises. Among the sections that this chapter introduces are background of the study, problem statement, research questions, research objectives, significance of the study, definitions in use for the key terms used in this study, and the organization of the study's five chapters.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, a background of the study was presented along with the research problem, questions, and objectives while expounding at the same time the significance and scope of the study. The current chapter tackles the existing researches and studies related to the concept of corporate social responsibility and its categories applied in diverse state-owned enterprises (SOEs) and private enterprises with reviewing also the concept of organizational performance.

Interests of executives today are turned into a vaster vista about social responsibilities and their strategic, nonfinancial, and financial impacts on performance of different organizations. As a result, many researches have investigated the relationship between CSR and organizational performance and a considerable portion of these studies emphasizes the positive relationship between these two concepts. Wissink (2012) contends that when organizations (i.e., SOEs or private enterprises) invest in social domain, this results in improving relationship between CSR and organizational performance which leads mostly to an overall better performance.

Accordingly, this chapter commences with a review on the history of the concept of CSR and it reviews other related issues, namely, CSR in the 21st century, CSR theories, principles, and models, Carroll's model of CSP and Carroll's pyramid of CSR,

stakeholder theory and CSR, CSR and the state-owned enterprises (SOEs), the concept of organizational performance with its two key types (i.e., objective and subjective), and the relationship between CSR and the organizational performance. An overview on the previous studies that have been carried out about CSR and its adoption in Yemen is also reviewed. At the end of this chapter, a summary of the reviewed literature is given showing concisely different tackled points and perspectives.

2.2 Definition of CSR

There are several definitions of CSR found in the literature and they have a consensus towards the importance of this concept for environment, societies, and stakeholders. The definition of CSR has evolved from a simple description of social acts and obligations during the early 1900s to a more sophisticated concept that has several dimensions and several impacts on other social and managerial concepts. The question about “What does the term CSR exactly stand for?” is still an object of controversy among scholars of Social Issues in Management (SIM), academics, and even executives of various public and private organizations. Freeman *et al.* (2010) argue that after nearly 50 years of research and argument, there is no specific and single commonly accepted definition of CSR. According to Dahlsrud (2006), the controversy about defining CSR might be potentially a significant problem and this could be due to the abundance of available definitions of the term. He argues that any try to develop a neutral definition of CSR is challenging due to having no methodology that can judge if this proposed definition is neutral or not. In the same context, Zu (2009) argues that academic researchers and non-academic advocators define CSR as a system approach considering both internal and external stakeholders, while others define it as purely voluntary. He adds that this confusion is increased by a proliferation of terminology in the area of business in society which implies terms such as corporate sustainability or citizenship,

corporate or business responsibility, business social responsibility, the ethical corporation, sustainable business, and other similar terms.

Once more, there are a huge number of definitions for the concept of CSR in the literature and only several important definitions are mentioned in this study. According to Rahman (2011), CSR's definitions include several dimensions such as economic development, ethical practices, environmental protection, stakeholders' involvement, transparency, moral obligation, and responsible behaviors. Academics and executives have definitions for CSR which are based—in many times—on their subjective beliefs or experiences. They relate CSR to the role of enterprises and other commercial organizations towards the society. One of the simple definitions of CSR is the one mentioned by Carroll *et al.* (2009) in which they state: “corporate social responsibility is seriously considering the impact of the company's actions on society” (p. 39). Although this definition has a broad and simple view about CSR, it reflects the core relationship that governs CSR, organizations, and society. Another simple broadest definition about CSR is the one posited by Crowther *et al.* (2008) in which they claim that “the broadest definition of CSR is concerned with what is—or should be—the relationship between global corporations, governments of countries, and individual citizens” (p. 10). In this definition, the governments are involved in the activities of CSR and mentioned as a component that helps in applying CSR with the cooperation of other entities.

Environmental aspects of CSR definition are also present and can be found in the definitions posited by international organizations and commissions. For example, the Commission of European Communities has its own definition of CSR which stresses on environmental issues beside social ones. This definition states: “CSR is a concept

whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis” (European Communities Commission, 2001, p. 6). The term ‘stakeholders’ mentioned in the definition could refer to various stakeholders such as shareholders, employees, customers, society, local communities, government, and others. The definition also stresses on the discretionary base that companies have towards their society, environment, and stakeholders concerning the adoption of CSR activities.

Another definition of CSR which includes the roles of organizations towards stakeholders is posited by Epstein (1987, p. 104) in which he states:

Corporate social responsibility relates primarily to achieving outcomes from organizational decisions concerning specific issues or problems which (by some normative standard) have beneficial rather than adverse effects upon pertinent corporate stakeholders. The normative correctness of the products of corporate action has been the main focus of corporate social responsibility.

Although this definition is somewhat dated but it shows clearly that stakeholders are essential in the process of having active CSR activities. It also emphasizes the relationship between CSR and the stakeholder theory which will be discussed later in this chapter.

Back to the paper composed by Dahlsrud (2006) in which he collected different definitions of CSR—37 definitions originated from 27 authors and published from 1998 onwards—through an extensive review of the literature which includes journal articles and web pages. He found out that these definitions of CSR are categorized into five main dimensions, namely, environmental, social, economic, stakeholder, and voluntariness dimensions. He concludes that natural environment is coded to the environmental dimension, the relationship between business and society is coded to the social dimension, the socio-economic or financial aspects are coded to the economic

dimension, the stakeholder groups are coded to the stakeholder dimension, and the actions not prescribed by law are coded to the voluntariness dimension (Dahlsrud, 2006).

The definitions of CSR have evolved with time and more dimensions have been suggested showing more importance and efficiency of the concept itself. One of these definitions that has been used successfully for researching purposes for over 25 years is the four-part definition postulated by Archie B. Carroll in 1979 (Carroll *et al.*, 2010). Carroll (1979) contends that social responsibility has been conceptualized in different ways by many prominent researchers and there is an accord that the concept of CSR has a wide range of economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary activities. Accordingly, the basic definition of CSR is the one suggested by Carroll (1979, p. 500) in which he asserts that:

The social responsibility of business encompasses the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary (philanthropic) expectations that society has of organizations at a given point in time.

The four categories of CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic) tackle the motivations for initiatives in the category and are instrumental for defining certain benefits concerned with organizations and societies in their fulfillment (Carroll and Shabana, 2010). Consequently, this current study adopts and uses this definition for its continuing usage in the academia concerning the concept of CSR.

2.3 Historical Background of CSR

It is essential to chronologically review the evolution of CSR during the last centuries and most importantly the 20th century which includes the major developments and adaptations concerning this contemporary concept. In order to understand entirely the modern CSR, to be aware of the impact of CSR on the organization's behavior, and to

comprehend the scholarly concepts and ideas embodied in current thinking about CSR, it is necessary to comprehensively review the evolution of this concept (McClerkin, 2013; Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011; Ohlrich, 2011). Consequently, an overview of the history of CSR concept and its related issues is provided in this review. The objective of such overview is to have a thorough conceptualization of CSR that is extremely practical for this study. In this way and also for the core purposes of the current empirical study, it seems sensible to focus on recent concepts related to CSR when tracking its history and when relating it with the perceived organizational performance of public and private enterprises in Yemen (i.e., the dependent variable of this study). Hence, the chronological literature of CSR's evolution in this section traces the concept starting from the early 1950s and then discussing CSR's development afterwards up until the recent 21st century. This kind of discussion is concisely mentioned in this section for shedding light on the general aspects of CSR's history and development by citing and referring to the most significant contributions done by scholars and other related practitioners. Therefore, it is important to pay the attention that this discussion per se is not intended to theoretically cover all the literature tackled the issues of CSR.

The concept of CSR has a long history in which many adaptations have been made on it to be more appropriate with different enhancements happened in societies and enterprises. Businesses in public and private sectors have many obligations towards their stakeholders and some of these obligations are social in nature. The chronology of CSR has not a certain point in time that specifies the commencement of it. However, it was traced during the 1800s that various responsibilities with a charitable nature have been emerged in Europe and especially in the United Kingdom (Carroll, 2008). During that time, dealing with these responsibilities was charitably done and it had not a social nature per se. According to Ohlrich (2011), the topic of charitable donation—which was

the predecessor of CSR—has been present since the early 1800s. He adds that in the period of 1910 to 1930, donations by capitalists in the United States were charitably donated personally to educational institutes or museums rather than giving such financial contributions through the corporations of those capitalists due to the fear from the variability of the court's regulations at that time.

Carroll (1999) contends that it is possible to trace the evidences of business community concern of societies for centuries. He adds that this kind of tracing is intended for enterprises emerged and operated only in the United States. On the other hand, writing of other researchers such as Carroll and Shabana (2010) maintains that the roots of CSR are believed to be extended before the period of World War II. As mentioned earlier in this section, there is a controversy among scholars and researchers concerning specifying the starting point in time for discussing the history of CSR. McClerkin (2013) argues that scholars introduced varying opinions for tracing the starting point of discussions related to business responsibility to society.

The period of the 1950s can be called as the beginning of the modern era of social responsibility (Carroll, 1999). One of the most prominent scholars of this decade is Howard R. Bowen who published a book entitled 'Social Responsibilities of the Businessman' in 1953. In this book, Bowen raised a question saying that "What responsibilities to society may businessmen reasonably be expected to assume?" He argues that social responsibility is not a magic potion but it has an essential truth which should guide business in the future (Bowen, 1953, p. xi, as cited in Carroll, 1999, p. 270). Bowen also posited a seminal definition of businessmen's social responsibilities in which he stated that "it refers to the obligations of businessmen to pursue those policies, to make those decisions, or to follow those lines of action which are desirable

in terms of the objectives and values of our society” (Bowen, 1953, p. 6, as cited in Moura-Leite *et al.*, 2011, p. 530). According to Carroll (1999), Howard Bowen deserves to be dubbed ‘Father of the Corporate Social Responsibility’ for his early and seminal works concerning CSR. During the 1950s, there were limited discussions for relating CSR with its benefits for businesses themselves and instead the main focus was on responsibilities of businesses towards society (Carroll and Shabana, 2010). In brief, Carroll (2008) maintains that the period of the 1950s was concerned more about ‘talk’ than ‘action’ regarding CSR since the period of the 1950s was itself a period of changing attitudes, with business executives learning to have comfortableness with CSR talk. Among other influential scholars who discussed CSR issues during the 1950s are Morrell Heald, Theodore Levitt, Peter Drucker, and Richard Eells (see, for example, Carroll, 1999; Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011; Ohlrich, 2011).

The period of the 1960s marked a significant growth in attempts to formalize and state what CSR exactly means (Carroll, 2008). This period is described by Carroll (1999) as the decade of expanding CSR’s literature. Freeman (1984) argued that “the social movements of the sixties and seventies in civil rights, anti-war, consumerism, environmentalism, and women’s rights served as a catalyst for rethinking the role of the business enterprise in society” (p. 38). According to Ohlrich (2011), one of the major scholars of this period was Keith Davis who posited the ‘Iron Law of Responsibility’ in which he warns wealthy businesses about their social responsibility and that government will regulate these businesses if they cannot self-regulate and assist in societal issues. This indicates that CSR became a great concern for both businesses and governments and that the relationship between businesses and society had a new dimension regarding societal concerns in the 1960s. This decade had several important social movements such as civil rights, women’s rights, consumers’ rights, and

environmental movements (Carroll *et al.*, 2010). They add that “the foundation for CSR was being developed by a quickly changing social environment and pressures from others, especially activists, to adopt CSR perspectives, attitudes, practices, and policies” (p. 87).

Carroll (1999) points to another prominent scholar of CSR in the 1960s who was Joseph McGuire. This scholar composed a book in 1963 entitled ‘Business and Society’ in which he stated: “The idea of social responsibilities supposes that the corporation has not only economic and legal obligations but also certain responsibilities to society which extend beyond these obligations” (McGuire, 1963, p. 144, as cited in Carroll, 1999, p. 271). This projection of CSR posited by McGuire in the 1960s depicted the fundamentals that construct CSR’s dimensions in the following decades. The two main dimensions that are suggested by McGuire were economic and legal dimensions which formulate the basics of CSR concept and the basics of the connection between businesses and society. McGuire also referred to other obligations (i.e., dimensions) in his projection of CSR but he had not clearly specified what could be these extended obligations (Carroll, 1999). Clarence Walton—who is described as a foremost thinker in business and society—has a significant contribution concerning CSR during the late 1960s through his book entitled ‘Corporate Social Responsibility’ (Carroll, 2008). According to Moura-Leite *et al.* (2011), the work of Walton has an ethics-oriented argument to CSR and it shows that the involvements’ costs of social events may have not a computable earnings. Other scholars who have tackled the concept of CSR during the 1960s include Robert Blomstrom, George Goyder, and William Frederick (see, for example, Carroll, 1999; Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011; Ohlrich 2011; Rahman 2011). Thus, the period of the 1960s paved the road for the coming scholars in the 1970s and offered a more clear way to follow on CSR’s related issues. In addition, an indication to

the ethical component of CSR was offered during this period which was more adopted with additional components of CSR in the next decade.

The period of the 1970s is considered by Carroll (2008) as the decade in which CSR accelerates and in which CSR's definitions proliferate. Many authors during this period focused on the content and implementation process of CSR which does not oppose the basic interests of businesses (Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011). The 1970s was a period of flourishing for CSR and different researchers had made many definitions and more clarifications about the concept of CSR. According to Carroll and Shabana (2010), in the 1970s, formal definitions of CSR began to proliferate and several other related concepts to CSR became an object of discussion such as corporate social responsiveness and corporate social performance (CSP). One prominent scholar who had investigated differences between CSR and CSP during the 1970s was S. Sethi who discussed CSP's dimensions and showed differences between various corporate behaviors known as 'social obligations', 'social responsibilities', and 'social responsiveness' (Carroll, 2008). CSR definitions thrive in this decade and businesspersons were considerably involved in philanthropic acts and other community activities (Rahman, 2011). Rahman adds that these definitions stressed on the inclusion of stakeholders needed for matching public anticipations and utilization of CSR for long-term benefit of the societies. Those stakeholders include other interested groups rather than only shareholders themselves such as society, local communities, customers, suppliers, and others.

According to Carroll *et al.* (2010), corporate social performance (CSP)—as an economic concept—impressively emerged in the mid-1970s. The Committee for Economic Development (CED)—which consists of a group of advisors, businesspersons, and instructors residing in the U.S.A.—had a momentous contribution

to CSR during the 1970s. The CED published in 1971 a publication dubbed ‘Social Responsibilities of Business Corporations’ in which CED observed the functions of business by public consent and it maintained at the same time that the business fundamental purpose is to serve practically the needs of society to the extent of granting the satisfaction to the society itself (Carroll, 1999). The CED suggested a model of three-concentric circles to define the social responsibility in which the inner circle comprises the specific basic responsibilities related to executing economic functions, the intermediate circle includes the responsibility needed to practice the economic functions of CSR maintaining a sensitive awareness of changing social values and priorities, and the last and outer circle consists of newly evolving and formless responsibilities which a business should undertake to be more involved in reinforcing the social environment (Carroll, 2008). Two other authors on CSR during the 1970s were Henry Eilbert and I. Parket who tackled the status of CSR during that period, attempted to associate CSR with organizational variables, and suggested that CSR consists of diverse activities (Carroll, 1999).

From the writings of those scholars who contributed to CSR issues during the 1970s, a consensus regarding the definition of CSR as a link between businesses and society can be found and that economic and legal components are the fundamentals of CSR. A major portion of those scholars also stressed on the postulation that there are additional components standing beside the two fundamental components of CSR. Although they had not obviously articulated what could be these additional components but their writings referred to several implied meanings such as moral, ethical, philanthropic, charitable, voluntary, and problem-solving meanings. In the late 1970s and specifically in 1979, Archie B. Carroll suggested an inclusive structure in which he theoretically tackled existent and new suggested components of CSR. This structure is one of the

most acceptable and recognizable structures among academics and researchers of SIM field for its comprehensibility, appropriateness, and contemporariness. In this structure, Carroll proposed a four-part conceptualization of CSR which expresses logically the idea that the corporation has not only economic and legal responsibilities but also ethical and philanthropic as well (Carroll, 1979). According to Moura-Leite *et al.* (2011), during the 1970s many scholars focused on the content and application process of CSR which do not oppose the primary interests of different businesses. Moreover, the 1970s was a decade which statutory initiatives mandated corporations to establish organizational systems to comply with laws coping with environment, product and worker safety, and employment discrimination (Carroll, 2008). Among other significant researchers who prevailed the 1970s are Harold Johnson, George Steiner, Keith Davis, Richard Eels, Clarence Walton, Dow Votaw, Lee Preston, James Post, Henry Manne, Henry Wallich, Sandra Holmes, Thomas Zenisek, R. Ackerman, H. Eilbert, I. Parket, and William Frederick (see, for example, Carroll, 1999; Carroll, 2008; McClerkin, 2013; Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011; Rahman, 2011).

The decade of the 1980s was a decade in which complementary themes to CSR were ascended (Carroll, 2008). Many socio-economic concepts were reinvestigated and developed during the 1980s due to the abundant definitions suggested during the 1970s by different scholars and business people. Among these socio-economic concepts were CSP, corporate social responsiveness, stakeholder theory, public policy, and business ethics (Carroll, 1999; Carroll, 2008; Wissink, 2012). The interest in CSR has not been reduced but it was reformed into other optional concepts, theories, and models (Carroll, 1999). According to Carroll and Shabana (2010), the 1980s produced fewer definitions of CSR but more empirical researches and more alternative themes. In this decade also,

business and social interests approached and various enterprises came to be more responsive to their stakeholders (Moura-Leite *et al.*, 2011).

One of the first scholars who tackled CSR in the early 1980s was Thomas Jones who defined CSR as “the notion that corporations have an obligation to constituent groups in society other than stockholders and beyond that prescribed by law and union contract” (Jones, 1980, pp. 59-60, as cited in Carroll, 1999, p. 284). Jones added that there are two facets of this definition: (i) the first is that the obligation must be adopted voluntary; and (ii) the second is that the obligation should be extended beyond the conventional duty to shareholders and should reach other social groups such as customers and local communities. At the same decade, there was a tendency towards investigating more the relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance (CFP) for different enterprises. Business people, scholars, and academics wanted to know more if CSR and social activities could affect positively or negatively the CFP of corporations. Carroll *et al.* (2010) contended that the decade of the 1980s witnessed a proliferation in researches trying to find the nature of the link between CSR and CFP. In 1984, another scholar, Peter Drucker, asserted that CSR could represent a business opportunity for businesses since it can enhance the financial profitability (Drucker, 1984, as cited in Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011, p. 533). Following researchers performed many empirical studies on the relationship between CSR and CFP and a major portion of these studies asserted on the positive role that CSR has on the enterprises’ CFP. Moura-Leite and Padgett (2011) mentioned that other scholars had performed researches to find out about the ways in which financial and social outcomes were implemented in the past and that they found an affirmative relationship between these outcomes.

In 1982, T. Donaldson considered the relationship between business and society from the side of the social contract tradition assuming at the same time that there is an implied social contract between business and society (Donaldson, 1982, as cited in Moura-Leite *et al.*, 2011, p. 532). Among other significant scholars during the 1980s was R. Edward Freeman who composed a momentous book entitled ‘Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach’ in which he tackled different aspects concerning shareholders and other stakeholders (Freeman, 1984). He maintained that CSR is often viewed as an add-on to business as usual and that business people consider it as a fine issue if they can afford it. Further writings of Freeman *et al.* (2010) asserted that intentions behind the concept of CSR are better satisfied when thinking about responsibility of a corporate’s stakeholder. Those scholars maintained and concluded their writings by saying that “stakeholder theory can add value to the future development of CSR by better specifying and integrating financial and social concern” (Freeman *et al.*, 2010, p. 236). This shows the importance that stakeholder theory holds regarding CSR and its prospective implementations in different societies by various enterprises. In general, Freeman (1984) through his postulated stakeholder theory strategically and economically linked businesses with their shareholders and other concerned stakeholders in societies and spawned at the same time a parallel linkage between this theory and the CSR’s other issues. Several other authors and scholars contributed to CSR’s issues during the 1980s. Among those scholars are L. Preston, J. Post, Frank Tuzzolino, Barry Armandi, D. Dalton, R. Cosier, Steven Wartick, Philip Cochran, Edwin Epstein, and Rich Strand (see, for example, Carroll, 1999; Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011; Rahman, 2011).

To conclude the period of the 1980s, CSR various activities adopted by commercial enterprises augmented their reputations and accordingly augmented loyalty of their

customers which led at the end to improved levels of profitability (Rahman, 2011). Additional concepts beyond CSR were remarkably presented during this decade such as CSP, corporate social responsiveness, business ethics, and the argumentative relationship between CSR and CFP.

The ten years of the 1990s were described by Carroll (2008) as the years in which CSR serves as a base-point for other complementary and alternative themes. According to Rahman (2011), few new definitions of CSR were composed during the nineties which contributed in a new phenomenon in this definition. Other socio-economic concepts that exhaustively tackled in the 1990s were CSP, corporate social responsiveness, stakeholder management theory, corporate citizenship, linkage between CSR and CFP, and business ethics theory (Carroll, 1999; Carroll, 2008). Starting from the 1990s up until the early 2010s, the concept of CSR has become comprehensively approved and supported by many scholars, business people, and other entities including governments, enterprises, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), customers, and even international bodies of the world such as the United Nations (UN), the World Bank, and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (Lee, 2008). Lee maintained that the U.S. magazine 'Fortune' conducted a study about the companies of 'Fortune 500'—a list of the 500 largest U.S. companies—in 1977 and in 1990 and concluded that less than half of the 500 U.S. companies had CSR activities in their annual report in 1977 whereas more than 90% of these companies enthusiastically reported CSR activities in their annual report in 1990 and mentioned CSR as a basic element of their organizational goals. This reflects the changes in the way that different people think about CSR and in the culture towards CSR and its related activities. Enterprises with their business executives managed CSR in the 1990s as a source of increasing their reputation, their market share, and consequently their profitability. During the 1990s,

the interest on CSR studies has moved away from an ethical perspective into a performance perspective and the level of analyzing CSR issues has changed away from a macro-social level into an organizational level (Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011).

One of the major contributors to CSR issues in the early 1990s was Donna Wood who revisited in 1991 the CSP concept suggested by Carroll in 1979 (Carroll, 1999). According to Wood (1991), the basic idea of CSR is that business and society are interlinked rather than being discrete things and this enables the society to have specific anticipations for behaviors and outcomes that should be done properly by businesses. The CSP model that was built by Carroll in 1979 has three main components which are CSR, corporate social responsiveness, and social issues. This model was revised by Wood in 1991 where she firstly interwove CSR's components (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic) with new principles, namely, institutional principle, organizational principle, and individual principle respectively. The second component of the Carroll's CSP model, namely, corporate social responsiveness, was described by Carroll (1979) to emphasize action, defense, accommodation, and proaction. Wood related this concept with other managerial theories such as stakeholder theory posited by R. Edward Freeman in 1984, environmental assessment, and other management issues. The third component of CSP is the involved social issues in which Carroll (1979) suggested several issues to include such as consumerism, environment, discrimination, occupational and product safety, and shareholders. Revisions of Wood (1991) for this component included turning these social issues into outcomes of corporate behaviors that imply social impacts, social programs, and social policies. Moura-Leite *et al.* (2011) maintain that Wood's revised model of CSP in 1991 is considerably more comprehensive than the model suggested by Carroll in 1979.

Other important contribution to CSR literature was achieved by Archie Carroll himself in 1991 when he revisited his four-part CSR model suggested in 1979 and revised it into his renowned pyramid of CSR (Carroll, 1991). This new structure of CSR graphically depicted a pyramid of CSR in which economic responsibilities settled in the base of the pyramid, legal and ethical responsibilities come respectively on top of the base, and philanthropic responsibilities located at the pinnacle of the pyramid. According to Carroll (1991), the economic component of Carroll's pyramid of CSR focuses on the foundation upon which all other components rest and it directs corporations to be profitable. However, the legal component stresses on the fact that law is the society's codification of right and wrong and it directs businesses to obey the law. The next third component is the ethical one which requires enterprises to be ethical and it stresses on having obligation to do what is right, just, and fair, and at the same time to avoid harm. The last component is the philanthropic one which stresses on contributing resources to the community and improving quality of life and it directs enterprises to be a good corporate citizen (Carroll, 1991). In 1994, a survey was conducted by Carroll in a quest to find out what topics management researchers thought were essential during the 1990s (Carroll, 1994). He suggested CSP concept instead of CSR to emphasize that the concept of CSR is primarily contained in CSP. The scholar observed through the analysis of the survey's results that CSP ranked in an advanced position in the list and preceded other social issues such as environmental issues, strategic issues, corporate governance, and stakeholders' issues. Carroll (1994) maintained that the succeeded social issues in the resulted list definitely imply CSR topics considering that CSR cannot be analytically extracted into a specific lonely category.

The decade of the 1990s had many other scholars who tackled in-depth CSR issues and among those scholars are Sophia Muirhead, M. Hopkin, S. Waddock, T. Jones, and J.

Elkington (see, for example, Carroll, 2008; McClerklin, 2013; Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011; Rahman, 2011).

2.4 CSR in the 21st Century

The concept of CSR during the 2000s and beyond is portrayed as the period of refinements, researches, alternative themes, management practice, and global expansion (Carroll, 2008). The view of CSR in the 21st century stresses more on ethical and philanthropic responsibilities that different enterprises and SOEs—that have commercial and profitable objectives—possess towards their societies. Carroll (1991) summarized CSR's ethical and philanthropic components in his pyramid of CSR by implying them in the states of being ethical and being a good corporate citizen respectively. Other researchers and business practitioners argue that CSR and its complementary issues have dramatically thrived during the 1990s up to the 21st century. For example, the weekly British magazine known as 'The Economist' points to the fact that CSR movement flowered in the decade of the 1990s and is carrying forward into the 2000s (Carroll, 2004). Moreover, The U.S. scholar, David Vogel, contended that CSR is vital for corporates' profitability and that the concept of CSR is developed during the 2000s to be a core business function which is pivotal for the corporate's overall strategy and success (Vogel, 2005). He maintained that the influence of CSR's business case had affected even the strategies of some NGOs. According to Carroll *et al.* (2010), the business case here refers to the primary rationales supporting why the business community should accept CSR cause. Vogel (2005) claimed that NGOs frequently incite corporations to behave more responsibly because doing so represents a good business for them. Among other notions that have attracted business community which appeared during the early 2000s were sustainability and sustainable development

which comprise an integral part of all debates concerning CSR (Carroll and Shabana, 2010).

McClerklin (2013) concludes that the developments of CSR concept from the mid-1980s until the 21st century happened in many aspects. He adds that CSR values and ethical issues represented a significant focus in this period and that the stakeholder theory posited by R. Edward Freeman in 1984 is included in many debates about CSR. He maintains that talks and questions about CSR in the 21st century found a strong linkage between CSR and CFP theories and that the discussions of CSR during this period caused the proliferation of CSR standards, certification, and reporting tools. One of the scholars who discussed CSR with other legal aspects is Doreen McBarnet who authored with others in 2009 a book entitled ‘The New Corporate Accountability: Corporate Social Responsibility and the Law’ in which they have included notions, perceptions, and observations concerning CSR in the 21st century (McBarnet *et al.*, 2009, as cited in Rahman, 2011, p. 172). Those researchers—headed by McBarnet—maintained that the 21st century is the epoch of emerging CSR industry where large corporations possess dedicated CSR departments and employ CSR managers and consultants. They added that law and accounting companies tackle CSR issues and cases in their fields and that universities periodically hold CSR conferences and their researchers contribute more to CSR literature day after another. They mentioned that also publishers and journalists participate in the regular activities related to CSR issues. Moreover, Rahman (2011) indicated that another vital aspect that grew in the 2000s was CSR reporting which became a compulsory activity in many countries. He points out that many organizations publish their annual reports that include CSR reports online as a transparent action for all interested individuals and especially stakeholders.

One of the contemporary researchers asserts that although its current popularity, CSR continues to be a vague and much argumentative concept in the 21st century (Pedersen, 2006). He adds that from a more practical perspective, CSR also remains difficult to operationalize. This is attributed to the prolific definitions, models, and related theories posited by many scholars and researchers belonging to various business schools during the 20th and 21st centuries. On the other hand, Harrison *et al.* (1999) argue that empirical studies concerning CSR are less conducted by researchers and that these studies are still in the early stage during the last 20th century. This passively influences the process of uniting definitions, concepts, opinions, and models concerning CSR which if achieved it could contribute in positively revealing more about CSR and its related issues. Accordingly, Carroll (2008) through his writings points out to this issue by considering the 2000s as the decade in which the emphasis on theoretical contributions and meanings concerned with CSR concept has given in to empirical researches on CSR and its complementary and alternative themes such as business ethics, stakeholder theory, sustainability, and corporate citizenship.

Carroll (2008) also maintains that the period from 2001 to 2002 was prevailed by empirical researches linking CSR and CSP to other relevant variables. The propensity for introducing new concepts of CSR diminished during this period and the efforts were directed towards investigating and considering comprehensively available CSR various themes and other related managerial issues. For instance, the empirical works of a group of scholars—headed by Kristin Backhaus—in 2002 studied the relationship between CSP and the employer attractiveness. Those researchers observed that job seekers do consider CSP to be essential in their assessment of firms. Moreover, they found out that the most vital dimensions of CSP are environment, community relations, employee relations, diversity, and product issues (Backhaus *et al.*, 2002, as cited in Carroll, 2008,

p. 40). It was apparent to academics, businesspersons, and even officials that CSR movement has turned into a global phenomenon during the 2000s and that the European Community witnessed more interest and growth of CSR in this period (Carroll, 2008). Writings of André Habisch and other scholars in 2005 were included in one book labeled ‘Corporate Social Responsibility Across Europe’ in which Habisch edited the writings which documented the phenomenon of spreading CSR across Europe (Habisch *et al.*, 2005, as cited in Carroll, 2008, p. 42). Those scholars claimed that CSR was unknown in the past and now it becomes as one of the most significant issues tackled by businesspersons, politicians, NGOs, and even consumers.

Among those other scholars who investigated CSR and related themes such as CSP, stakeholder theory, and business ethics during the 2000s are Bryan Husted, Tim Rowley, Shwan Berman, Jennifer Griffin, Ray Jones, Audrey Murrell, Mark Schwartz, Philip Kotler, Nancy Lee, and Jeremy Moon (see, for example, Carroll, 2008).

2.5 CSR Theories, Principles, and Models

The significance of CSR during the last three decades was pervasive in different aspects of business and management in developed and also developing countries. Researchers and academics have investigated CSR concept and its complementary themes and postulated many principles, theories, terminologies, and models which helped in understanding CSR more and in understanding its effect on other aspects of the managerial issues. As Carroll and Shabana (2010) state: “Today, one cannot pick up a newspaper, magazine, or journal without encountering some discussion of the issue, some recent or innovative example of what business is thinking or doing about CSR, or some new conference that is being held” (p. 85). Accordingly, this section tackles only the most important principles, theories, and models of CSR whereas other less

significant principles, theories, and models are condoned due to the abundance of them in the literature and due to their farness of the scope of this study.

The way that scholars have tackled the theories of CSR differs from one scholar to another based on their understanding for the term “theory” per se. For example, some of them consider that the concept of CSR theory is related to the chronological process of CSR’s development and advancement. One of those scholars is Min-Dong Lee (2008) who traced the conceptual evolutionary path of theories on CSR and considered CSR development’s implications. Lee (2008) claims that two extensive shifts have occurred in the conceptualization of CSR. The first shift has occurred in terms of the level of analysis where scholars have moved from discussing the macro-social effects of CSR to discussing instead the organizational-level analysis of CSR’s effects on profitability. The second shift has happened in terms of theoretical orientation where researchers have moved from implicitly ethics-oriented arguments to implicitly normative and performance-oriented managerial studies. An evolution of the theory of CSR is traced and documented by Lee in 2008 while emphasizing the relative modernity of CSR concept. This scholar maintained that over the years the concept of CSR has been gradually developed through a number of revolutionary studies (Lee, 2008). He summarized CSR theories (i.e., studies) according to the decades of the 20th century and considered them as the theoretical trends in CSR thinking. According to Lee (2008), the dominant theme in the theoretical trends in CSR thinking during the decades of 1950s and 1960s was the ethics and social obligation of businesses and that there was a very high level of uncertainty with CSR during this period. In the decade of 1970s, enlightened self-interest was the dominant theme of CSR thinking and that the level of CSR uncertainty was still high. The period of the eighties (i.e., 1980s) contained the dominant theme of CSP model which was suggested by Archie Carroll in the late 1970s

and then reviewed by Donna Wood in the late 1980s. The level of uncertainty during this decade decreased and theoretical trends of CSR directed to studying CSR and CFP relationship. The last theoretical trend in CSR thinking investigated by scholar Lee was the dominant theme known as the stakeholder approach and strategic management during the decade of the 1990s. According to Lee (2008), a tight coupling between CSR and CFP prevailed in CSR theory during this period with a low level of uncertainty with CSR.

An interesting study concerning mapping the territory of CSR theories was performed by the scholars Elisabet Garriga and Domènec Melé in 2004. In this study, those researchers categorized the primary CSR theories into four groups, namely, instrumental theories, political theories, integrative theories, and ethical theories. They rationally found out that each group of CSR theories portrays four dimensions concerned with profits, political performance, social demands, and ethical values. Each group of theories contains a number of approaches suggested by different scholars in different periods of time through the development of CSR concept. These approaches detail the type of theories that they belong to and contend at the same time on their respective dimension among the previous mentioned four dimensions. According to Garriga *et al.* (2004), the first type of theories is the instrumental theories which concentrates on achieving economic objectives through social activities. There are three main approaches related to instrumental theories, namely, the approach of maximization the shareholder value which deals with maximizing the long-term value of the corporate, the approach of strategies for competitive advantage which focuses on achieving social achievements in a competitive context, and the approach of cause-related marketing which involves doing altruistic activities which are socially recognized to be used as an instrument of marketing. The second type of CSR theories

is the political theories which focuses on the responsible use of business power in the political arena. Three main approaches represent these theories which are the corporate constitutionalism that is based on the dogma that social responsibilities of corporates stem from their amount of possessed social power, the integrative social contract theory which assumes an existence of social contract between business and society, and the third approach about the corporate citizenship concept which supposes that a corporate is understood as a citizen with specific involvements in the community.

The integrative theories represent the third type of CSR theories suggested by Garriga *et al.* (2004) and these theories focus on the integration of social demands. There are four approaches belong to this type of CSR theories, namely, issues management which involve corporate processes related to social and political issues, public responsibility which involves law and existing public policy process related to social performance, stakeholder management which balances the interests of the corporate's stakeholders, and the last approach is the CSP which focuses on social legitimacy and processes supporting social issues. According to Garriga and Melé (2004), the last category of CSR theories is the ethical theories which concentrate on the right thing to do and the necessity for achieving a good society. The same researchers maintain that there are four approaches revolve around these ethical theories. The first approach is the stakeholder normative theory that considers fiduciary duties towards stakeholders of the enterprise. The second approach is about the universal rights which are the frameworks based on the human and labor rights, and respecting the environment. The third approach is the sustainable development which aims at achieving human development considering present and prospective generations. The last approach is the common good which is oriented towards the society's common good contributed specifically by businesses (Garriga *et al.*, 2004).

Scholars that have tackled the principles of CSR have also diverse methods and speculations. This is because of the relatively long period that it has taken to admit CSR as a vital concept in management and business sciences. Crowther *et al.* (2008) argue that it is difficult to be certain about any of the activities concerned with CSR. The same researchers claim that there are three principles forming all CSR activities which are sustainability, accountability, and transparency. According to Crowther and Aras (2008), the first principle of CSR activities is sustainability which is concerned with the effects on available options in the future caused by taken actions in the present. They add that sustainability involves that society should not consume more of a resource than it can be generated. They point out that practically most organizations in different sectors have a tendency to be unsustainable by increasing the way in which resources are utilized. The second principle—that those two researchers refer to—is the accountability which is concerned with the organization's recognition of its actions that affect external environment while assuming responsibility for the effects of these actions. They argue that accountability entails the organization to furnish external stakeholders with required periodic reports concerning the actions taken by this organization. The researchers maintain that accountability calls for the development of proper measures of environmental performance by organizations and also a better reporting of taken actions by those organizations to their all stakeholders. The third principle of CSR is the transparency which focuses on the dogma that the external impact of the taken actions by an organization can be determined through the organization's reporting itself with emphasizing the principle that the related information should not be concealed in the reporting process. The same researchers contend that transparency as a principle of CSR is considerably important for external users for such information and that transparency can be considered as preservation for

other two principles (i.e., sustainability and accountability). In addition, it can be considered alike as a part of the process of recognizing required responsibility by the organization towards stakeholders (Crowther and Aras, 2008).

Among other researchers who tackled the principles of CSR is Subhabrata Banerjee (2007) in the book entitled 'Corporate Social Responsibility: the Good, the Bad, and the Ugly.' Banerjee claims that consequent development occurred on the Carroll's (1979) CSP model implied identifying principles concerning the components of CSP model (i.e., CSR, corporate social responsiveness, and corporate behaviors' outcomes). These proposed principles of CSR are able to be used at institutional, organizational, and managerial different levels. The same principles of CSR were also suggested by Wood (1991) in her paper that revisited the concept of CSP. She claimed that a review of the literature regarding CSR principles showed that there are three conceptually expectations forming these principles. Wood added that these three levels of analysis are institutional, organizational, and individual. Through these CSR principles, Wood postulated three corresponding principles of CSR, namely, the principle of legitimacy which its level of application is the institutional one, the principle of public responsibility which its level of application is the organizational one, and the principle of managerial discretion which its level of application is the individual one. These proposed principles by Wood focus on different issues such as obligations and sanctions on institutional level, behavioral parameters for organizations on organizational level, and choice, opportunity, and personal responsibility on individual level.

Accordingly and based on the reviews of Wood's (1991) paper, Banerjee postulates that principles of CSR that operate at the institutional level focus on the legitimacy of business in society accompanied by business obligations to society and sanctions that

society can apply to business when it fails to match its obligations. He adds that parameters specifying legitimacy are determined sometimes using a system of rules and exclusions which do not deal with marginalized groups' concerns in societies. Based on the writings of the Banerjee, the second principle of CSR is the one concerned with public responsibility which operates at the organizational level. This principle is used to make larger societal concern more relevant through providing behavioral parameters for organizations on the basis of relating issues to the enterprise's activities and interests. The last principle of CSR that Banerjee tackles is the one related to the managerial level which it focuses on strategic choices, options, and personal responsibilities of managers in fulfilling institutional and organizational social goals. Banerjee contends that managers' role in accommodating stakeholder interests is predefined at higher levels, and accompanied practices in this level are ruled by both institutional and organizational discussions and communications. Eventually, the same scholar inquires about this vital principle and states: "Do managers really have genuine freedom to make socially responsible decisions?" (Banerjee, 2007, p. 21).

Many researchers and scholars suggested and discussed different models for describing CSR and its related activities (Carroll, 1991; Certo & Certo, 2009; Davis, 1975; Wood, 1991; Zu, 2009). These models are used based on the purposes that could be utilized by other subsequent generations of researchers and scholars. According to Zu (2009), most of CSR models focus on the argument whether business is a single dimensional entity for maximizing profit or a multi-dimensional entity helping considerably societal interests. Writings of Zu imply three classifications for CSR models which are social-economic model, stakeholder model, and triple-bottom line model. The first category of CSR model is the social-economic model which has two groups of researchers with a specific view for each group. Zu adds that the first group represents the conventional

model that stresses on having only a single dimensional activity for the business social responsibility which requires corporations to offer products and services for society in return for a profit. The second group of scholars investigated by Zu considers the social contribution of corporations to the welfare of society as a whole which reinforces the opinion that businesses have more responsibilities beyond the principle of profit maximization. The second postulated model of CSR by Zu is the stakeholder model of CSR in which researchers are divided into two main groups, namely, the market stakeholders and the non-market stakeholders. Zu considers that the market stakeholders are the primary ones who engage in direct economic reciprocal exchange with the corporate such as shareholders, customers, employees, and suppliers whereas non-market stakeholders are those who do not engage in direct economic exchange with the enterprise including communities, various levels of government, media, and NGOs. Writings of Zu consider that the stakeholder model of CSR was founded by scholars for its great practicality over other CSR theoretical suggested models. For this reason, Zu (2009) states: “The stakeholder model solved the problem of measurement and testing by more narrowly identifying the actors and defining their positions and function in relation to one another” (p. 26). It is also essential to mention that the stakeholder model of CSR has a significant potential to come to be the central and vital model for business and society field and this includes CSR as a major component of such relationship (Jones, 1995). The last model of CSR suggested by Zu is the triple-bottom line (TBL) model of CSR which combines financial, social, and environmental factors into the corporate’s obligation to growth and sustainable profitability. Zu describes the concept of TBL as the spectrum of economic, environmental, and social criteria and as the values needed for measuring organizational and societal success for an enterprise. He contends that TBL approach could be more confident through relating the stakeholder

model to CSR with the three dimensions comprising the TBL concept per se (i.e., economic, environmental, and social). Zu (2009) states that “TBL has stimulated much corporate activity and has generated tools that can yield quantified expressions of triple-bottom line performance; cover the full ground of sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR)” (p. 31). He concluded the third category of CSR models, namely, the triple-bottom line model of CSR, by considering that this model requires the corporate’s responsibility be directed at stakeholders with its large meaning rather than directing it towards only shareholders or owners.

Other well-known models of CSR subsisting in the literature include Keith Davis’ model of CSR (1975) and Archie Carroll’s model of CSR (1991). Davis (1975) postulated a model of CSR in which he mentioned five propositions that an organization should follow to be socially responsible towards society and the organization itself. These five propositions include: (i) proposition 1: social responsibility arises from social power; (ii) proposition 2: business shall operate as a two-way open system, with open receipt of inputs from society and open disclosure of its operations to the public; (iii) proposition 3: the social costs and benefits of an activity, product, or service shall be thoroughly calculated and considered in deciding whether to proceed with it; (iv) proposition 4: the social costs related to each activity, product, or service shall be passed on to the consumer; and (v) proposition 5: business institutions, as citizens, have the responsibility to become involved in certain social problems that are outside their normal areas of operation (Davis, 1975). The last model developed by Archie Carroll in 1991 is detailed in the next section.

2.6 Archie Carroll's Social Model of CSP and Pyramid of CSR

As discussed previously, there are several models that describe and adopt the concept of CSR in the literature. Among these models are the models proposed by the scholar Archie Carroll. To explain more about this researcher of SIM field, Garriga *et al.* (2004) consider Archie Carroll as one of the most prominent scholars in the discipline of CSR. Carroll's first model is the one postulated in 1979 for CSP in which CSR is embedded in this model as a separate and full dimension. Later, this separate dimension of CSR was more comprehensively represented by the Carroll's pyramid of CSR—suggested in 1990—which has attracted the attentions and approvals of diverse scholars and researchers of the SIM field during the last decades of the 20th century and the early decades of the 21st century. Wood (2010) states: “Carroll's pyramid made intuitive sense to many as a way of describing the full set of managerial duties in social responsibility terms” (p. 53). Accordingly, the two subsequent subsections discuss the Carroll's model of CSP and the Carroll's pyramid of CSR respectively.

2.6.1 Archie Carroll's Model of CSP

For nearly more than 34 years, Archie Carroll's model of CSP—which was postulated in 1979—is recognized as one of the most acceptable and recognizable approaches among the researchers of the SIM field and among other social practitioners interested in CSR and CSP issues. According to Wood (1991), Carroll's model of CSP is still among others which is used today as an independent and implicitly competing model for thinking about CSR. The writings of Lee (2008) claim that the CSP model of Carroll became one of the most broadly cited articles in the literature concerning the field of business and society. Many researchers discussed the model from different sides with explaining its practical usage and dimensions (Azzellino, 2011; Carroll, 1979, 1991, 1999, 2000, 2004, 2008; Carroll & Buchholtz, 2009; Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Duarte,

Mouro, & Das Neves, 2010; Garriga & Melé, 2004; Jones, 1995; Lee, 2008; Kolb, 2008; McWilliams & Siegel, 2001; Moura-Leite & Padgett, 2011). One of the other researchers even reviewed and revised the Carroll's CSP model (Wood 1991; Wood, 2010).

The definition of CSP is included in the Wood's (1991) in which she states that it is “a business organization's configuration of principles of social responsibility, processes of social responsiveness, and policies, programs, and observable outcomes as they relate to the firm's societal relationships” (p. 693). In a try to relate CSP concept to the corporate's performance concerning major social activities, Wood argues that CSP concept can be measured through three types of measurements which are: (i) the degree to which principles of social responsibility stimulate actions taken by the corporate; (ii) the degree to which the corporate exploits socially responsive processes; and (iii) the subsistence of policies and programs used to manage the societal relationships of the corporate. Carroll *et al.* (2009) argue that the process of developing a conceptual framework for CSP should identify the nature of CSR's four categories of responsibilities (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic), identify also a specific philosophy, pattern, strategy of responsiveness, and finally identify the stakeholder issues to which these responsibilities are revealed.

The model of CSP postulated by Carroll (1979) comprises three key distinct dimensions that must be interrelated to achieve a desirable level of social performance for a business. According to Carroll *et al.* (2009), the first dimension of the Carroll's CSP model is the corporate social responsibility with its four categories (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic). The second dimension is the philosophy of social responsiveness (e.g., reaction, defense, accommodation, and proaction), and the third

dimension is the social issues (i.e., stakeholder issues) that imply for example consumers, employees, environment, and others. Figure 2.1. shows Carroll’s model of CSP postulated by Archie Carroll in 1979 which is graphically depicted as a cube with three main axes, namely, social responsibility, philosophy of social responsiveness, and social issues involving stakeholders. The cube that represents Carroll’s CSP model contains 96 cells—which can be increased or decreased based on the number of included issues—in which CSP could probably be evaluated (Wood, 2010).

Source: Archie B. Carroll, "A Three-Dimensional Conceptual Model of Corporate Social Performance," *Academy of Management Review* (Vol. 4, No. 4, 1979), 503.

Figure 2.1.: Archie B. Carroll’s CSP Model (Carroll, 1979)

From the Carroll’s CSP model shown in Figure 2.1., Carroll *et al.* (2009) maintain that the dimension of CSR emphasizes obligation or accountability whereas the dimension of corporate social responsiveness emphasizes action (i.e., activity) and that the overall CSP emphasizes the outcomes or results. They argue that this model of CSP is instrumental for managers because it assists them to understand that social

responsibility is not separated from economic performance since it integrates economic activities into a social performance framework and it puts ethical and philanthropic responsibilities into a rational economic and legal framework. The same researchers add that the model also is beneficial for academics since it represents a conceptual aid for understanding the differences among the concepts of CSR existent in the literature such as responsibility, responsiveness, stakeholders, and other social issues. In this way, another scholar, Lee (2008), states: “the purpose of the model was to help clarify and integrate various definitional strands that have appeared in the literature” (p. 60). He adds that the most significant contribution of the Carroll’s CSP model is in its three-dimensional structure which does not deal with the enterprise’s economic and social goals as mismatched trade-offs but it instead integrates them into the framework of total social responsibility of business that comprises economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities.

2.6.2 Archie Carroll’s Pyramid of CSR

Concerning the first dimension of the CSP model, namely, corporate social responsibility, Carroll’s definition of CSR exists amid those definitions which have suggested the broader range of obligations towards society (Schwartz *et al.*, 2003). Writings of Carroll (1979) implied that social responsibility has been defined or conceptualized in different ways by different researchers and in these diverse conceptualizations the term CSR includes a vast range of economic, legal, and voluntary activities. Carroll accordingly postulated his four-part definition of CSR in 1979 which involves what a business could have of different types of social responsibilities towards society. He contends that for having a definition of social responsibility which entirely addresses a business’s whole range of responsibilities to society, this definition should express the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary

categories of the business performance. Carroll himself later replaced the term ‘discretionary’ with the term ‘philanthropic’ in his articles published during the early 1990s and onward. According to Carroll *et al.* (2009), the four-part definition puts economic and legal expectations of business in surrounding environment by associating them more with socially oriented concerns including ethical and discretionary or philanthropic responsibilities. For making the concept of the four-part definition of CSR easier to be imagined and remembered, a graphical depiction was posited by Carroll in 1991. He suggested a pyramid that is consisted of four layers comprising the four parts of CSR definition (economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities). This graphical illustration is known as the pyramid of corporate social responsibility and is shown in Figure 2.2.

Source: Archie B. Carroll, "The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the Moral Management of Organizational Stakeholders," *Business Horizons* (July–August 1991), 42.

Figure 2.2.: Archie B. Carroll's Pyramid of CSR (Carroll, 1991)

Figure 2.2. holds a brief description for each component comprising the Carroll's pyramid of CSR which contains the economic responsibilities in the base of the pyramid, the legal responsibilities positioned one layer above the base, the ethical responsibilities located two layers above the base, and the philanthropic responsibilities that stand at the pyramid's peak. According to Wood (2010), Carroll's pyramid of CSR still an appreciated depiction and a popular model amid CSP scholars. Carroll *et al.* (2009) argue that the pyramid of CSR is projected for portraying that the total social responsibility of a business is composed of separated components which can be all together combined to form an entire unified entity, namely, the corporate social responsibility. In a discussion concerning how could CSR and especially its ethical component manages the functions of multinational corporations (MNCs) which have global stakeholders, Archie Carroll argues in his article published in 2004 that the pyramid of CSR—dubbed in this article as the global pyramid of CSR—can be used as an implement that furnishes global managers and their MNCs with a conceptual framework for thinking regarding their variety of expectations. Moreover, he adds that the global pyramid of CSR portrays the whole range of responsibilities that MNCs and their global managers are expected to concurrently achieve (Carroll, 2004).

As mentioned in this section, the pyramid of CSR illustratively represents the four-part definition of CSR posited by Archie Carroll in 1979 and embedded in his model of CSP suggested in the same year. Accordingly, concise explanations and clarifications for the four components contained in this CSR's pyramid are suitable in this study. This due to the fact that these components are believed to considerably influence and control various actions of various enterprises (Carroll, 2000).

In this way, the economic responsibilities are the required and primary responsibilities that a business has. Carroll *et al.* (2009, p. 40) refer to the business by the object 'it' in the following statement and expound the economic component by stating:

It should be an institution whose objective is to produce goods and services that society wants and to sell them at fair prices—prices that society thinks represent the true value of the goods and services delivered and that provide business with profits adequate to ensure its survival and growth and to reward its investors.

According to Carroll (2000), the economic component of CSR refers to the businesses' basic role for being profitable. He adds that although attaining adequate profits by a business is not essential from a societal perspective but it is significant for those persons who engage in a commercial venture. The economic responsibilities are required to be achieved by businesses towards their owners or shareholders and employees since these responsibilities squarely influence those stakeholders (Carroll *et al.*, 2009). According to the writings of Carroll (1991), it is vital to mention that all other responsibilities comprising the three other components of CSR are foreseen upon the economic component of the enterprise because without this component the others come to be a controversial consideration.

The legal responsibilities are the business's second type of responsibilities. They are required to be fulfilled by businesses to have necessary lawful support for achieving economic responsibilities. Carroll *et al.* (2009, p. 41) expound the legal component of CSR by stating:

Legal responsibilities reflect society's view of 'codified ethics' in the sense that they embody basic notions of fair practices as established by our lawmakers. It is business's responsibility to society to comply with these laws.

The same scholars claim that in the past decades, many laws and legislations were sanctioned that attempted to rule the behavior of businesses. In this respect, Carroll (2000) argues that in the 21st century, more legal systems will be enacted and many of

these current laws reflect adequate ethical standards. He adds that in the future, legal responsibility of business will be seen as a tough sphere of activity. The legal responsibilities are required to be done by businesses towards their owners, shareholders, employees, and consumers (Carroll *et al.*, 2009). Legal responsibilities of CSR stand in the second layer of CSR pyramid just one layer above the base (Figure 2.2.) and this reflects their historical development but at the same time they are suitably seen as coexisting with the economic responsibilities of CSR as fundamental principles of the free enterprise system (Carroll, 1991).

The third type of CSR responsibilities is the ethical responsibilities which stand in the third layer of the pyramid of CSR (Figure 2.2.). These responsibilities are in a reciprocal relationship with legal responsibilities since the changes of ethics or values come before the establishment of laws (Carroll *et al.*, 2009). For showing the essence of these expected responsibilities, Carroll (2000, p. 36) states:

Ethical responsibilities embrace a range of norms, standards, or expectations of behavior that reflect a concern for what consumers, employees, shareholders, the community, and other stakeholders regard as fair, right, just, or in keeping with stakeholders' moral rights or legitimate expectations.

The same scholar contends that this component of CSR will be more important in the future than ever due to the fact that businesses have willfully and zealously embraced the notion of business ethics and this drift is expected to continue. Carroll *et al.* (2009) argue that these ethical responsibilities are expected to be fulfilled by businesses for all stakeholders but with specific attention for consumers and employees. According to Visser *et al.* (2010), 'business ethics' is a term that is considered among some researchers as a synonym for CSR and even in sometimes as a subfield of CSR. They add that "business ethics can be seen as the analytical tool that managers and others can use to understand, conceptualise and legitimise the moral status of corporate policies,

strategies and programmes” (p. 46). In this regard, Carroll (1991) maintains that the business ethics movements of the 20th century have steadily established the ethical responsibility as a legitimate CSR component. Through this discussion and views of those researchers, ethical responsibilities can be viewed as the responsibilities of CSR that are related more to the legal responsibilities and not far from economic responsibilities. This is essential to be considered in the mentalities of those who run different for-profit enterprises in order to maintain a balance of achieving a satisfactory profit with considering more ethical responsibilities and eschewing at the same time any expected scandals that could topple these enterprises like the managerial and financial scandals that prevailed during the early 2000s in the world.

The philanthropic (discretionary or voluntary) responsibilities are the last type of responsibilities contained in the Carroll’s pyramid of CSR. A debate regarding this component of CSR exists to whether considering it as a responsibility or as a discretionary or benevolent activity of businesses. In this regard, Carroll *et al.* (2009) stress that these activities could be viewed as responsibilities since they indicate the publics’ current expectations regarding businesses’ activities. For having a close view of these responsibilities, Carroll (1991, p. 42) states:

Philanthropy encompasses those corporate actions that are in response to society's expectation that businesses be good corporate citizens. This includes actively engaging in acts or programs to promote human welfare or goodwill.

A person could have a conflict between identifying ethical and philanthropic responsibilities since the two components are close to each other. Accordingly, Carroll (2000) suggests a slight difference between them by pointing out that the philanthropic responsibilities are not expected by businesses with the same degree of ethical responsibilities. In other writings of Carroll *et al.* (2009), they argue that society considers businesses are either desired or expected to perform philanthropic

responsibilities for communities. They add that philanthropic responsibilities are desired to be fulfilled by corporates towards the community and the employees since these responsibilities affect the morals of employees and their perceived work. Carroll considers the philanthropic component of CSR as the narrow view of a good corporate citizenship whereas he considers the wider view of a good corporate citizenship as the portraying of all four components of CSR (Carroll, 2000).

2.7 Stakeholder Theory and CSR

The debates over the last decades on CSR concept in specific and the relationship between business and society in general had a large pile of articles and books composed by different scholars belonging to diverse cultures and societies. This considerable pile of literature—specifically starting from the first half of the 1980s—was enriched by a new concept known as the stakeholder theory that tried to investigate more the relationship between business and those entities who are internally and externally interested of the outcomes and contributions for businesses, namely, the stakeholders. To support this approach, Freeman *et al.* (2010) claim that “Many philosophers writing on business ethics call for a more explicit connection between stakeholder theory and the more traditional normative ethical theory” (p. xvii). They also support this supposed connection between stakeholder theory and CSR by adding that there are many scholars who have resorted to stakeholder theory to identify better and operationalize the different concepts of CSR. Besides, Park (2010) maintains that stakeholder theory proposes a positive association between CSR activities and the organizational performance which is a pivotal issue for the core of this study. She adds that “CSR can help a company improve a firm’s reputation by serving the implicit claims of major stakeholders (i.e., employees, customers, investors, etc.)” (p. 25). Consequently, it is

important to succinctly analyze the stakeholder theory and its vital and indispensable relationship with CSR concept.

Freeman *et al.* (2010) claim that the stakeholder term can be defined in a number of ways. They divide the stakeholders into two main groups; primary (internal) and secondary (external). The groups of primary stakeholders are “those groups without whose support, the business would cease to be viable” (Freeman *et al.*, 2010, p. 26). They add that the primary stakeholders represent the first or inner circle that surrounds the corporate which includes financiers (shareholders and owners), customers, suppliers, employees, and communities. The same scholars contend that secondary groups of stakeholders affect primary stakeholders. They define the secondary stakeholders as the groups that affect or can be affected by the recognition of an organization’s purpose. Those scholars add that these groups of stakeholders represent the second or outer circle that surrounds the corporate which contains government, competitors, media, special interest groups, and consumer advocate groups.

Writings on stakeholder theory have started within the landmark book entitled ‘Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach’ composed by R. Edward Freeman in 1984. In this book, Freeman provided important fundamentals concerning the stakeholder theory and other related managerial issues including strategic management. According to Freeman (1984), the stakeholder theory is about the broad view of stakeholders in which the corporate has responsibilities towards them beside those who are the main or primary stakeholders of the corporate. Freeman (1984) considers the stakeholder in an organization as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization’s objectives” (p. 46). He considers also that every individual or group that may affect or be affected by the company’s activity has a right

to be considered in the process of decision-making. Freeman (1984) claims that the stakeholder approach “advocates that we have a thorough understanding of our stakeholders and calls for the recognition that there are times when stakeholders must participate in the decision-making processes of the firm” (p. 196). Freeman mentions in his book the term ‘stakeholder approach’ which he uses interchangeably to refer to the stakeholder theory. He also argues on enabling all stakeholders (i.e., primary and secondary) representing both the narrow and broad view of stakeholders to be a part of the decision-making process. This is consistent with the view that the stakeholder model separates the conception that shareholders are the only significant elements among other stakeholders (Pedersen, 2006). Moreover, Keinert (2008) argues that the stakeholder theory is not one theory as the term suggests but that the term originally is the ‘stakeholder theories’ as suggested in the book of Freeman (1984) itself. Keinert adds that Freeman uses the term stakeholder theories to clarify the diverse opinions on the scope of stakeholders that a corporate has. The book of Freeman also addresses stakeholder theory and its relationship with strategic and organizational management and with business ethics, namely, CSR concept. According to Pedersen (2006), the stakeholder model is best used to indicate the modern understanding of corporates as integrated in the rest of the society rather than being separated from. Moreover, concerning the term ‘stakeholder management’ (i.e., stakeholder relations) which is included in Freeman’s book of 1984, Freeman states: “Stakeholder Management as a concept, refers to the necessity for an organization to manage the relationships with its specific stakeholder groups in an action-oriented way” (p. 53). Keinert (2008) claims that stakeholder (relations) management is concerned with balancing multiple stakeholders’ interests in which part of these interests are compatible whereas the other parts of these interests could oppose each other. In a complementary context, Garriga *et*

al. (2004) mention that the fundamental goal of stakeholder management can be done through achieving a full and inclusive cooperation between the whole stakeholder groups' system and the corporation's objectives.

Stakeholder theory is very vital when a discussion is planned concerning the relationship between society and business especially business ethics and CSR concept. When trying to connect business with ethics, ethicists adhere to stakeholder theory and use it as a strong tool for thinking about this relationship (Freeman *et al.*, 2010). They add that this theory provides a systematic and certain collection of views about essential issues that a corporate can care about in the field of ethics and it provides also an argumentative environment in which different ethicists can show up their contributions. In the same regard, Pedersen (2006) claims that during the last decades, stakeholder theory is importantly becoming the common frame of reference when tackling CSR concept. Other scholars stress on using the stakeholder approach as a primary unit of analysis when dealing with ongoing debates concerning CSR (Freeman *et al.*, 2010). The same scholars maintain that stakeholder theory is also an essential concern when addressing the relationship between social responsibilities of a business and its financial obligations since it can add value to the prospective development of CSR through well detailing of the integration of financial and social issues.

McClerklin (2013) contends that several scholars maintain that integrating stakeholder concepts into CSR concept is a beneficial action for businesses such as controlling more the activities of CSR in different contexts. He maintains that stakeholder literature written from a stakeholder-centric view would help different groups of stakeholders to comprehend more their significance to CSR engagement. In the same context and following the stakeholder theory, Garriga *et al.* (2004) contend that an enterprise—

described as socially responsible—needs concurrent attention regarding legal interests of all the enterprise’s primary and secondary stakeholders with balancing at the same time these diverse interests of those stakeholders. This means that the interest of primary stakeholders (i.e., owners or shareholders) should be embedded in the wide and broad interests of other stakeholders who are also significant for the enterprise and for its existence. One of the considerable integration between stakeholder theory and CSR is the one postulated by scholars Linda Munilla and Morgan Miles in 2005 when they portrayed a CSR continuum containing three modes of engagement with stakeholders as follows: (1) the first mode is ‘compliance’ where expenses of CSR activities are understood as the cost of doing business; (2) the second mode is ‘strategic mode’ where CSR is viewed as an investment of the corporate’s competencies; and (3) the last mode is ‘forced mode’ where CSR is considered as a tax imposed by external or secondary stakeholders such as the government (Munilla *et al.*, 2005).

Carroll and Buchholtz (2009) tackled the stakeholder approach and its intertwining relationship with business, society, and ethics. They argue that the stakeholder approach to management is balanced for pursuing development and specifically in the field of business and society. The same scholars refer to the three different values of stakeholder approach of a corporate that should be appreciated and mention them starting with: (1) the ‘descriptive value’ of the stakeholder approach which provides concepts to effectively describe the corporation; (2) the ‘instrumental value’ of the stakeholder approach which characterizes the relationship between the practice of stakeholder management and the resulting achievement of corporate performance goals; and (3) the ‘normative value’ of the stakeholder approach—considered as the ethical value since it stresses on how stakeholders should be treated—in which stakeholders are seen as a

possessing value irrespective of their instrumental use to management (Donaldson *et al.*, 1995, as cited in Carroll *et al.*, 2009, pp. 92-93).

Moreover, scholars stress on the importance of integrating stakeholder theory, business ethics, and CSR issues in the future which has a positive impact on enhancing the awareness of stakeholders towards their role in such integration. Among those scholars are Harrison and Freeman (1999) who argue that through building and testing strong and relevant theories using the constructs of stakeholders and ethics, new generations of researchers and academics will have a bright future.

2.8 CSR and State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs)

For a long period of time over the last decades, CSR has captured a pivotal attention of many enterprises, SMEs, MNCs, and other private entities. This kind of attention augments day after another and it becomes a great concern for many entities today. There are different types of businesses that offer products or services to have adequate profits which satisfy the needs of their shareholders or owners. These businesses ethically should have in parallel a great concern on social responsibilities towards other significant stakeholders. The major trend on the discussions regarding CSR concept and its complementary issues is about businesses and enterprises that operate on private sector. This is can be attributed to the fact that enterprises belong to the private sector have a main objective which is about profit maximization that contributes accordingly in maximizing the shareholders' wealth. These privately-run businesses or enterprises are known as for-profit enterprises that belong to different economic sectors or industries, namely, raw materials, manufacturing, trade, and services.

Through browsing and examining the literature regarding CSR, a researcher can find out that this literature majorly focuses on privately-run businesses and their expected

role towards CSR and its complementary issues. On the contrary, a small portion of this literature involves an indication to the government (i.e., public sector) and its role towards CSR concept (Amba-Rao, 1993; De Bernardis, Maiolini, & Braccini, 2010; Finskas, 2007; Hinz, 2009). According to the European Communities Commission (2001), there are socially responsible practices which can be found in all types of public and private enterprises which implies that CSR is present in public sector as it is present in private sector. Amba-Rao (1993) also contends that moral responsibilities must be agreed on by both private and public enterprises in their economic transactions in order to improve social welfare and individual interest. Supporting such kind of posing, De Bernardis *et al.* (2010) state: “Yet the public sector has often been left out of discussion of CSR” (p. 3). They contend that there are no many studies which discuss how public sector adopts CSR and how CSR can influence the environment that public sector’s entities operate in. The same scholars maintain that the contemporary idea of CSR is just one-way in which enterprises from the private sector should be responsible because there are public institutions that control them. This view is one of the many reasons behind the notion that leads to drifting away the major thinking about and discussing of CSR issues in the entities comprising the public sector. The same scholars justify such scarcity of resources that examine the public sector and CSR relationship and state: “Existing studies provide a limited understanding of how differences between public and private organizations can explain differences in CSR behavior that go beyond financial performance (especially in the public sector)” (De Bernardis *et al.*, 2010, p. 3).

It is important to refer to the fact that CSR is not restricted on only profit-driven corporates and enterprises exist in the private sector. It has also a clear influence on the outcomes produced by other entities in public sector and even nongovernmental organizations. This is clear in the writings of Stepanenko (2012) in which she maintains

that the main driving force in the process of developing CSR in Europe is the state authorities and local governments. In another paper which clarifies the importance of the government for CSR, (Ohlrich, 2011) contends that CSR concept has many definitions which in general refer to the relationship between three main entities, namely, corporation, government, and civil society. He adds that CSR suggests that these three entities act and work together for establishing a more civilized society and for assisting in the process of solving diverse societal issues. One of the other researchers claims that the relationship between CSR and public sector is related to the development objectives (Okoye, 2012). This researcher contends that the relationship between government (i.e., public sector) and CSR leads to achieving developmental objectives which are part of the government responsibility itself. Tackling issues of CSR could be important for private sector in the viewpoints and writings of scholars because CSR can affect positively or negatively the CFP of entities that operate in private sector and this renders it more significant and more productive to be discussed in this sector. However, public sector is still neglected partially in the literature concerning CSR and many obtainable researches, papers, and studies that investigate such relationship focus on state-owned enterprises (SOEs) as the main interface of public sector in this regard. Moreover, SOEs are considered similar to the privately-run enterprises operating in the private sector since both are for-profit enterprises with common commercial activities and also have common stakeholders with different interests that should be properly fulfilled.

In order to have more specific knowledge about what do SOEs stand for, a definition would be a great asset which reveals more about this obscure term used slightly in literature. Kowalski *et al.* (2013) maintain that countries apply multiple definitions of SOEs which complicates formulation of a meaningful uniform definition of SOEs. One

of the most accepted definitions in the literature is the one posited by MacCarthaigh (2009) in which he states that the SOE is “an entity in which the state has a majority or complete shareholding, and which is principally involved in commercial activity in a market environment” (p. 5). State or government enterprises can be controlled towards achieving particular social and environmental objectives according to government’s determined national priorities (MacCarthaigh, 2009). In Canada, the state-owned enterprises (SOEs) are defined as the enterprises that belong to the public sector domain—because they are controlled by the government—and they operate in the market place, often in competition with privately owned organizations (Christiansen, 2011). The same researcher points out that SOEs are classified as profit-oriented entities or government business enterprises which are controlled by the federal government in Canada. In order to accomplish their objectives set and monitored by the government, SOEs must have a kind of active autonomy which is planned and maintained by the government for promoting a long-term interests of these SOEs (Thomas, 2012). For clarifying the relationship between SOEs and their stakeholders, Thomas (2012) states: “SOEs are advised to regularly report on their stakeholder relationships and to develop an internal code of ethics that takes cognisance of stakeholder rights” (p. 454). Accordingly, the SOE has stakeholders and responsibilities towards those stakeholders as any other private enterprise. This is due to the fact that the SOE is a for-profit entity and the principles of stakeholder theory are applied on it including fulfilling CSR activities and furnishing stakeholders with required financial and other reports.

According to Kowalski *et al.*, (2013) numerous countries—described as intensely traded—have the highest SOE shares and have also economic sectors with strong SOE presence. They add that some conducted studies found that out of the world’s 2000 publically listed enterprises, there are 204 enterprises that are classified as SOEs and the

majority of them are located in China. The same scholars add that 47 percent of these 2000 largest enterprises belong to several industrial countries—abbreviated in the acronym BRIICS (i.e., Brazil, Russia, India, Indonesia, China, and South Africa)—have been classified and defined as SOEs.

For discussing more from another perspective the relationship between CSR and entities of public sector (i.e., SOEs), it is essential to indicate that a person can wonder about the government or public sector (i.e., state sector) and its relationship with CSR since the core obligation of the overall public sector is to serve society and to serve citizens who comprise this society. This is correct for the portion of the public sector that is not overtly intended for making profit through conducting commercial activities but for other portions the case is totally different. It is accepted that the public sector comprises several subsectors and among them the subsector that belongs to the government and at the same time is intended to make profit through performing commercial and business activities and through competing other private enterprises in the market. This subsector of public sector consists of entities known as state-owned enterprises (SOEs) or government-owned corporations (GOCs) which have a dual role. One part of this role is socially intended and the other part is commercially intended.

It is obvious that SOEs of the public sector are created and administered by the government in order to perform several objectives and among these objectives is a sheer profit-oriented objective beside the basic and normal social objectives of these entities. According to Lin (2010), there are nearly 150 SOEs in China which are directed by the Chinese central government's control and most of them are listed in the Chinese stock exchanges. Lin adds that the Chinese government released in 2008 a guide opinion for social responsibility implementation for the SOEs which are controlled by the central

government of China. This guide opinion explains a number of broad CSR principles for SOEs based on the international definitions of CSR and at the same time it is adapted with the domestic Chinese characteristics (Lin, 2010). Lin summarizes these principles in the four parts that this guide opinion contains as follows: (i) the first part expounds and lists why CSR is important for SOEs; (ii) the second part considers the basic principles required for implementing CSR in SOEs; (iii) the third part describes major contents of CSR for SOEs; and (iv) the fourth and last part proposes major measures for the implementation of CSR by SOEs.

In a recent comparative study conducted in China in the late 2000s, Gao (2011) found other important characteristics that SOEs have with respect to CSR. Gao claims that SOEs show higher propensity in addressing a major portion of social issues and in addressing more the interest of charity than non-SOEs, and that SOEs are more politically sensitive than non-SOEs. It is clear to say that government strict control and direct governing are essential factors for having profitable and successful for-profit and commerce-oriented SOEs. In this way, the writings of Hinz (2009) imply that the government—as one of the most important stakeholders—is considered as the key driver of CSR activities fulfilled by SOEs. He adds that the responses made by SOEs in the field of CSR activities are chiefly driven by the encouraging policy imposed by the government.

Accordingly, government or public sector has a clear and influential relationship with CSR either as a significant stakeholder or as a competitive partner amid other sectors. The literature has scantily discussed this relationship in the past but sights now for some researchers—especially those who are interested in societal issues such as researchers of SIMs field—are directed to more investigating CSR activities in public fields. Entities

of the public sector which have for-profit objectives, namely, SOEs, are slightly considered or investigated by scholars despite their essential roles in supporting diverse national economics and societal activities for many developed and developing nations. This posing is implied in the state of Finskas (2007) when this researcher says: “studying CSR and governmental approaches to CSR is a fairly new endeavor and has therefore no robust empirical or theoretical base” (p. 28). However, the body of literature could be considerably enriched with the practical contributions and actions made by some developed and developing countries for supporting such concepts (i.e., CSR and public sector, SOEs and CSR, SOEs in developed and developing countries) and for increasingly making government as the influential partner in all social responsibilities of diverse societies.

2.9 Organizational Performance

One of the most vital concepts for describing an organization of being successful or not is its level of organizational performance. This concept is based on several different and distinct components that render the process of measuring the organizational performance or defining it a controversial issue amid diverse scholars in the literature. Gavrea *et al.* (2011) claim that organizational performance is one of the most important variables in management research. Those researchers add that the definition of the organizational performance is difficult due to its many meanings. They maintain that there is no universal accepted definition of this concept. Moreover, Hancott (2005) states: “Organizational performance as a concept suffers from problems of conceptual clarity in a number of areas” (p. 32). He adds that these areas include the definition of the organizational performance and the measurement used for measuring it. Accordingly and for making the organizational performance clearer to investigate,

several definitions of this term are detailed in this section obtained from different scholars and researchers in the literature.

According to Venkatraman *et al.* (1986a), organizational performance is fundamental in the process of management practice and also research. The same scholars consider organizational performance as an indicator for measuring how well an organization could fulfill its objectives. Chajnicki (2007, p. iii) provides a concise definition that includes the widely known measures of organizational performance and states:

Organizational performance is defined as the weighted combination of both perceived (operational and knowledge) and objective (hard financial) performance information.

Other researchers define organizational performance as the indicator that is used to measure the ability's level of an organization to achieve its objectives (Hamon, 2003; Ho, 2008; Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986a). Furthermore, Boulay (2008) considers organizational level outcomes as the definition of organizational performance. He maintains that "organizational performance is measured by the instrument items productivity and financial performance" (p. 55). This definition of Boulay indicates that the measurement of the organizational performance implies two main types of measurements, namely, perceptual and financial. Lusthaus *et al.* (1999) are among other researchers who define organizational performance by considering it as an explanation of the conducted activities by the organization itself to achieve its mission. They contend that the outputs and their effects of the organization's different functions are the most visible aspects of the organizational performance. The same researchers specify four major categories that organizational performance implies which are effectiveness, efficiency, relevance, and financial viability.

Most of the previous definitions of organizational performance include a description of what could this term stand for and what are its main categories. Organizational performance is multidimensional and has many factors that are used to define and measure it (Carton & Hofer, 2006; Talbot, 2010). Many scholars in the literature stress on the fact that measuring organizational performance is challenging and a difficult issue and this renders it as a rich field for discussion and controversy amid practitioners and interested academic people (Bacha, 2010; Carton & Hofer, 2006; Leitão & Franco 2009; Talbot, 2010; Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986a). The majority of executives uncomfortably know that there is no one specific or definite method for measuring organizational performance (Hancott, 2005). According to Leitão *et al.* (2009), measurements used to measure organizational performance are still a controversial topic. Among the main types of measurements utilized to measure this concept are the financial (i.e., objective) and nonfinancial (i.e., subjective) measures. According to Hancott (2005), these two types of measures are considered as the most important used measures for assessing organizational performance and they are differently called among the scholars in the literature. Some scholars refer to the financial organizational performance using the terms objective, tangible, quantitative, or economic. However, other scholars refer to the nonfinancial organizational performance using the terms subjective, perceptual, intangible, or operational. These terms are sometimes used interchangeably in the books, articles, and academic papers subsisting in the literature referring to objective and subjective measures of organizational performance respectively. One of the most clear and simple example of financial measures is profitability whereas customers' satisfaction is used as one of the most simple and direct perceptual measures for measuring the organizational performance. Allen *et al.* (2008) state: "There is a great debate in the performance measurement literature regarding

whether the use of objective or subjective measures provide the most valid results” (p. 23). They conclude that both types of measures hold advantages and disadvantages. Moreover, Venkatraman *et al.* (1986a) performed an empirical study concerning the two salient categories of organizational performance measurement, namely, objective and subjective, and found out that there is a strong degree of convergence between them. In the same context, studies conducted by scholars found out that subjective measures by self-reported measures correlate well with objective measures of the organizational performance (Powell, 1992).

In another paper, Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986b) claim that the entire domain of business performance consists of three main domains represented by three concentric circles as shown in Figure 2.3. They add that the inner or small circle is about the domain of financial performance which focuses on the use of simple-outcome based financial indicators which fulfill the economic goal of the enterprise. The second circle represents the domain of both financial and operational (i.e., nonfinancial) performance. They contend that nonfinancial indicators of the organizational performance are added for making the researchers thinking out of the black box approach to characterize the exclusive usage of financial measures and focusing at the same time on the nonfinancial measures which result in financial performance. The third domain is the outer or larger circle which embodies the organizational effectiveness that is indicated in major conceptual literature in strategic management and organization theory (Venkatraman *et al.*, 1986b).

Source: N. Venkatraman and Vasudevan Ramanujam, "Measurement of Business Performance in Strategy Research: A Comparison of Approaches," *The Academy of Management Review* (Oct., 1986), 803.

Figure 2.3.: Marking out the domain of business performance
(Venkatraman *et al.*, 1986b)

Furthermore, Carton and Hofer (2006) examined a period of five years of empirical researches—nearly 1045 articles published from 1996 to 2001—that were published in different five journals interested in publishing empirical researches in the field of measuring organizational performance. Those scholars found out that out of the 1045 examined articles, only 138 studies used overall organizational performance as the dependent variable and the rest of the 907 articles used intermediate performance variables which could partially affect the overall organizational performance. They also contend that 88 different variables were used as measures for organizational performance which can be classified into nine key performance dimensions. These nine dimensions are: (1) the profitability dimension such as accounting measures; (2) the operational dimension that copes with how the enterprise is developing based on nonfinancial aspects such as the number of patents received; (3) the market dimension

such as market value added; (4) the growth dimension such as growth in employees; (5) the efficiency dimension such as sales per employee; (6) the liquidity dimension such as cash flow ratios; (7) The size dimension such as total number of employees; (8) the survival dimension such as survival through a point in time; and (9) other measures that researchers have used over time, such as subjective assessments by top managers for ideal performance of the organization (Carton *et al.*, 2006).

According to Haynes (2007), the scholar D. Scott Sink proposed seven dimensions for measuring the organizational performance and these measures are categorized into tangible and intangible measures. These seven dimensions are: (1) effectiveness; (2) efficiency; (3) quality; (4) profitability; (5) productivity; (6) quality of work life; and (7) innovation (Sink, 1985, as cited in Haynes, 2007, p. 147). Accordingly, the overall organizational performance in general has two main categories that are used to measure this concept, namely, objective or financial measures and subjective or nonfinancial measures. These two main categories used for assessing organizational performance are discussed in the next subsections.

2.9.1 Objective or Financial Measures of Organizational Performance

For a long time, the typical measures used to squarely assess the concept of organizational performance had a financial or objective nature. These measures along with their diverse types are used in many studies in the literature for measuring the concept of organizational performance. There are many objective measures that were used to define and measure organizational performance since the mid-1900s and have progressed to include additional financial measures with time (Hancott, 2005). According to Venkatraman *et al.* (1986a), objective measures of organizational performance are based on some established systems such as internal accounting, or

systematic tracking by external agencies. They state: “While objective assessments may reduce the possibility of overrating performance, they may not always be available in the form desired for the specific research question (e.g., in comparison with competitors, or in relation to the goals)” (p. 2). Allen *et al.* (2008, p. 23) summarize the concept of objective measures of organizational performance by stating:

Objective measures tend to be more concrete but are often limited in scope to financial data. They often limit the breadth and scope of organizations that can be included in a study since organizations from a single industry are needed for valid comparison purposes with objective measures.

Among the most commonly cited and used objective or financial measures for assessing organizational performance are profitability indicated by several financial ratios (i.e., return of investment (ROI), return on sales (ROS), return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE)). Other objective measures include earnings per share (EPS), stock price performance (SPP), sales growth, net income growth, cash flow return on equity, and volume of sales (Allen, Dawson, Wheatley, & White, 2008; Carton & Hofer, 2006; Guest & Peccei, 2001; Hancott, 2005; Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986a).

On the other hand, scholars oppose using only financial measures as a base for assessing and measuring organizational performance. Scholars argue that the financial measures are inappropriate for their lagging for the performance and this causes difficulty in evaluating exactly the organizational performance in modern environments (Kaplan *et al.*, 1996). Moreover, Hancott (2005) contends that objective measures may not entirely measure an executive’s effectiveness and consequently this leads to partially measuring the organizational performance. In the same line, Leitão *et al.* (2009) state: “In fact, a financial or economic measure is unlikely to capture the relative performance of the firms” (p. 4). They contend that financial and economic measures represent serious limitations in evaluating the organizational performance. Furthermore, Carton *et al.*

(2006) claim that understanding well the relative information content of financial measures of organizational performance can be supportive for managers in picking nonfinancial measures which both help in evaluating the overall organizational performance. On the contrary, Bacha (2010) claims that it is interesting to use objective measures to study organizational performance because these measures are more accurate and precise. This contradiction reflects the paradoxical views and thoughts regarding the measurement of organizational performance amid scholars in the literature and refers at the same time to the problematic aspects in this concern which exist among diverse researchers and practitioners.

2.9.2 Subjective or Nonfinancial Measures of Organizational Performance

It was clear for scholars, researchers, and academics that financial or objective measures were the dominant indicators used for assessing the organizational performance in the last decades. These measures depend on sheer accounting and financial data obtained from reports issued periodically by different organizations. According to Gavrea *et al.* (2011), with time and with the increasing of complexity in the measurement systems used for evaluating organizational performance, nonfinancial or subjective measures were used by scholars, researchers, and business people. They add that consulting firms and practitioners greatly have emphasized the necessity for adopting nonfinancial indicators when assessing organizational performance. Allen *et al.* (2008, p. 23) summarize the concept of subjective measures of organizational performance by stating:

Subjective measures on the other hand lack concreteness or reproducibility, but often provide the researcher with a richer description of the effectiveness of an organization with respect to their competitors. Subjective measures allow a broader range of organizations to be compared within a single study.

Among the most commonly cited and used subjective or nonfinancial measures for organizational performance in the literature are customer satisfaction, quality of

products and services, product or service innovation, relative competitive position, ability to retain existing customers (retention), ability to attract new customers (attraction), employee retention, employee attraction, management and employee relation, relations among employees, manufacturing value added, marketing effectiveness, and operating efficiency (Allen, Dawson, Wheatley, & White, 2008; Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Dollinger & Golden, 1992; Guest & Peccei, 2001; Henri, 2004; Kuo, 2011).

Moreover, it is important to relate subjective indicators with the perception expected from employees and executives working in diverse organizations when assessing their organizational performance. Operational (i.e., subjective or perceptual) measures include variables that represent how the organization is performing on nonfinancial issues (Carton *et al.*, 2006). Those researchers add that these nonfinancial measures (i.e., subjective) often involve the management's qualitative assessments. In the same line and according to Venkatraman *et al.* (1986a), subjective measures of organizational performance are based on judgments made by executives. They add that the scholar Lynn Phillips commented on the perceptual assessment in 1981 and mentioned its effects on respondents. Phillips (1981) contends that perceptual assessment permits anyone to obtain data in the required format, but involves the respondents to make complex and difficult judgments. Furthermore, scholars claim that subjective measures attach importance to the perceptual component of the analysis (Allen *et al.*, 2008). They add that this slight shift of thinking concerning subjective assessment measures of organizational performance reveals more regarding how employees think about their enterprise's performance.

To relate this with organizational performance of the enterprise, Carton (2004) contends that the use of such subjective assessments can be viewed as an attempt to address the multiple dimensions of performance for the enterprise itself. For example, Henri (2004) inspects the expected relationship between objective and subjective measures and concludes that the nonfinancial measures of the organizational performance serve as good predictors of long-term financial performance and share value than existing financial measures. He adds that this subjective information “possesses predictive ability and complements financial information, which remains important” (p. 106). With relation to this, Spitzer (2007) states: “It is most certainly possible to satisfy all the key requirements of a good performance measure with a subjective measure” (p. 207). He adds that good subjective measures are relatively satisfactory substitutes for harder measures (i.e., financial measures). As a key point concerning the usage of subjective measures to assess the organizational performance, Spitzer claims that when objective measures are weak or not feasible, then subjective measures can be a good and practical substitute. He concludes his writings by adding that subjective evaluations are all that a scholar can depend on for measuring some of the intangible, innovative, and predictive constructs (Spitzer, 2007).

There are several causes that render scholars, practitioners, and academics to be interested more and more in assessing the organizational performance of an enterprise using perceptual or subjective measures. For instance, Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986a) maintain that subjective assessments obtained from executives can be used as acceptable operationalization for the organizational performance. Those scholars add that perceptual evaluations are a good substitute for objective measures whenever: (i) precise objective measures are unavailable; and (ii) the option is to eliminate the consideration of performance from the research design. Subjective measures are also

preferable when confidentiality is a great concern for enterprises and executives. Some private firms seem reluctant in providing sensitive financial data even with stressing from the researchers on guaranteeing the confidentiality (Dollinger & Golden, 1992). In the same line, Delaney and Huselid (1996) maintain that perceptual measures of organizational performance are vital in assessing the performance of nonprofit organizations (i.e., nongovernmental organizations or NGOs) since these entities do not have profits and the process of assessing their performance based on objective measures is unavailable in reality. Accordingly, the same scholars contend that perceptual measures of organizational performance are regularly used in academic researches. Moreover, they add that the usage of perceptual measures allows for an analysis of profitmaking and nonprofit organizations or NGOs.

In another way for empirically utilizing different subjective and objective measures at the same time, some scholars use objective or financial measures to assess perceived organizational performance by investigating the subjective perceptions of employees or executives working in these organizations (Allen, Dawson, Wheatley, & White, 2008; Bacha, 2010; Dollinger & Golden, 1992; Gavrea, Ilieş, & Stegorean, 2011; Guest & Peccei, 2001; Moideenkutty, Al-Lamki, & Murthy, 2011; Powell, 1992; Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986a). Those scholars perform studies and allow respondents freely to evaluate financial or objective measures by their own perceived evaluations and through their personal experience. Although this method of researching is used among scholars and academics, Talbot (2010) has reservations concerning it. The writings of this scholar claim that practitioners and academics make simple errors concerning performance when they designate survey data of people opinion as subjective data. He adds that such reliable and valid survey data are objective data about people's subjective perceptions (Talbot, 2010). Some researchers could agree with such sayings of this

scholar and other scholars could disagree with him and keep using such kind of mixture between objective and subjective measures which deepens the fact that organizational performance and its two key categories of measures are still under a great debate in the literature.

2.10 Relationship between CSR and Organizational Performance

When trying to study managerial concepts such as corporate social responsibility, organizational performance, and the relationship between these two concepts, a researcher finds difficulties in the process of methodically defining, measuring, and operationalizing them. Through browsing the body of the literature, different scholars posited several definitions and conceptualizations for CSR and organizational performance but no standard definitions have been agreed amid scholars for theoretically or empirically describing these concepts. Moreover, scholars find and encounter adversities when trying to empirically measure and assess CSR activities or organizational performance of diverse enterprises. The same thing can be found concerning the relationship between CSR and the organizational performance since this connection is not usually well-defined and is not a simple issue to be understood. Although many academic studies and researches tied CSR and organizational performance more, but the relationship per se has not been empirically validated and explicitly expressed (Lee, 2008).

In this way, the majority of the studies existing in the literature focus on investigating the relationship between only main social concerns and sheer financial aspects. Scholars are interested more about finding additional and new aspects of the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and corporate financial performance (CFP) and knowing more if CFP is affected positively or negatively by socially responsible

activities achieved by different enterprises and organizations. These conducted and published studies greatly care about objective measures of organizational performance and consider them among the key part of this relationship along with CSR. On the other hand, a scant number of studies consider subjective or perceptual measures of organizational performance when studying the relationship between CSR and organizational performance. It is palpable that scholars are more interested in investigating the impact of hard indicators (i.e., objective measures) used to measure the organizational performance on CSR instead of investigating the possible effects that subjective or nonfinancial indicators could have on the different activities of CSR.

There are numerous studies in the literature that tackled the connection between CSR and organizational performance during the last decades (Akanbi & Ofoegbu, 2012; Aupperle, Carroll, & Hatfield, 1985; Becchetti, Di Giacomo, & Pinnacchio, 2005; Bird, Casavecchia, & Reggiani, 2006; Campbell, 2007; Carter, 2005; Griffin & Mahon, 1997; Harrison & Freeman, 1999; Margolis & Walsh, 2003; McGuire, Sundgren, & Schneeweis, 1988; Park, 2010; Paskert, 2008; Quazi & Richardson, 2012; Roman, Hayibor, & Agle, 1999; Vollono, 2010; Wissink, 2012; Wood, 2010). A large amount of these studies considers CSR as a phenomenon that affects the organizational performance and most of these studies use the objective measures to assess organizational performance. The desired objective of these studies is to find out if CSR has a positive influence on organizational performance of different for-profit enterprises. Conversely, the scholars of the literature considerably ignore the possible effects that perceptual and nonfinancial measures of organizational performance could impact on CSR and this ignorance weakens this area of researching among different researchers. This is clear in the published articles and empirical studies concerning the tries to reconcile CSR activities with organizational performance in the literature.

Several scholars criticize this kind of propensity towards only studying the relationship between socially responsible activities and financial performance of enterprises and stress on considering other indicators for assessing the organizational performance (Campbell, 2007; Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Margolis & Walsh, 2003; McGuire, Sundgren, & Schneeweis, 1988).

During the last decades of the 20th century and the early decades of the 21st century, researchers have studied the link between CSR and CFP and found diverse results. They found out that the association between CSR and the enterprise's performance mostly exists in one of three principal types as follows: (i) the first type implies a positive association; (ii) the second type implies a negative association; and (3) the third type implies a null or neutral association between CSR and CFP (Aupperle, Carroll, & Hatfield, 1985; Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Griffin & Mahon, 1997; Lee, 2008; Margolis & Walsh, 2003; McGuire, Sundgren, & Schneeweis, 1988; Park, 2010; Roman, Hayibor, & Agle, 1999; Vogel, 2005; Wissink, 2012). Discussing some of the most significant empirical studies in this regard is necessary in this section. Accordingly, a starting considerable research is the one conducted by Margolis and Walsh in 2003. They examined the literature during the period of 1972 to 2002 and found that 127 published studies empirically investigated the relationship between enterprises' socially responsible activities and their financial performance. Those scholars found that CSP (i.e., corporate social performance as the independent variable) predicts organizational performance as the dependent variable in 109 studies out of the 127 studies. They add that nearly half of the results indicate a positive relationship between CSP and financial performance, a small portion of the results (i.e., 6.4%) indicates a negative relationship, and nearly 26 percent of the studies indicate that there is no relationship between CSP and organizational financial performance. They conclude their study by claiming that

the so-called positivity between CSR and CFP mainly lingers unsettled (Margolis *et al.*, 2003).

Among those other scholars who examined this relationship is Campbell (2007) who contends that economic conditions affect the level to which enterprises behave in socially responsible ways and this behavior is mediated by several institutional factors such as organized dialogues among corporations and their stakeholders. He adds that if enterprises operate in a bad economic environment, then these enterprises will have difficulties in achieving satisfactory profit and consequently will be more reluctant to behave in socially responsible ways. The writings of McGuire *et al.* (1988) imply an empirical study that maintains the positivity of the relationship between the perceptions of enterprises' CSR and measures of their financial performance. Those scholars used objective measures (i.e., stock-market returns and accounting-based measures) to assess the organizational financial performance and found out that enterprises which are high in social responsibilities experience higher return on assets (ROA) and higher stock-market returns. Moreover, they detailed several studies by several scholars who investigate the relationship between CSR and CFP and maintained that these studies yield mixed results regarding this relationship that include positive, negative, and in some cases absent association between CSR and CFP.

On the other hand, the study of Aupperle *et al.* (1985) regarding examining the link between CSR and financial performance shows distinct results. Those scholars investigate the link between CSR and profitability through correlating the enterprise's concern for society score with its profitability. They employed both short- and long-term ROA as a profitability indicator to adjust possible generated risk. The results of their study yield that no statistically significant relationship between CSR and the

profitability of the enterprise. They concluded their research by stating: “There is insufficient evidence to support the claim that socially responsible firms are more profitable than other firms” (Aupperle *et al.*, 1985, p. 462). Furthermore, they detailed several studies by several scholars who investigated the relationship between CSR and CFP and maintained that these studies yield also mixed results regarding this relationship that include positive, negative, and in some cases absent association between CSR and CFP.

The same results were also concluded by Park (2010) when she claims that most of the studies conducted concerning the relationship between CSR and enterprise’s performance suggest a positive relationship between them while other studies argue that CSR activities have either a negative association or no relationship at all with the organizational performance. However, the writings of Lee (2008) include an indication to the fact that the convergence between CSR and organizational performance happens in two directions. In the first direction, CSR grows to enclose economic and social concerns on macro- and organizational levels whereas in the second direction, organizational performance grows as well to enclose economic and social concerns on institutional and organizational levels. Lee contends that the successful management needs to adopt and develop CSR as a resource for improving the overall performance of the enterprise.

According to Wood (2010), management scholars have been concerned with the relationship between CSP and CFP in order to rationalize their approval or disapproval of socially responsible behaviors performed by different enterprises. Among those several scholars who investigate the connection between CSP and CFP are Carroll and Shabana (2010) who argue that there is a positive link between these two concepts.

They state: “On the whole, CSP–CFP research seems to indicate the existence of a positive relationship between CSP and CFP; however, some inconsistencies linger” (p. 94). These inconsistencies—which Carroll and Shabana refer to—are caused by methodological differences, interpretation biases, and mediating variables and situational contingencies influencing CSP-CFP association. Other scholars refer to the same point and mention that CSR activities which are evaluated without considering the mediating variables and situational contingencies could affect the connection between CSR and organizational performance (Carter, 2005; Park, 2010).

In the same line, Vogel (2005) contends that studies that link the measures of environmental performance to the measures of financial performance experience several weaknesses. He argues that researches that examine the connection between CSR and organizational performance encounter difficulties due to the distinct things that these researches measure. This can be explained and reinforced by the contradictions that several scholars have concerning the definitions and measures of both CSR and organizational performance. Vogel concludes his views regarding the relationship between CSR and CFP by relating this relationship to strategic and competitive advantage’s issues of enterprises. He argues that enterprises could be more profitable when they are more responsible but this does not essentially mean that other less responsible competitors would be less profitable since they have less social responsibilities. He then concludes this relationship and states: “a link between responsibility and profitability does not necessarily mean that firms would be even more profitable if they were more responsible, since there may be declining returns for behaving more responsibly” (Vogel, 2005, p. 33). If all enterprises behave responsibly according to the principles of CSR, this would reject the dogma that CSR is a source of competitive advantage among diverse enterprises and would jeopardize the statistical

significance of the relationship between CSR and the organizational performance (Vogel, 2005).

On the other hand, very few studies in the literature attempted to empirically examine the relationship between CSR and perceived organizational performance using absolute subjective or nonfinancial measures such as customer satisfaction, employee retention, employee attraction, level of innovation, and quality of offered services and products. Currently, scholars are aware of the importance in adding more subjective measures to evaluate organizational performance rather than only depending on financial measures especially if the enterprise's performance is intended to be empirically studied with other variables (i.e., CSR). Complexity of measuring the organizational performance incites researchers to have other dimensions which could help in having more precise and thoroughly assessment of the organizational performance. According to McGuire *et al.* (1988), when conducting studies to examine the link between CSR and the organizational performance, the selection of performance measures is a vital concern for the expected results. They stress that researchers should cautiously select these measures of organizational performance which adequately match the research questions they examine. In this line, Margolis *et al.* (2003) criticize the existing literature because it overlooks other factors that could influence CSP other than financial ones and they stress on more thoughtful academic investigation concerning social responsibilities of organizations and their organizational performance.

Among the rare studies in the literature that investigate the relationship between CSR and perceptual organizational performance using majorly subjective measures beside few objective measures is the study of Paul Akanbi and Onyema Ofoegbu (2012). Those scholars perform a study to examine the impact of CSR on the perceived

organizational performance in the banking industry in Nigeria. They found out that CSR four dimensions (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic) have an influence on the organizational performance of the Nigerian banks. Furthermore, they claim that CSR activities help these organizations to attract and retain both customers and employees and this contributes in attaining a long-term endurance for the organizations and enhance accordingly their organizational performance. They conclude their study by indicating that the dimensions used to measure CSR are predictors of the organizational performance of the banking industry in Nigeria.

In general and concerning the nature of the link between CSR and organizational performance, the majority of the writings and studies conducted by diverse scholars subsisting in the literature refer to the fact that there is a slightly positive relationship exists between socially responsible activities (i.e., CSR activities) and organizational performance whether this performance is assessed by objective or subjective measures. Moreover, other types of association include a negative or a neutral relationship which represent the minority beside the numerous studies that support the positivity of the association between CSR and the organizational performance.

2.11 CSR Initiatives in Yemen

The concept of CSR has emerged in Europe during the early 19th century as an action or a behavior that can be simply described as a charitable donating for society (Ohlrich, 2011). Thence, this concept has spread and spotted in different places and countries around the world and acquired more concerns from academics and business people. More and more interests are directed now towards CSR activities in developed countries and more empirical studies are conducted to have more explanations about the impact of CSR on other managerial issues and vice versa. Currently, CSR is associated with many

modern concepts such as corporate citizenship, corporate governance, organizational performance, strategic management, transparency, and globalization and this makes it very vital for enterprises in the world.

Although its popularity and significance, CSR is still a vague, neglected, and perplexed issue for several nations and specially those belong to the Third World countries including Yemen. According to Amba-Rao (1993), despite the importance of CSR, a limited discussion is evident in the literature on CSR in the Third World countries. This limited discussion could be caused by several reasons such as the negligence for the vital effects of CSR on organizational performance, the paucity of allocated financial resources for CSR activities, the avoidance of enclosing CSR reports in annual reports of different enterprises, and the weakness in the government regulations and laws that motivate and regulate CSR activities in diverse economic sectors.

Yemen as a Third World country has modest concerns about CSR and few theoretical and empirical studies have addressed CSR and its impact on different managerial aspects in this country. As a way for bringing the attention of Yemenis (i.e., businessmen, businesswomen, government officials, media, academics, citizens, and others), Yemen held three summits in different cities concerning CSR during the 2000s and the early 2010s. The first summit was held in Sana'a City in 2008, the second summit was held in Sana'a City in 2009, and the third summit was held in Aden in 2010. It was clear to notice during those occasions that there is a misunderstanding about CSR and its essential functions towards stakeholders among different Yemeni enterprises. This could be due to the fact that most of the enterprises comprising the private sector in Yemen are family-owned businesses and the major concern of these

businesses is to maximize the shareholders' wealth in a short-term period without paying an attention for other social issues.

In this line and as a positive initiative towards CSR, only few enterprises have established dedicated units for following up and administering CSR activities and the Yemeni government itself starts slightly to focus more about this concept in the recent years. However, tangible impacts on Yemeni society produced by these CSR initiatives still weak and unconvincing, and most of the time diverse stakeholders do not have their expected benefits and rights resulted from such social initiatives. On the other hand, an observer living in Yemen can easily notice that the major interest of Yemeni for-profit enterprises—either those existent in public or private sector—concerning CSR is about offering charitable donations and financial religious or spiritual obligations to society (Al-Abbasi, 2011; Naji, 2010; Said, 2011). Furthermore, Yemeni government has supported CSR concept and enacted several laws in a try to reinforce this concept in society and among different for-profit enterprises owned by the government itself (i.e., SOEs). In this respect, the Yemeni government enacted the job law in 1995 that lists several obligations which for-profit enterprises should secure as a supporting way for its social responsibilities (Said, 2011). Said added that among these obligations are providing means of transportation for employees, providing places for accommodation, providing required occupational safety and health, providing required health care, and providing jobs for people with disabilities and other minorities such as women.

There are several studies—majorly conducted by Yemeni scholars—tackled CSR concept and its related issues in Yemen in both public and private sectors (Al-Abbasi, 2011; Al-Hamdi, 2003; Al-Hamdi & Ja'abil, 2008; Al-Kumaim, 2006; Naji, 2010; Said, 2011; Sharhan, 2009). Those scholars discussed CSR from different viewpoints and in

both public and private sectors. They studied the nature of the relationships between CSR and diverse managerial issues such as customer satisfaction, psychological or mental health, and accountability. For example, the study of Al-Hamdi (2003) discussed the marketing dimensions of CSR and their effects on the customer's satisfaction in Yemen. He found that the obligation degree of the researched enterprises towards marketing factors of CSR (i.e., protecting consumers, business ethics, and protecting environment) is moderately higher than the assumed arithmetic mean value. Moreover, the customer satisfaction concerning the social activities performed by these enterprises was weak among the respondents of this study. He concluded his study by referring to the fact that there is a significant relationship between the marketing dimensions of CSR and the customer satisfaction.

Another study conducted by Al-Kumaim (2006) for investigating the level of social responsibilities that a Yemeni government employee possesses. This scholar found out that nearly 44 percent of the Yemeni government employees in different six governorates possess a moderate level of social responsibilities and that nearly 56 percent of the same employees have a high level of social responsibilities. He concluded his study by arguing that there is no significant difference between female and male government employees concerning social responsibilities.

In a study conducted by Al-Hamdi and Ja'abil in 2008, they examined the extent of manager's perception concerning CSR concept and its resulted activities. They found out that the majority of respondents believe that their enterprises offer safe, healthy, and good quality products for their customers. They concluded that managers have positive feelings towards their enterprises and believe that these enterprises perform positive activities which reinforce their social responsibilities and obligations towards all

stakeholders (Al-Hamdi *et al.*, 2008). In this way, Sharhan (2009) examined in another study the relationship between CSR and psychological health of the students of Sana'a University and found out that those students have knowledge about what could CSR stand for and there is no difference between female and male students concerning this point. He claimed that the first-year students are more socially responsible than those who study in the last year. He concluded his study by stressing on the fact that social responsibility is positively related with the mental health among the female and male students of the University of Sana'a.

Among other studies concerning CSR initiatives in Yemen is the one conducted by Said (2011) about the possibility of applying accountability of CSR in industrial private enterprises in Yemen. Said found out in her study that there is a perception among industrial private enterprises in Yemen about the broad meaning of CSR concept. She also empirically observed that Yemeni industrial private enterprises pay attention to the overall CSR and to other different fields of CSR such as retention of employees, improving the relationship with consumers, and protecting the environment and natural resources in Yemen. She concluded her research by contending that industrial private enterprises in Yemen have no basic factors used for applying accountability of CSR. In another study, Al-Abbasi (2011) examined CSR through qualitative measures in Yemen and especially in the Taiz industrial zone where several private enterprises operate. Mainly, the case study of Al-Abbasi aimed at investigating the awareness of the society's members regarding CSR and the perception of the employees working in a private pioneering enterprise concerning its CSR activities in a Yemeni city. He contended that the study revealed the fact that there is a high level of awareness of CSR in Yemen among community's members and employees of this private enterprise. He

concluded his research by stating: “The private sector in Yemen is still in the first stage of implementing the concept of CSR in its broader meaning” (Al-Abbasi, 2011, p. 42).

2.12 Summary

This chapter succinctly traced the development in the related aspects of CSR and organizational performance in different societies which showed the importance of these concepts for businesses and their associated societies and stakeholders. The chapter reviewed chronologically the development of CSR concept starting from the early 1800s and up until the 21st century where CSR has new phases with more complexity and more ramified details. Garriga and Melé (2004) refer to such new phases and contend that CSR field presents not only a landscape of theories but also a proliferation of approaches, which are controversial, complex, and unclear. The chapter then tackled briefly several theories, principles, and models used in the literature of CSR. The focus was on the most important theories and models that other scholars depend on when conducting their studies about CSR. Both famous models related to CSR postulated by Archie Carroll (i.e., Carroll’s CSP model and Carroll’s pyramid of CSR) were reviewed since this study is mainly based on these models. The most important thing in these models is about the four-part definition of CSR depicted in the pyramid of CSR which are economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities.

Furthermore, the stakeholder theory posited by Freeman (1984) was discussed for its importance and for its pivotal association with CSR. Moreover, the chapter tackled CSR in other sectors, namely, public sector, through having a close look of CSR in SOEs because these for-profit public enterprises have important and indispensable contributions to different economies of several great industrial nations in the world.

The other variable in this study, namely, the organizational performance, was reviewed in this chapter and detailed with its two main types of measures (i.e., financial or objective and nonfinancial or subjective). The chapter discussed the fact that the literature redundantly addresses the financial measures of the organizational performance and fairly neglects its perceptual measures when assessing it. The chapter reviewed several studies regarding organizational performance and found that numerous scholars stress on the fact that CFP is positively related with CSR which makes the relationship between them positively significant. Other subjective measures used to evaluate the organizational performance were tackled in the chapter and it was found out that they are rarely investigated with CSR and this renders the literature likely to having a clear a gap in this area which this study tries modestly to fill.

This chapter was concluded by a review for the literature concerning CSR initiatives in Yemen. The review revealed that CSR concept is still nascent in this Third World country and that most of the for-profit enterprises—including Yemeni SOEs—deal with CSR as a charitable and benevolent issue emerging from the religious and spiritual obligations towards the society. Several other studies and researches were discussed which address CSR in Yemen from diverse perspectives and with different managerial issues.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The main objective of this study is to research the effect of the four components of CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) on the nonfinancial organizational performance in for-profit public (i.e., SOEs) and private organizations in Yemen. Besides, the study is intended to have an ostensible comparative analysis to determine any significant difference of CSR's adopted levels between different for-profit public and private enterprises. Accordingly, this chapter goes over the various methods which were used to study these relationships between independent and dependent variables. The main primary data source is obtained through using a quantitative method by distributing questionnaires among the sample's elements concerned with this study.

This chapter, namely, *Chapter III*, has several sections concerning the research methodology. The chapter discusses in its first sections the research framework and the developed hypotheses of the current study which are empirically examined to show the type and magnitude of the relationship between the study's dependent and independent variables. Among other sections contained in this chapter are the research design, research location, unit of analysis, population and sampling methods, research

instrument, data collection, and the last section is about the techniques used for data analysis.

3.2 Research Framework or Theoretical Framework

The theoretical area of this study is related to CSR—along with its four categories—as it influences the organizational performance of SOEs and private organizations operating in Yemen. This organizational performance is concerned in this study with perceptual, nonfinancial, or subjective aspects that differ from the accounting and financial objective aspects used to evaluate and measure the organizational performance. Some common measures of perceived organizational performance include product or service quality, innovation, retention policy, customer satisfaction, and management-staff interactions (Delaney *et al.*, 1996). Although the relationship between CSR and organizational financial performance has been copiously investigated in the literature, a very scant portion of the same plentiful literature tackles the influence of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance for different for-profit enterprises. One of the recent quantitative studies performed in a Nigerian bank for analyzing this relationship found out that the dimensions of CSR have clear effects on subjective organizational performance (Akanbi *et al.*, 2012).

On the other hand, writings of Roman *et al.* (1999) imply that the majority of researchers stress on the affirmative effect that corporate social performance (CSP) has on the corporate financial performance (CFP). Caring about the interests of diverse stakeholders is also important for a for-profit organization and among those stakeholders are employees, customers, local communities, government, and the society at large. Hence, this problematic process of managing and balancing the diverse stakeholders' interests results in adopting CSR activities which eventually leads to

enhancing the organizational financial performance. As Banerjee (2007) argues that stakeholder theory has moral overtones, so it focuses on what a for-profit organization should do in order to fulfill its social responsibilities.

The implementation of the corporate governance—which is primarily about properly governing the organization and managing well relationships between its various stakeholders—can be further facilitated with the leverage of CSR initiatives (Tuan, 2012). The link between the organizational performance (i.e., subjective and objective) and CSR could be indirectly supported through adopting corporate governance practices in organizations. According to Esa *et al.* (2012), in Malaysia and just after the 1997's Asian financial crisis, the Malaysian code on corporate governance was released which stresses that the organization's board should receive reports including indicators of objective and subjective organizational performances. Some of these objective indicators could be concerned with financial-oriented activities and other perceptual indicators could include indicators for the customers' satisfaction and product or service quality. The same researchers maintained that this requirement is expected to make some pressures on managements of organizations to involve in more socially responsible activities (Esa *et al.*, 2012).

Governments in developed and developing countries have also adopted the concepts of social responsibilities due to the numerous benefits that such adoption has on the interests of both individuals and their respective societies. State-owned enterprises (SOEs) as for-profit public entities have adopted also different CSR activities which reflect their strategic and modern way of thinking and their serious intentions for having a competitive advantage over their private competitors in the local markets. The writings of Amba-Rao (1993) are consistent with these thoughts when she points out

that there is a rising consensus that both private and public organizations should admit ethical responsibilities for the social welfare and the interests of individuals in their economic transactions. It is significant to refer to the essential role of the governments concerning CSR which aims at developing humans and their societies. In this way, Okoye (2012) argues that the basic authority of the country with its government is preserved to drive the developmental policies in the country and one essential policy among them is engaging with CSR and drive CSR developmental objectives by the government itself. Moreover, in a research conducted to analyze CSR activities of several large SOEs in China, Hinz (2009) claims that Chinese largest SOEs become more aware of CSR and its various activities due to the government's new policy guidelines about CSR activities and their applications in SOEs. He argues that the size of the largest SOEs and their tremendous profits are the reasons that could drive these enterprises to provide a key contribution to both environment and society if these SOEs would apply practices of CSR. This argument expounds that CSR is a major concern for both private and public for-profit organizations in the 21st century and that governments' commercial investments are now focused on the economic role of SOEs in their respective societies beside their intrinsic and fundamental social role that they have founded for.

For achieving the purposes of this study which are intended to analyze the impact of CSR on organizational performance, a considerable revision is done for *Chapter I* which contains the research objectives and questions and for *Chapter II* which reviews diverse literature related to the independent and dependent variables of the study. Accordingly, the theoretical framework is developed to identify and examine the relationship between different variables. The dependent variable is the organizational performance which is measured through perceptual or subjective criteria. The

independent variable is CSR which has four categories of responsibilities, namely, economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic. Figure 3.1. depicts graphically the relationships between different variables that contained in this study.

Figure 3.1.: Schematic Diagram of the Research Framework

3.3 Development of Research Hypotheses

The concept of CSR is concerned with various societal responsibilities that an enterprise (i.e., public or private) has towards the society operating in and commercially benefiting from. CSR also is concerned with the stakeholders that have interests in this enterprise itself. The four-tier pyramid of CSR—which was conceptualized by Archie Carroll in 1991—depicts the postulation that the total social responsibility of a business consists of discrete components and if they are taken together, they compose the whole (Carroll *et al.*, 2009). The same researchers argue that the socially responsible enterprise should strive to make a profit, obey the law, be ethical, and be a good corporate citizen. CSR is exploited now as a strategic tool used for enticing societies to accept and respond more to the products or services offered by various for-profit enterprises in different economic sectors resulting in more enhanced levels of organizational performance. In

this way, Ohlrich (2011) maintains that modern CSR can raise financial and marketing measures such as market share and revenue streams for corporations. This scholar claims that CSR has evolved from being seen and observed only as a charitable giving to the society.

The current study empirically evaluates the effect of the four distinct components of CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic) on the organizational performance justified by nonfinancial measures in for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen. According to Kothari (2004), in the empirical research, the researcher should first provide operational hypotheses and estimate the probable results then this researcher should strive to have enough data to prove or disprove these hypotheses. Accordingly, this study has developed several hypotheses which can be listed as follows:

Hypothesis 1₀ (null): A significant difference does not exist between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general. ($H1_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$)

Hypothesis 1_a (alternative): A significant difference exists between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general. ($H1_a: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)

Hypothesis 2_a: There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 2_b: There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 3_a: There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 3_b: There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 4_a: There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 4_b: There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 5_a: There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 5_b: There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 6_a: There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 6_b: There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 6_c: There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Hypothesis 6_d: There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

3.4 Research Design

The current study is an empirical quantitative study which is mainly based on data and depends on the experiment that leads to specific conclusions related to the research's hypotheses. The research design of this study contains the needed collecting methods for the information which are required for solving the research problem. Different components of the research design of this study are intended to explore the influence of the four categories of CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) on the nonfinancial organizational performance in for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen. Accordingly, the research design includes the analysis unit, research location, population, sampling technique, measurements and instruments of independent and dependent variables, data collection method, questionnaire design, data collection, and data analysis. Different statistical analyses suggested to be used for

having empirical results are also detailed in this chapter such as descriptive and inferential statistics.

For the purpose of this study, the quantitative data are obtained from a close-ended questionnaire that was disseminated among the elements of the research sample. The questions are administered to a sample of selected for-profit public and private organizations in the Capital City of Sana'a, Yemen. These questions are used to identify the effects of the four components of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance. The questionnaire is also used for measuring any significant difference between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting CSR in general.

3.5 Unit of Analysis

Typically and among different researchers, there are three different units of analysis from which a researcher can select: (i) the individual; (ii) the group; and (iii) the organization. The unit of analysis used in the current study is the organization. This study focuses on two main types of for-profit organizations. The first type is concerned with the private enterprises that operate in Sana'a in different economic sectors (i.e., raw materials, manufacturing, trade, and services). The second type is interested in the public for-profit organizations, namely, state-owned enterprises (SOEs), which are administered by the government and have for-profit purposes.

3.6 Research Location

This study is conducted in different for-profit private and public enterprises (i.e., SOEs) in the Capital City of Sana'a, Yemen. The selected economic sectors for conducting this study are raw materials, manufacturing, services, and trade. The reason for selecting these sectors is to find out the activities of CSR conducted by enterprises forming these

sectors and the impact of these activities on their nonfinancial organizational performance. Some of these enterprises have not been imposed to the subject that this study focuses on which is about CSR and its effects on the nonfinancial organizational performance.

3.7 Population

The study is conducted in the Capital City of Sana'a and the unit of analysis is the organization. Accordingly, the population of this study consists of two main groups. These groups include all for-profit public and private enterprises (i.e., organizations) operating in the Capital City of Sana'a and listed as SOEs in the Ministry of Finance and as private enterprises in the Ministry of Industry and Trade. As it was discussed in the literature review, public for-profit enterprises are the state-owned enterprises (i.e., SOEs known as economic units or for-profit enterprises) which are administered by the Yemeni government and have commercial and profitable purposes. The private enterprises included in the study's population are classified into three key types, namely, partnerships, joint-stock companies (corporations), and limited companies. The lists containing the names of these enterprises were obtained from different government sources. The names and titles of the SOEs were obtained from the sector of economic units in the Ministry of Finance whereas the lists of the private enterprises were obtained from the Ministry of Industry and Trade in Sana'a, Yemen. This population includes all the enterprises which have for-profit purposes and operate in four main economic sectors, namely, raw materials, manufacturing, services, and trade. A survey instrument—in the form of close-ended questionnaires—was developed for this study. Later on, these questionnaires were disseminated among for-profit public and private enterprises operating in the Capital City of Sana'a.

3.8 Sample

For the purposes of this study, the samples were selected from the two main population groups (i.e., SOEs and private enterprises). The two lists—which contain the titles of the for-profit public and private enterprises comprising the population—were used as the sample. The first list of the for-profit public enterprises contains nearly 55 SOEs divided into the three key types, namely, productive, service, and mixed sectors. On the other hand, nearly 700 private enterprises were included in the list of the private enterprises in Yemen. These private enterprises are divided into partnerships, joint-stock companies (corporations), and limited companies.

The criteria of the enterprise selection are based on the following: (i) the total number of the enterprise's employees should exceed 50 employees; and (ii) the age of the enterprise should be at least 10 years and more (i.e., foundation year is 2002 and before). Size of the organization is discussed by several scholars due to its relationship with other variables. According to Park (2010), larger enterprises usually have more available resources and are able to engage in more CSR activities. Moreover, Verbenko (2011) contends that larger firms have a larger operational impact and for this reason they are expected to engage in more CSR activities in order to obtain a higher rating for socially responsible activities. Thence, enterprises with 50 or more employees are included in the sample as suggested by Moideenkutty *et al.* (2011) because higher cutoff will significantly reduce the sample size. The same thing can be considered about the age of the enterprise which is indicated by several scholars as an influential factor when trying to measure other variables in different empirical studies. For example, Park (2010) claims that older enterprises may have a competitive advantage within their domain, and thus influence revenues. Furthermore, Carroll and Hannan (2000) maintain that several studies have proposed that the growth of the enterprise along with its

performance degenerate with age. Consequently, other enterprises that do not meet these criteria are eliminated from the sample of the study since it is supposed that Yemeni enterprises with small sizes and short tenures may not be large and mature enough to have any effective CSR activities in the society. As a result, nearly 255 enterprises were eventually selected from the two lists for disseminating the questionnaires among them.

Since the population of the study does not form a homogenous group, the stratified sampling is the technique used for generating the sample. In this technique, the population is divided into several homogenous sub-populations (strata) and after that items are randomly selected from each stratum to form the sample. Moreover, a random stratified sampling method is implemented for selecting the elements of the sample (i.e., enterprises). In this respect, Kothari (2004) states: “if the items selected from each stratum is based on simple random sampling the entire procedure, first stratification and then simple random sampling, is known as stratified random sampling” (p. 16).

In addition, all questionnaires of the study were personally delivered by the researcher himself to the representatives of the for-profit public and private enterprises working in the middle- and top-level management positions within these enterprises. The positions of those representatives include chief executive officers (CEOs), general managers, chief financial officers (CFOs), human resource directors, marketing directors, and also consultants.

3.9 Questionnaire Design

In this study, the survey method was used by asking respondents close-ended questions included in a questionnaire. This questionnaire consists of three principal sections as

shown in Table 3.1. These sections are: (i) demographic information; (ii) corporate social responsibility (CSR); and (iii) nonfinancial organizational performance.

Table 3.1.: Principal sections of the study’s questionnaire

Section Name	Description	Number of Items
Section 1	Demographic information	8
Section 2	Corporate social responsibility (CSR)	32
Section 3	Nonfinancial organizational performance	8

Items (i.e., questions) related to the second section of the questionnaire concerning CSR use five-point Likert-type responses that give the range of 1 = extremely not important, 2 = not important, 3 = do not know, 4 = important, and 5 = extremely important. Similarly, the questions related to the third section of the questionnaire concerning the nonfinancial organizational performance use five-point Likert-type responses that give the range of 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree. ‘Section 1’ of the questionnaire has the information concerning the demographic values for both the respondents and their respective organizations. These values include the respondent’s gender, age group, educational level, current position, type of enterprise, nature of enterprise’s activities, enterprise’s date of foundation, and the total number of the enterprise’s employees in 2013. In ‘Section 2’, the respondents rated the level of importance or unimportance with each item of the four categories comprising CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities). The last section (i.e., ‘Section 3’) of the questionnaire measures the respondents’ subjective or perceptual level of agreement or disagreement with each item comprising the nonfinancial organizational performance of their respective enterprises. The full items

of the three sections are contained in the questionnaire which can be seen in APPENDIX A.

3.10 Measurement

In this study, the independent variable, namely, CSR, is assessed by four dimensions consisting of 32 items with an additional one item for evaluating the overall level of adopting periodically CSR in the organization. Additionally, the dependent variable (i.e., nonfinancial organizational performance) is assessed with eight items. All items of the questionnaire are evaluated on a five-point Likert scale (interval scale) ranging from 1 (extremely not important/strongly disagree) to 5 (extremely important/strongly agree). Consequently, this study uses reliable scales drawn from the literature which are slightly modified, adapted, and employed in the survey and these scales are detailed in the next sections.

3.10.1 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Different models for describing CSR have been discussed by several scholars (Carroll, 1991; Certo & Certo, 2009; Davis, 1975; Wood, 1991; Zu, 2009). One of the most accepted models used for describing CSR is the one postulated by Archie Carroll in 1979 known as the four-part definition of CSR. This model involves what a business could have of different types of social responsibilities towards society. Archie Carroll in 1991 evolved his four-part definition of CSR into the Carroll's pyramid of CSR which consists of the four key categories of CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities). A standard questionnaire for measuring these four dimensions of CSR is adopted for this study provided by Professor Archie B. Carroll himself on 22nd of January 2013 to the researcher of this study. Professor Archie B. Carroll thankfully added in his message: "I am attaching the questionnaire that was used

on the four-part definition/model” (Archie B. Carroll, personal communication, January 22, 2013). This instrument for measuring CSR four parts was included in Carroll’s (1991) article. This scale assesses the four main categories of responsibilities comprising CSR through the views and opinions of respondents who belong to middle- and top-level management of different for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen. These responsibilities include economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic which comprise the four-part of CSR model.

The CSR questionnaire is used for assessing corporate social responsibility orientation (CSRO) based upon Carroll’s 1979 four-part CSR model. The long-form original questionnaire consists of 60 questions and it was abridged and modified into a short-form questionnaire consists of 32 questions in this study. This was done by the researcher to make it more acceptable, easier, and faster to be completed when being disseminated among different respondents who have top and middle positions in their associated enterprises. The 32-item questionnaire has a five-point Likert scale (i.e., 1 = extremely not important, 2 = not important, 3 = do not know, 4 = important, and 5 = extremely important) in which respondents are asked to offer their impressions concerning distinct items of the questionnaire. Several scholars in the literature have used Carroll’s CSR instrument to measure CSR and showed satisfactory and consistent results (Akanbi & Ofoegbu, 2012; Aupperle, Carroll, & Hatfield, 1985; Tan & Komaran, 2006). According to Aupperle *et al.* (1985), they tested reliability of the Carroll’s CSR instrument consisted of four parts and found reliable values for Cronbach’s alphas (i.e., economic component, $\alpha = .93$; legal component, $\alpha = .84$; ethical component, $\alpha = .84$; and philanthropic component, $\alpha = .87$).

3.10.2 Organizational Performance

As the literature review has discussed in the previous chapter, the concept of organizational performance can be assessed by two key methods, namely, objective and subjective. In this study, the dependent variable, namely, the organizational performance, is assessed by subjective or nonfinancial measures through respondents' perceptions on their enterprises' nonfinancial performance. The instrument used to measure the nonfinancial organizational performance in this study is proposed by Delaney and Huselid (1996). This instrument has eight subjective and nonfinancial items for assessing organizational performance (i.e., products or services quality, innovation of products or services, employees' attraction, employee's retention, customers' satisfaction, management and employment relationship, employees' relationships with managers, and relationships among employees themselves). Assessing organizational performance using subjective measures by this instrument was adopted by several scholars and researchers in the literature (Chan & Mak, 2012; Delaney & Huselid, 1996; Guest & Peccei, 2001; Katou, 2012; Kuo, 2011; Lee & Lee, 2009; Lin & Kuo, 2007). Accordingly, eight adapted statements—that are included in the disseminated questionnaires among respondents—were used for measuring the perceived organizational performance of the different for-profit enterprises comprising the sample of this study. Each statement gives the range of 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree. Delaney *et al.* (1996) maintained that they had a value of .85 for the Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α) for their scale that was used for measuring perceived organizational performance consisted of originally seven items (i.e., questions).

There are several justifications that made the researcher of this study to adopt subjective measures for assessing nonfinancial organizational performance of the for-profit public

and private enterprises in Yemen. One of these justifications is the difficulty in having accurate and real financial data when using financial measures to assess the organizational performance. In fact, the majority of the private enterprises in Yemen are family-owned businesses and the conservative owners of these businesses would not easily reveal their financial data for others under any reason—including researchers and academics—in a Third World country like Yemen especially if these data have sensitive and classified information. This is in line with the writings of (Dollinger *et al.*, 1992) when they state: “In addition, some privately held firms are often reluctant to provide sensitive financial data even with the guarantee of confidentiality” (p. 9). In the same line, Powel (1992) suggests to use subjective measures instead of financial measures because private enterprises would not provide confidential information extracted from their financial statements as a matter of policy. Another reason for using subjective measures in this study is related to the unavailability of accurate financial information of Yemeni for-profit enterprises. The absence of having a trusted government data center in Yemen containing different factual and precise financial indicators of different enterprises is another barrier for utilizing financial measures for assessing organizational performance in general.

In this respect, Boulay (2008) adds that “The limited accessibility of financial data from privately held firms, such as small and medium-sized enterprises, makes the use of objective organizational performance measures even more complex” (p. 44). He adds that scholars instead can use subjective indicators for measuring organizational performance which could be concluded from the reported perceptions of enterprises’ managers. Other justifications for using nonfinancial measures in this study are included in the writings of other scholars such as Robert Carton, John Delaney, and Mark Huselid. According to Carton (2004), many scholars contend that a researcher could

resort to nonfinancial perceptual measures when financial measures are hard to be obtained or found. In addition, the writings of Delaney and Huselid (1996) claim that subjective measures of organizational performance are frequently used in academic studies conducted by different scholars.

3.11 Data Collection

This quantitative study uses a questionnaire as the instrument to measure its different variables. Hence, the process of data collection is made through primary available resources in the study's location. The instrument's items concerning the corporate social responsibility (CSR)—represented by the four independent variables—are adopted from Carroll's CSR model known as CSRO (i.e., corporate social responsibility orientation). Moreover, the items of the instrument related to the dependent variable (i.e., the organizational performance) are adopted from the survey prepared by Delaney *et al.* (1996) that measures nonfinancial organizational performance. Instruments with their items from these two sources are used as references and are adapted and abridged whenever applicable to fit the proposed theoretical framework of this study. Nearly 255 questionnaires were distributed personally among the respondents in the top- and middle-level management who administer different for-profit public enterprises (SOEs) and private enterprises in Yemen. Approximately, 103 valid questionnaires (i.e., 40.4 percent of the total disseminated questionnaires) were gradually collected back and then prepared for the analysis process.

3.12 Data Analysis Techniques

Different techniques of data analyses help researchers to have organized ideas about collected data and to build consistent conclusions concerning their studies. Accordingly, collected data of this study were analyzed with descriptive and inferential statistical

analyses using the program SPSS (i.e., Statistical Package for the Social Science) version 13.0 for Microsoft Windows. The items and other demographic variables of the collected questionnaires were coded before they were keyed in the SPSS program. Then, factor analyses for the 32 items of the CSR and the 8 items of the nonfinancial organizational performance were conducted to obtain the KMO (i.e., Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) values. In this respect and according to Ntoumanis (2001), the factor analysis uses KMO which is a measure of sampling adequacy that examines the degree of correlation among the questionnaire's items. Moreover, Muijs (2004) states: "The factor analysis was designed to see whether each item measured the subscale it was supposed to measure to look at construct validity" (p. 70).

After that, the reliability analysis was conducted for obtaining the results of Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α) for each independent and dependent variable included in the questionnaire to determine the consistency of the study's instrument. Furthermore, frequency analyses were conducted concerning the demographic information collected from the respondents such as age, gender, job position, nature of the organization's activities, and other information. Subsequently, correlation analyses—depending on the values of the Pearson's coefficient (r)—were utilized to test the relationship between independent variables (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) and dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance, and to determine the type and magnitude of these relationships. In addition, linear multiple regression analysis was used for determining the most influential independent variable or variables on the dependent variable and in determining which are the main predictors—among CSR dimensions—for the nonfinancial organizational performance as the dependent variable of this study. The last analyses were conducted using Welch and independent-samples t -Tests for measuring the difference and its significance of the

level of adopting CSR activities between for-profit public and private enterprises with the assumption of having normal distributions for the gathered data of the dependent and independent variables.

3.12.1 Descriptive Statistics

Several descriptive analyses were used in this study including frequency distributions which include measures of central tendency (i.e., mean and standard deviation) and other charts such as bar charts which graphically describe the collected data. These descriptive statistics are used to describe the demographic information of the respondents who replied the questionnaires and majorly formed the sample of this study.

3.12.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential analyses were utilized in this study which include the bivariate correlations using Pearson's coefficient, the linear multiple regression analysis, and comparing the means using the *t*-Test analyses. For the Pearson's correlation coefficient (*r*), Kothari (2004) stated: "Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation (or simple correlation) is the most widely used method of measuring the degree of relationship between two variables" (p. 139). He added that the value of '*r*' rests between ± 1 . Moreover, Cohen (1988) mentioned the criteria for describing how 'strong' a correlation is. He claimed that correlation coefficients below the value of .30 indicate a weak relationship between correlated variables, coefficients between .30 and .49 indicate a moderate relationship, and coefficients of .50 and over indicate a strong relationship. For the multiple regression analysis, it is used to have a prediction for the dependent variable relying on its covariance with all other related independent variables of the study (Kothari, 2004). This analysis shows the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable and

specifies which one of those independent variables has the most influence on the dependent variable. For the *t*-Test, it is used for determining the significant mean differences between two groups in the variable of interest (Sekaran, 2003). This kind of analysis was employed in this study to examine if there is any significant difference between the overall adoption of CSR activities in SOEs and private enterprises in Yemen.

3.13 Summary

This chapter has discussed the research design needed for conducting this study which aims at investigating the impact of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance in different Yemeni for-profit public and private enterprises. Through this chapter, several aspects of the research design were explained including theoretical framework, hypotheses, location of the study, unit of analysis, population and sample techniques, and also the measurements and adopted instruments for both independent and dependent variables. At the end of this chapter, the processes of data collection and data analysis using distinct statistical analyses were discussed in detail.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter, namely, *Chapter IV*, has several sections and subsections regarding the diverse results of the statistical analyses about this study. These statistical analyses comprise descriptive analyses about demographic variables and other inferential analyses about different relationships between independent variable (i.e., corporate social responsibility) and dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance. The descriptive analyses that were used include frequency distributions such as the measures of central tendency (i.e., mean and standard deviation) whereas the inferential analyses that were utilized in this study include the bivariate correlation, the linear multiple regression, and the *t*-Test analyses. The data were analyzed using the program SPSS version 13.0 for Microsoft Windows to implement the diverse statistical analyses needed for this study. This chapter also presents the reliability and KMO tests for different items used in the study's instrument.

4.2 Sample Characteristics

Around 255 questionnaires were disseminated among different respondents working in various Yemeni SOEs and private enterprises in the Capital City of Sana'a during the months of October, November, and December 2013. Those respondents were employees who have top- or middle-level positions in their for-profit enterprises (i.e.,

SOEs and private enterprises) including CEOs (Chief executive officers), general managers, consultants, department managers, and section heads. The researcher delivered himself the questionnaires to the respondents and a period of nearly 15 minutes was granted for each respondent to fill and return the questionnaire to the researcher. Due to the availability and time restrictions of the respondents, other questionnaires were left with those respondents and were later collected by the researcher himself in other days. Unfortunately, some of these questionnaires were lost by the respondents and also other questionnaires have never been collected. However, the total returned and collected questionnaires were 149 and only 103 of them were valid for further analysis. Those 103 valid questionnaires represent nearly 40.4 percent of the total distributed questionnaires among all respondents in SOEs and other private enterprises. Table 4.1. shows several details concerning the distributed questionnaires among for-profit enterprises included in the sample of the study.

Table 4.1.: Analysis of the distributed questionnaires among for-profit enterprises

Location of Distribution	Questionnaires				
	Distributed	Returned	Discarded	Valid	Valid Rate
Public enterprises (SOEs)	55	42	11	31	56.4%
Private enterprises	200	107	35	72	36%
Total	255	149	46	103	40.4%

4.3 Demographic Characteristics

The total number of collected and valid questionnaires is 103 out of 255 distributed ones. The program SPSS version 13.0 was used to statistically analyze the demographic data using the descriptive frequency statistics. These demographic variables are shown and described in the subsequent tables included in this chapter. The first demographic variable which was described is the gender and it is shown in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2.: Frequency Distribution - Gender

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female	8	7.8
Male	95	92.2

The total number of respondents is 103 working in top- and middle-level managerial positions in the for-profit public and private enterprises. From this total number, 95 respondents were males with a percentage of 92.2% and eight female respondents replied the questionnaire with a percentage of 7.8% only. The distribution of the second demographic variable, the age of respondents, is shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3.: Frequency Distribution - Age of Respondents

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Under 25 years	4	3.9
25 to 34 years	36	35
35 to 44 years	40	38.8
45 to 54 years	18	17.5
55 to 64 years	5	4.9
Above 64 years	-	-

The frequency distribution of this demographic variable shows that the major respondents are either in their second half of thirties or their first half of forties, (i.e., from 35 to 44 years old), with a percentage of 38.8%. The total number of those major respondents is 40 ones. The second major category is the respondents with ages from 25 to 34 years old with a total number of 36 respondents which represents 35% of the total number of respondents. Other subsequent groups of age are from 45 to 54 years with 17.5 percent then the group from 55 to 64 years with 4.9 percent and 5 respondents. The

last and least group of ages is under 25 years with only 4 respondents. The frequency analysis which shows the distribution of the educational level of the respondents is shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4.: Frequency Distribution - Level of Education

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
High School Graduate	4	3.9
Diploma after the High School	6	5.8
Bachelor's Degree	81	78.6
Master's Degree	8	7.8
Doctoral Degree	4	3.9

The frequency distribution of this demographic and descriptive variable shows that the highest educational level among the respondents is the bachelor's degree with a percentage of 78.6% and a total number of 81 respondents. Almost 7.8% of the major respondents hold Master's degrees which represents the second major educational level among respondents with 8 persons. Moreover, almost 6 respondents or 5.8% hold diplomas after the high school. Only 4 respondents have high school certificates from the total number of respondents with a percentage of 3.9% and the same number and the same percentage (i.e., 4 and 3.9% respectively) for the holders of doctoral degrees among the respondents.

Another major frequency distribution is the current position that a respondent holds in the for-profit private and public enterprises forming the sample of the study. Table 4.5. represents this descriptive variable for the 103 respondents.

Table 4.5.: Frequency Distribution - Current Job Position

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
CEO (Chief Executive Officer)	6	5.8
General Manager	8	7.8
Consultant	3	2.9
Department Manager	74	71.8
Section Head	12	11.7

The table suggests that the majority of the respondents are department managers or directors with a total number of 74 respondents or 71.8%. A percentage of 11.7% represents the second major position of the respondents which is a section head with a total number of 12 respondents. General managers working in SOEs represent 8 respondents out of the total number of respondents or 7.8 percent. A percentage of 5.8% represents the fourth major position of the respondents which is a CEO with a total number of 6 respondents. The last position the respondents assume in the sample of this study is the consultant with only a percentage of 2.9% and only 3 persons. The frequency analysis which shows the distribution of the type of the enterprise is shown in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6.: Frequency Distribution - Type of the For-Profit Enterprise

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Private enterprise	72	69.9
Public enterprise (State-owned Enterprise or SOE)	31	30.1

The table shows that the majority of the researched enterprises are in the private sector with a total number of 72 organizations or 69.9 percent. A percentage of 30.1% represents the second major type of the researched enterprises which are SOEs (i.e., public for-profit enterprises) with a total number of 31 organizations. The frequency

analysis which explains the distribution of the nature of enterprise's activity is shown in Table 4.7.

Table 4.7.: Frequency Distribution - Nature of the Enterprise's Activity

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Private Service Sector	47	45.6
Private Manufacturing or Product Sector	24	23.3
Public Service Sector	22	21.4
Public Manufacturing or Product Sector	10	9.7

The table indicates that the majority of the researched enterprises operate in the private service sector with a total number of 47 organizations or 45.6 percent. A percentage of 23.3% represents the second major nature of the enterprises' activity which is private manufacturing or product sector with a total number of 24 organizations. Enterprises belong to the public service sector represent 22 ones of the total number of researched organizations or 21.4%. The last type of the enterprises' activity is the public manufacturing or product sector with only a percentage of 9.7% and only 10 public organizations. The frequency analysis which demonstrates the distribution of the enterprise's date of foundation is shown in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8.: Frequency Distribution - Enterprise's Date of Foundation

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Before 1940	3	2.9
From 1940 to 1950	6	5.8
From 1951 to 1960	3	2.9
From 1961 to 1970	14	13.6
From 1971 to 1980	27	26.2
From 1981 to 1990	22	21.4
From 1991 to 2002	28	27.2

The table shows that the majority of the researched enterprises have been founded during the 1990s to the early 2000s (i.e., from 1991 to 2002) with a total number of 28 organizations or 27.2 percent. A percentage of 26.2% represents the second major date of foundation for the researched enterprises which is the decade of the 1970s (i.e., from 1971 to 1980) with a total number of 27 organizations. Enterprises that have been established during the 1980s (i.e., from 1981 to 1990) represent the third major part with 22 ones of the total number of researched organizations or 21.4%. During the decade of the 1960s, namely, from 1961 to 1970, almost 14 enterprises were founded with a percentage of 13.6% among the total number of other organizations. Moreover, six enterprises, which represent 5.8% of the total researched enterprises, have been founded in the 1940s (i.e., from 1941 to 1950). The last and least percentage for the date of foundation, namely, 2.9, is for the enterprises which have been founded during the 1950s (i.e., from 1951 to 1960) and before the 1940s with only three organizations for each period. The frequency analysis which shows the distribution of the enterprise's total number of employees in 2013 is demonstrated in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9.: Frequency Distribution - Enterprise's Total Number of Employees in 2013

Item	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Less than 50 employees	-	-
From 50 to 250	41	39.8
From 251 to 500	19	18.4
From 501 to 1000	12	11.7
From 1001 to 3000	20	19.4
From 3001 to 5000	5	4.9
From 5001 to 10000	4	3.9
More than 10000 employees	2	1.9

The table shows that the majority of the enterprises' labor force in 2013 is in the range of 50 to 250 employees with 41 for-profit enterprises or 39.8% of the total researched organizations. A percentage of 19.4% represents the second major category of the enterprise's total number of employees in 2013 with a total number of 20 organizations that have between 1001 to 3000 employees. Enterprises with a labor force between 251 to 500 employees represent 19 ones of the total number of organizations or 18.4 percent. Moreover, enterprises with a labor force between 501 and 1000 employees represent 12 ones of the total number of organizations or 11.7%. The last total amounts of labor force in 2013 in the researched enterprises are for larger enterprises that have more than 3000 employees. There are five enterprises that have employees from 3001 to 5000 (almost 4.9% of the total number of researched enterprises). Also, there are four enterprises that have employees from 5001 to 10000 (almost 3.9% of the total number of researched enterprises). Only two researched enterprises have more than 10000 employees (only 1.9% of the total number of the researched enterprises).

4.4 Goodness of Measure

Several statistical analyses were implemented for examining the factors' structure of the scales used to measure both of the independent variable and its four categories (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) and also the dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance.

4.4.1 Factor Analysis

According to Ling (2011), factor analysis is used for exploring the inter-relationships among the set of independent and dependent variables during the early stages of a study. Moreover, Coakes *et al.* (2005) state: "When the researcher's goal is to construct a reliable test, factor analysis is an additional means of determining whether items are

tapping into the same construct” (p. 154). Consequently, the factor analysis was performed on the 32 items used for measuring the independent variable, namely, the corporate social responsibility. The value of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) was used to measure the sampling adequacy for the independent variable composed of four categories (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities). This value of KMO was .796 which is larger than the minimum value (i.e., .60) suggested by Coakes *et al.* (2005) for a good factor analysis. Besides, the Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was statistically significant at .000 (p-value < .05). Therefore, the factor analysis is considered proper and supportive for the factorability of the correlation.

In the same way, the factor analysis was performed on the eight items used for measuring the dependent variable (i.e., the nonfinancial organizational performance). The value of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) was used to measure the sampling adequacy for the dependent variable composed of one category measured by eight close-ended questions. This value of KMO was .829 which is above the minimum suggested value (i.e., .60) for a good factor analysis. Moreover, the factor analysis according to this value is considered appropriate and supportive for the factorability of the correlation since the Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was statistically significant at .000 (p-value < .05).

4.4.2 Reliability Test

In this study, the reliability test was performed for having more information about the relationships between individual items in the scales of the study. Several reliabilities tests were used for studying the measurement scales' properties and the items forming these scales and instruments. According to Ntoumanis (2001), the Cronbach’s alpha coefficient (α) is the most frequently used index of reliability which reflects the average

correlation among the items that constitute a scale. Based on the outputs of the reliability analyses, all scales used in this study are steadily and internally consistent. These results obtained from performing the reliability analyses are shown in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10.: Reliability Analyses of the Study's Instruments

Description of Variable	Number of Items	Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α)
Dependent variable		
Nonfinancial Organizational Performance (NFOP)	8	.864
Independent variables		
Economic Responsibilities (Eco_CSR)	8	.701
Legal Responsibilities (Leg_CSR)	8	.803
Ethical Responsibilities (Eth_CSR)	8	.737
Philanthropic Responsibilities (Phi_CSR)	8	.894

This table shows the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients of the independent and dependent variables and all these values are over than .70 range. Hence and based on the obtained results, the internal consistency reliability of the measures used in this study can be considered good and acceptable. The scientist Sekaran (2003) states: "The closer the reliability coefficient gets to 1.0, the better. In general, reliabilities less than .60 are considered to be poor, those in the .70 range, acceptable, and those over .80 good." (p. 311).

Consequently, the result indicates that the Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α) for the eight-item related to the nonfinancial organizational performance measure is .864 which indicates a good reliability's value. Other values for Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α)

concerned with the independent variables (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) are considered also highly acceptable and good. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α) for the independent variable known as economic responsibilities, shown in Table 4.10., is .701 which is considered an acceptable value for measuring the consistency of the eight items comprising this variable. Other values for other independent variables are legal responsibilities with $\alpha = .803$, ethical responsibilities with $\alpha = .737$, and a value of $\alpha = .894$ for philanthropic responsibilities which represents the highest value among all other values obtained in this study.

4.5 Descriptive Analyses

As their name implies, descriptive statistics are used to describe the data collected in studies and to accurately characterize the variables under observation within a specific sample. For this study, descriptive analysis includes the mean and standard deviation for the four dimensions of the corporate social responsibility and the nonfinancial organizational performance. These main descriptive analyses that focus on the mean and the standard deviation (S.D.) for the dependent and independent variables are obtained and shown in Table 4.11.

Table 4.11.: Descriptive Analyses for Dependent and Independent Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation (S.D.)
Nonfinancial Organizational Performance (NFOP)	4.31	.535
Economic Responsibilities (Eco_CSR)	4.33	.437
Legal Responsibilities (Leg_CSR)	4.44	.507
Ethical Responsibilities (Eth_CSR)	4.36	.454
Philanthropic Responsibilities (Phi_CSR)	3.74	.771

Table 4.11. shows the descriptive statistical results of the main study's variables (i.e., nonfinancial organizational performance and the four components of the corporate social responsibility). Through examining the results shown in this table, it is inferred that the respondents generally expressed that they were satisfied with the overall nonfinancial organizational performance of their respective enterprises (Mean = 4.31, S.D. = .535). All in all, those respondents also expressed that they were concerned with the economic responsibilities (Mean = 4.33, S.D. = .437), the legal responsibilities (Mean = 4.44, S.D. = .507), and the ethical responsibilities of their respective enterprises (Mean = 4.36, S.D. = .454). Alternatively, the respondents expressed that they were moderately and fairly concerned with the philanthropic responsibilities of their respective enterprises (Mean = 3.74, S.D. = .771).

4.5.1 Organizational Performance with Economic Responsibilities

As mentioned earlier in this chapter, eight items were used to measure the respondent's perception on the nonfinancial organizational performance of their enterprises with respect to these enterprises' economic responsibilities. Averagely, the respondents are satisfied and concerned with the existing corporate social responsibilities of their enterprises in relation to the economic responsibilities adopted and practiced by their organizations.

According to the frequency distribution of the eight items concerning the economic responsibilities, the respondents feedback is the highest (Mean = 4.81, S.D. = .525) regarding their enterprises' concern for maintaining a strong competitive position in the Yemeni market. The respondents' feedback has also indicated a high mean value on the enterprises' concern of being committed to being as profitable as possible (Mean = 4.68, S.D. = .675) and followed by ensuring that a high level of operating efficiency is

maintained by the enterprises (Mean = 4.53, S.D. = .607). There is a slightly higher indication of the respondents' feedback about the enterprises' concern of monitoring new opportunities that can enhance their financial health (Mean = 4.47, S.D. = .639) and followed by the concern of allocating organizational resources as efficiently as possible (Mean = 4.35, S.D. = .667) as well as the enterprises' concern of defining a successful firm as the one which is consistently profitable (Mean = 4.06, S.D. = .838).

However, the respondents' feedback concerning the enterprises' viewing of consisting profitability as a useful measure of organizational performance indicates average (Mean = 4.00, S.D. = .970). Moreover, the lowest respondents' feedback is regarding the concern of their enterprises in pursuing only those opportunities which provide the best rate of return (Mean = 3.73, S.D. = 1.059). Generally, the respondents appear to have slightly high concern (Mean = 4.33, S.D. = .437) with the economic responsibilities of their enterprises.

4.5.2 Organizational Performance with Legal Responsibilities

As indicated earlier in this chapter, eight items were used to measure the respondent's perception on the nonfinancial organizational performance of their enterprises with respect to these enterprises' legal responsibilities. On average, the respondents are satisfied and concerned with the existing corporate social responsibilities of their enterprises in relation to the legal responsibilities adopted and practiced by their organizations.

Out of the eight items comprising the legal responsibilities, the respondents feedback regarding their enterprises' concern for performing in a manner consistent with expectations of the Yemeni government and the Yemeni laws is the highest (Mean = 4.71, S.D. = .588). The respondents' feedback has also indicated a high mean value on

the enterprises' concern of fulfilling seriously their legal responsibilities (Mean = 4.65, S.D. = .622) and followed by being committed to abiding by Yemeni laws and regulations (Mean = 4.64, S.D. = .669). There is a slightly higher indication of the respondents' feedback about the enterprises' concern of recognizing that corporate integrity and ethical behavior go beyond mere compliance with Yemeni laws and regulations (Mean = 4.50, S.D. = .752) and followed by the concern of viewing compliance with the law as a useful measure of the organizational performance (Mean = 4.40, S.D. = .796) as well as the enterprises' concern of providing goods and services which at least meet minimal legal requirements (Mean = 4.31, S.D. = .852).

However, the respondents' feedback concerning preventing social norms from being compromised in order to achieve organizational goals by their enterprises indicates average (Mean = 4.18, S.D. = 1.046). Moreover, the lowest respondents' feedback is regarding the concern of their enterprises in defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its legal obligations (Mean = 4.16, S.D. = .826). In general, the respondents appear to have slightly high concern (Mean = 4.44, S.D. = .507) with their enterprises' legal responsibilities.

4.5.3 Organizational Performance with Ethical Responsibilities

As detailed earlier in this chapter, eight items were used to measure the respondent's perception on the nonfinancial organizational performance of their enterprises with respect to these enterprises' ethical responsibilities. Commonly, the respondents are satisfied and concerned with the existing corporate social responsibilities of their enterprises in relation to the ethical responsibilities adopted and practiced by their organizations.

According to the frequency distribution of the eight items concerning the ethical responsibilities, the respondents feedback is the highest (Mean = 4.74, S.D. = .523) regarding their enterprises' concern for fulfilling all their tax obligations. The respondents' feedback has also indicated a high mean value on the enterprises' concern of advertising goods and services in an ethically fair and responsible manner (Mean = 4.54, S.D. = .711) and followed by avoiding discrimination against women (Mean = 4.48, S.D. = .726). There is a slightly higher indication of the respondents' feedback about the enterprises' concern of monitoring new opportunities which can enhance the ethical and moral image of the enterprises in the society (Mean = 4.43, S.D. = .553) and followed by the concern of performing in a manner consistent with expectations of societal mores and ethical norms (Mean = 4.42, S.D. = .761) as well as the enterprises' concern of defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its ethical and moral responsibilities (Mean = 4.39, S.D. = .689).

Nevertheless, the respondents' feedback concerning the enterprises' avoidance of compromising societal norms and ethics in order to achieve goals indicates average (Mean = 4.30, S.D. = .861). In addition, the lowest feedback of the respondents is regarding the concern of their enterprises in not discouraging the 'whistle blowing' at any corporate level (Mean = 3.57, S.D. = 1.134). Overall, the respondents seem to have slightly high concern (Mean = 4.36, S.D. = .454) with their enterprises' ethical responsibilities.

4.5.4 Organizational Performance with Philanthropic Responsibilities

As revealed earlier in this chapter, the respondent's perception on the nonfinancial organizational performance of their enterprises with respect to these enterprises' philanthropic responsibilities was measured using eight items. All in all, the respondents

are moderately satisfied and concerned with the existing corporate social responsibilities of their enterprises in relation to the philanthropic responsibilities adopted and practiced by their organizations.

Out of the eight items comprising the philanthropic responsibilities, the respondents' feedback regarding their enterprises' concern for performing in a manner consistent with the philanthropic and charitable expectations of the Yemeni society is the highest (Mean = 3.95, S.D. = .933). The respondents' feedback has also indicated a slightly high mean value on the enterprises' concern on assisting voluntarily those projects which enhance a community's 'quality of life' (Mean = 3.84, S.D. = 1.017) and followed by providing assistance to private and public educational institutions (Mean = 3.83, S.D. = 1.014). There is an average indication of the respondents' feedback about the enterprises' concern of monitoring new opportunities which can enhance the organization's ability to help solve social problems in the Yemeni society (Mean = 3.74, S.D. = .960) and followed by the concern of the enterprises' managers and employees in participating in voluntary and charitable activities within their local communities in Yemen (Mean = 3.73, S.D. = 1.040) as well as the enterprises' concern of viewing philanthropic behavior as a useful measure of organizational performance (Mean = 3.70, S.D. = 1.056).

Even so, the feedback of the respondents concerning maintaining a policy of increasing charitable and voluntary efforts over time by their enterprises indicates slightly low value (Mean = 3.66, S.D. = .996). Besides, the lowest feedback of the respondents is about the concern of their enterprises in defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its philanthropic and charitable responsibilities (Mean = 3.48, S.D. = 1.110).

Generally, the respondents seem to have moderate concern (Mean = 3.75, S.D. = .771) with their enterprises' philanthropic responsibilities.

4.6 Correlation Matrices

The correlation statistical tests were performed in this study to examine the relationship between dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance, and the four components of the independent variable (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities). The bivariate correlations were used and divided into three main statistical tests that measure the relationships between CSR and nonfinancial organizational performance in: (i) state-owned enterprises (i.e., public for-profit enterprises); (ii) private enterprises; and (iii) both of SOEs and private enterprises in Yemen as a whole entity. These statistical tests are shown in Table 4.12., Table 4.13., and Table 4.14. respectively.

Table 4.12. shows the bivariate correlation used to determine the relationship between CSR and nonfinancial organizational performance in the 31-public for-profit enterprises operating in Sana'a known as the state-owned enterprises.

Table 4.12.: Inter-Correlations of Variables in SOEs (N = 31)

	Eco_CSR	Leg_CSR	Eth_CSR	Phi_CSR
Nonfinancial Organizational Performance (NFOP)	.279	.115	.265	.273
Economic Responsibilities (Eco_CSR)	-	.392*	.440*	.472**
Legal Responsibilities (Leg_CSR)	-	-	.541**	.119
Ethical Responsibilities (Eth_CSR)	-	-	-	.622**
Philanthropic Responsibilities (Phi_CSR)	-	-	-	-

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.13. shows the bivariate correlation used to determine the relationship between CSR and nonfinancial organizational performance in the 72-private enterprises operating in the Capital City of Sana'a in different economic sectors.

Table 4.13.: Inter-Correlations of Variables in Private Enterprises (N = 72)

	Eco_CSR	Leg_CSR	Eth_CSR	Phi_CSR
Nonfinancial Organizational Performance (NFOP)	.414**	.352**	.368**	.463**
Economic Responsibilities (Eco_CSR)	-	.363**	.272*	.294*
Legal Responsibilities (Leg_CSR)	-	-	.596**	.479**
Ethical Responsibilities (Eth_CSR)	-	-	-	.500**
Philanthropic Responsibilities (Phi_CSR)	-	-	-	-

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.14. shows the bivariate correlation used to determine the relationship between the overall CSR and the overall nonfinancial organizational performance in the 103 for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity operating in different economic sectors and located in the Capital City of Sana'a, Yemen.

Table 4.14.: Inter-Correlations of Variables in Both SOEs & Private Enterprises (N = 103)

	Eco_CSR	Leg_CSR	Eth_CSR	Phi_CSR
Nonfinancial Organizational Performance (NFOP)	.360**	.272**	.327**	.375**
Economic Responsibilities (Eco_CSR)	-	.351**	.311**	.320**
Legal Responsibilities (Leg_CSR)	-	-	.584**	.394**
Ethical Responsibilities (Eth_CSR)	-	-	-	.523**
Philanthropic Responsibilities (Phi_CSR)	-	-	-	-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation matrices shown in Table 4.12., Table 4.13., and Table 4.14. describe the correlations between nonfinancial organizational performance as the dependent variable and the CSR's four components, known as the independent variables, which are economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities in different for-profit enterprises comprising the sample of this study. Sekaran (2003) argues that if the correlation is closer to the value of 1.0, so the relationship between variables is considered very significant positively. He adds that if the correlation is closer to the value of -1.0, then the relationship is negatively very significant. There are several Pearson's Correlation scales in the academia which translate the relationship between different variables of different studies. This study adopts the scale of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r) suggested by Cohen (1988) shown in Table 4.15. to identify the nature of the relationships between dependent and independent variables and their levels of significance.

Table 4.15.: Pearson's Correlation Scale according to Cohen (1988)

Value of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r)	Indication
Value of $\pm .50$ and over	Strong correlation
Between $\pm .30$ to $\pm .49$	Moderate correlation
Below $\pm .30$	Weak correlation
Value of $.00$	Negligible correlation

Consequently, the data that were collected, analyzed, and correlated regarding the dependent and independent variables of this study were eventually used to compare the study's developed hypotheses and the following results were found:

Hypothesis 2_a: There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in SOEs. According to Table 4.12., the result indicates that there is an insignificant relationship between the economic responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .279$, $p\text{-value} \geq .05$). Consequently, *hypothesis 2_a* is not accepted.

Hypothesis 2_b: There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in private enterprises. According to Table 4.13., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the economic responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .414$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$). Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .414 and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive moderate correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 2_b* is accepted.

Hypothesis 3_a: There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in SOEs. According to Table 4.12., the result indicates that there is an insignificant relationship between the legal

responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .115$, $p\text{-value} \geq .05$). Consequently, *hypothesis 3_a* is not accepted.

Hypothesis 3_b: There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in private enterprises. According to Table 4.13., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the legal responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .352$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$). Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .352 and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive moderate correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 3_b* is accepted.

Hypothesis 4_a: There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in SOEs. According to Table 4.12., the result indicates that there is an insignificant relationship between the ethical responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .265$, $p\text{-value} \geq .05$). Consequently, *hypothesis 4_a* is not accepted.

Hypothesis 4_b: There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in private enterprises. According

to Table 4.13., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the ethical responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .368$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$). Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is $.368$ and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive moderate correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 4_b* is accepted.

Hypothesis 5_a: There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in SOEs. According to Table 4.12., the result indicates that there is an insignificant relationship between the philanthropic responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .273$, $p\text{-value} \geq .05$). Consequently, *hypothesis 5_a* is not accepted.

Hypothesis 5_b: There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in private enterprises. According to Table 4.13., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the philanthropic responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .463$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$). Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is $.463$ and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive moderate correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 5_b* is accepted.

Hypothesis 6_a: There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity. According to Table 4.14., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the economic responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .360$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$) in both for-profit public and private enterprises. Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .360 and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive moderate correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 6_a* is accepted.

Hypothesis 6_b: There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity. According to Table 4.14., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the legal responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .272$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$) in both for-profit public and private enterprises. Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .272 and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive weak correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 6_b* is accepted.

Hypothesis 6_c: There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity. According to Table 4.14., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the ethical responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .327$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$) in both for-profit public and private enterprises. Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .327 and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive moderate correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 6_c* is accepted.

Hypothesis 6_d: There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The relationship between the corporate social responsibility (CSR) is examined against the nonfinancial organizational performance (NFOP) in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity. According to Table 4.14., the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between the philanthropic responsibilities and the nonfinancial organizational performance ($r = .375$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$) in both for-profit public and private enterprises. Because the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .375 and according to Table 4.15., the relationship can be expressed to be a positive moderate correlation. Consequently, *hypothesis 6_d* is accepted.

In brief, the correlation tests were performed to examine the study's hypotheses and a major part of these hypotheses was accepted whereas the other minor part was rejected. Based on the obtained results, all the four components comprising the CSR in for-profit public enterprises (i.e., SOEs) have insignificant influence on the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises. Conversely, all the four components comprising the CSR in private enterprises have significant positive influence on the

nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises. Similarly, all the four components comprising the CSR in both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity have significant positive influence on the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises.

4.7 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was performed by treating separately the dimensions of the independent and dependent variables of this study. Moreover, this analysis was conducted to know more about the most influential dimensions of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The multiple regression analysis shown in Table 4.16. suggests that the predictors (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) are significantly and positively related to the criterion known as the nonfinancial organizational performance or the dependent variable.

Table 4.16.: Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)		
(Constant)	13.623	4.768		2.857	.005
Eco_CSR	.296	.120	.242	2.470	.015
Leg_CSR	.033	.120	.031	.277	.782
Eth_CSR	.136	.141	.116	.965	.337
Phi_CSR	.156	.075	.225	2.095	.039
F-value	6.815				
R ²	.218				
Adjusted R ²	.186				
Durbin-Watson	2.151				

* p-value < 0.05, ** p-value < 0.01

The results obtained from the regression analysis indicated that the predictor known as the economic responsibilities is the most influential independent variable on the dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance, with a value of .242 for Beta (β) and with a p-value $\leq .05$ at a 95% confidence level. Moreover and through examining the ' β ' values obtained through the regression analysis, the unstandardized coefficients indicated that the enterprises' economic responsibilities explained 29.6% of the variance in the dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance. This means that economic responsibilities of different public and private enterprises as a whole entity have more effect on the nonfinancial organizational performance of these organizations. This is also in parallel with the previous result obtained in this study which supports the fact that the economic responsibilities of enterprises are significantly related to the nonfinancial organizational performance of the same enterprises.

The obtained results from the regression model also indicated that the predictor known as the philanthropic responsibilities adopted by different for-profit public and private enterprises has significant influence on the nonfinancial organizational performance of the same enterprises. The model shows an effective statistical significance for the philanthropic responsibilities ($\beta = .225$, p-value $\leq .05$) at a 95% confidence level. Moreover and through examining the ' β ' values obtained through the regression analysis, the unstandardized coefficients indicated that the enterprises' philanthropic responsibilities explained 15.6% of the variance in the dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Briefly and based on the obtained results from the regression analysis, only two independent variables (i.e., economic and philanthropic responsibilities) are significant

predictors for the criterion, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance. Conversely, other independent variables of CSR, namely, the legal and ethical responsibilities, are not predictors of the nonfinancial organizational performance.

Furthermore, Table 4.16. of the multiple regression shows that the value of R^2 —which identifies the portion of the variance explained by the independent variables of the study—is nearly .218. This means that 21.8% of the four independent variables have impacts on the dependent variable. It also explains that nearly 21.8 percent of the variance in the nonfinancial organizational performance has been significantly expounded by the four components of the corporate social responsibility. Besides, this means that there are certainly other components and factors that contribute to the nonfinancial organizational performance beside these four components of the CSR. In addition, Muijs (2004) suggests the rule of thumb for explaining how well the regression model fits the analyzed data. He contends that if: (i) the value of the adjusted R-square < 0.1 , then there is a poor fit; (ii) value of adjusted R-square is between $0.11 - 0.3$, then there is a modest fit; (iii) value of adjusted R-square is between $0.31 - 0.5$, then there is a moderate fit; and (iv) value of adjusted R-square is > 0.5 , then there is a strong fit. Accordingly, the value of the adjusted R^2 in this study is .186 and this suggests that the four predictors of this study are fitting modestly at predicting the criterion, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance.

The Durbin-Watson statistical test is also used in this study to detect the level of autocorrelation between errors. The Durbin-Watson statistic ranges in value from 0 to 4. As the rule of thumb, a value near 2 for the Durbin-Watson statistic indicates non-autocorrelation, a value towards 0 indicates positive autocorrelation, and a value towards 4 indicates negative autocorrelation (Ibodullayevna, 2011). Hence, Table 4.16.

suggests that the obtained value from the Durbin-Watson analysis is 2.151 which is a value close to the integer value of 2. This means that the independent variables (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) and dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance, are significant and there is a non-value for the autocorrelation.

4.8 *t*-Test Analyses

The *t*-test analysis was conducted to know more about the difference in the level of adopting the concept of CSR generally in both for-profit public and private enterprises as a periodic institutional activity. Moreover, the *t*-test is used in this study to examine the postulated null hypothesis concerning the difference in the level of adopting CSR in both types of for-profit enterprises in Yemen.

4.8.1 Welch's *t*-Test Analysis

The Welch's *t*-Test is used when there are two samples that have unequal variances. From the frequency analysis, the values of variances are 1.083 and 1.314 for private and public enterprises respectively. Obviously, the two samples of this study possess unequal variances. Accordingly, Welch's *t*-test was used through defining the statistic t_{calc} by the following formula:

$$t_{calc} = \frac{\bar{\mu}_1 - \bar{\mu}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{N_2}}}$$

where:

t_{calc} = The *t*-test value (calculated);

$\bar{\mu}_1$ = sample mean of private enterprises = 4.04;

$\bar{\mu}_2$ = sample mean of for-profit public enterprises = 3.77;

s_1 = sample variance of private enterprises = 1.041;

s_2 = sample variance of for-profit public enterprises = 1.146;

N_1 = sample size of private enterprises = 72;

N_2 = sample size of for-profit public enterprises = 31.

Hence, the t -test value was found to be 1.1268. Also, the df (i.e., degree of freedom) was obtained from the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} df &= N_1 + N_2 - 2 \\ &= 72 + 31 - 2 = 101 \end{aligned}$$

The tabulated t -test value or t_{crit} (i.e., t -critical) was found to be 1.9837 obtained from the t -distribution table. Accordingly, it can be concluded that $t_{crit} > t_{calc}$ (i.e., $1.9837 > 1.1268$) and this renders the t_{calc} value to be in the acceptance region, Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1.: t -Test analysis for comparing values of t_{calc} and t_{crit}

Consequently, the data that were collected and analyzed regarding the level of periodically adopting CSR activities between the two groups of the for-profit enterprises in this study (i.e., public and private) were eventually used to compare the study's developed hypotheses and the following results were found:

Hypothesis I_0 (null): A significant difference does not exist between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general. ($H1_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$)

Hypothesis I_a (alternative): A significant difference exists between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general. ($H1_a: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)

The difference between the for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general was examined. Consequently, the result indicates that the null hypothesis should be accepted ($|t_{\text{calc}}| < t_{\text{crit}}$, $p\text{-value} = .249 \geq .05$). Consequently, *hypothesis I_0 (null)* is accepted and *hypothesis I_a (alternative)* is rejected.

4.8.2 Independent-Samples *t*-Test Analysis

The independent-samples *t*-Test was performed also to automatically compare the difference between the two main groups of this study (i.e., level of adopting CSR in both SOEs and private enterprises) using the software SPSS and to find out if this difference is significant. The result of the independent-samples *t*-Test analysis is shown in Table 4.17.

Table 4.17.: The Independent-Samples *t*-Test Analysis

Description		Value
Private Enterprises	N	72
	Mean	4.04
	S.D.	1.041
Public Enterprises (SOEs)	N	31
	Mean	3.77
	S.D.	1.146
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	F	1.263
	Sig.	.264
<i>t</i> -Test for Equality of Means	t	1.16
	df	101
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.249

The result obtained from the independent-samples *t*-Test analysis indicated that the difference is considered statistically insignificant [$t(101) = 1.16$, $p\text{-value} = .249 \geq .05$]

between the two groups, namely, for-profit public enterprises (Mean = 3.77, S.D. = 1.146) and private enterprises (Mean = 4.04, S.D. = 1.041).

Furthermore, the effect size known as Eta-squared or η^2 which is used to measure the size of differences between groups is calculated using this formula:

$$\eta^2 = \frac{t^2}{t^2 + (N_1 + N_2 - 2)}$$

where:

η^2 = effect size (Eta-squared);

t = t-statistic = 1.16;

N_1 = sample size of private enterprises = 72;

N_2 = sample size of for-profit public enterprises = 31.

According to Cohen (1988), the rule of thumb concerning the value of Eta-squared is that if: (i) $\eta^2 = .01$, then the effect is weak; (ii) $\eta^2 = .06$, then the effect is moderate; and (iii) $\eta^2 = .14$, then the effect is strong. Hence, the final calculated value of the effect size (i.e., η^2 or Eta-squared) is .0131 which reflects a weak effect size. Accordingly, the variable known as the type of the enterprise (i.e., either a for-profit public or a private enterprise) only explains 1.31% of the variance in the level of adopting generally the concept of CSR among for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen.

4.9 Summary

This chapter primarily discussed the results and findings obtained through various statistical analyses performed on the collected data of the disseminated questionnaires among for-profit public and private enterprises in the Capital City of Sana'a, Yemen. Then, collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical analyses including frequencies, reliability tests, factor analyses, Pearson's correlations analyses, regression analysis, and t-Test analyses.

The correlation analysis indicated that the four components comprising the CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) are significantly and positively correlated with the nonfinancial organizational performance in all the sample's enterprises as a whole entity, namely, public and private enterprises. Conversely, the other correlation analysis indicated that the four components of the CSR have insignificant influence on the dependent variable when this analysis was separately conducted only on the for-profit public enterprises of the sample. However, the correlation analysis indicated that the four components of the CSR have significant positive influence on the dependent variable when this analysis was separately conducted on only the private enterprises of the sample.

Furthermore and through the multiple regression analysis, the enterprises' economic and philanthropic responsibilities as components of CSR were the main predictors of the dependent variable (i.e., the nonfinancial organizational performance) whereas the other two components of CSR, namely, legal and ethical responsibilities, were not predictors. In addition, Durbin-Watson statistical analysis showed that the four independent variables and the dependent variable are significant with a negligible autocorrelation value. Additionally, the *t*-Test analyses indicated that the difference between the SOEs and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting CSR in general as a periodic institutional activity is insignificant. Moreover, the size of differences between these two groups is weak with a small value for Eta-squared.

CHAPTER V

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter, namely, *Chapter V*, as the final chapter of this study, discusses and concludes all the findings and results collected and analyzed in the previous chapter (i.e., Chapter IV). As discussed in preceding chapters, the primary purpose of the current study is to determine whether there is an influence of CSR, the independent variable, consisted of four components (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) on the dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance in for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen. Furthermore, this chapter sheds light on the limitations of the study and the recommendations contributed by the researcher and his suggestions concerning the expected prospective researches in the future.

5.2 Summarizing of the Findings

This study was conducted to measure the influence of corporate social responsibility adopted by SOEs and private enterprises on the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises in Yemen. The study instrument (i.e., the questionnaire) was disseminated among the 255 representatives of the for-profit public and private enterprises operating in different economic sectors in Yemen as the targeted respondents. This questionnaire was adopted from two academic researches in academia

then adapted and abridged for the purpose of collecting the following information: (i) demographic statistical data concerning respondents who represent their for-profit enterprises. These demographic data include gender, age of respondents, level of education, current position, type of enterprise, nature of the enterprise's activity, the enterprise's date of foundation, and the total number of the enterprise's employees in the year 2013; (ii) the components related to the four categories comprising CSR or the independent variable; and (iii) the components related to the nonfinancial organizational performance or the dependent variable.

The four components of the corporate social responsibility were measured with a questionnaire that is used for assessing corporate social responsibility orientation (CSRO) based on Carroll's 1979 four-part CSR model (Carroll, 1979). This 60-item instrument of CSR was adapted and abridged by the researcher of this study into 32 items. However, the instrument used to measure the nonfinancial organizational performance was proposed by Delaney and Huselid (1996) and extended to 8 items instead of the original 7 items.

Accordingly, the collected entire data through the questionnaires were statistically analyzed—using the software dubbed SPSS Version 13.0—to determine the answer of the main enquiry that this study discusses. This enquiry is about “Does corporate social responsibility with its four distinct components has a significant relationship with the nonfinancial organizational performance of for-profit public and private enterprises operating in various economic sectors in Yemen?” Several hypotheses were postulated to find the answers for the main four research questions of this study. Moreover, the impacts of the four components comprising CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance (i.e., the dependent variable) were analyzed to find out the types and

significances of these relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The findings showed that the four components of CSR (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic) have different influences on the dependent variable depending on the type of the enterprise. In this regard, obtained results showed that the CSR's four components have no significant relationship with nonfinancial organizational performance in for-profit public enterprises, namely, state-owned enterprises. Conversely, the obtained results revealed that there is a significant relationship between CSR with its four components and the nonfinancial organizational performance in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity and also in only private enterprises operating in various economic sectors in Yemen when analyzed separately. Furthermore, results obtained showed that the most dominant independent variables on the dependent variable were the economic responsibilities of enterprises and followed by the philanthropic responsibilities in the next rank. However, other components of CSR (i.e., legal and ethical responsibilities) were not predictors of the dependent variable in for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen. Moreover, the findings showed that there is no significant difference in the level of adopting CSR generally between for-profit public and private enterprises. Table 5.1. illustrates all the important findings concerning the postulated hypotheses of this study.

Table 5.1.: Results of the Study's Tested Hypotheses

Hypothesis		Outcome
<i>Hypothesis I_0</i> (<i>null</i>):	A significant difference does not exist between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general. ($H1_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$)	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>Hypothesis I_a</i> (<i>alternative</i>):	A significant difference exists between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general. ($H1_a: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)	<i>Rejected</i>

Table 5.1.: Results of the Study's Tested Hypotheses (continued)

Hypothesis		Outcome
<i>Hypothesis 2_a:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Rejected</i>
<i>Hypothesis 2_b:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>Hypothesis 3_a:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Rejected</i>
<i>Hypothesis 3_b:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>Hypothesis 4_a:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Rejected</i>
<i>Hypothesis 4_b:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>Hypothesis 5_a:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by for-profit public organizations (i.e., SOEs) and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Rejected</i>
<i>Hypothesis 5_b:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by private organizations and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>Hypothesis 6_a:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between economic responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>Hypothesis 6_b:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>Hypothesis 6_c:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>

Table 5.1.: Results of the Study's Tested Hypotheses (continued)

Hypothesis		Outcome
<i>Hypothesis 6_d:</i>	There is a significant positive relationship between philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance	<i>Accepted</i>

5.3 Discussion of the Findings

The fundamental purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between the corporate social responsibility and the nonfinancial organizational performance in the for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity operating in various economic sectors in Yemen. The study has four research questions. The first, second, and third research questions inquire about whether there is a relationship between CSR's components—adopted by the SOEs, the private enterprises, and the both entities as a whole—with the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises. The fourth research question inquires about which are the components of CSR that have more influence on the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises. Briefly, the findings of the data analyses—which are related to the hypotheses and research questions—revealed that the CSR's four components have no significant relationship with nonfinancial organizational performance (i.e., dependent variable) in only for-profit public enterprises. Moreover, findings demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between CSR with the dependent variable in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity and separately in only private enterprises operating in various economic sectors in Yemen. Furthermore, findings showed that the most dominant independent variable on the dependent variable is the economic responsibilities of both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity followed by philanthropic responsibilities of these enterprises. On the other hand, the difference

concerning adopting generally CSR as a periodic activity in both for-profit public and private enterprises was statistically insignificant.

It is also important to refer to the point that the discussions, implications, and conclusions in the coming sections will be based on the aggregated obtained results for the entire enterprises comprising the sample of the study, namely, the for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity. This means that the discussions of the separate samples (i.e., SOEs and private enterprises) will be neglected in order to have a whole impression about CSR and its adoption generally in all for-profit enterprises included in the sample of this study, namely, the 103 elements. This is also done for avoiding any further discussions and implications which would be out of the scope of this study from the theoretical and academic perspectives.

5.3.1 Economic Responsibilities of Enterprises

According to Table 5.1., there is a positive significant relationship between the economic responsibilities adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises operating in diverse economic sectors in Yemen. The value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .360 ($p\text{-value} \leq .05$) which renders the relationship to be a positive moderate correlation according to Cohen (1988). Besides, the economic responsibilities have the most influence among other types of CSR's responsibilities on the nonfinancial organizational performance ($\beta = .242$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$) at a 95% confidence level. This means also that the enterprises' economic responsibilities explained approximately 29.6% of the variance in the nonfinancial organizational performance (i.e., the dependent variable).

This justifies the findings that if the economic responsibilities of CSR (i.e., producing desired goods and services by society as well as maximizing profits and wealth of stakeholders, Carroll, 1979) adopted by different for-profit enterprises are high, then the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises will be positively improved. This finding is in accordance with the obtained results of the research conducted by Akanbi *et al.* (2012) who argue that there is a significant difference between economic responsibilities of CSR and the subjective organizational performance using the *t*-Test analysis. The same scholars claim also that the economic responsibility of CSR is a predictor of the organizational performance which is also in accordance with the finding of the researcher in this study.

In this way, caring more about being more profitable whenever it is possible is considered a vital policy for these for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen. This policy can improve the satisfaction level of the enterprises' shareholders and other core stakeholders. The Yemeni market is an oligopolistic one which imposes several aggressive situations on these enterprises and pushes them to have competitive position in this market to fulfill their economic responsibilities. Moreover, enterprises that improve their outputs—such as adopting new commercial innovations and increasing customers' satisfaction—and their inputs (i.e., controlling firmly expenditures and controlling employees) are among those enterprises that survive more in the Yemeni market. These enterprises define a successful for-profit enterprise as the one which has adequate steady amount of profit with adequate amount of other essential intangible issues related to the society. Monitoring new opportunities that lead to enhancing the financial health of the enterprises is also an economic responsibility which can be attained by using accounting and other financial systems and by hiring more financial experts. Available organizational resources could also enhance the financial and

economic situations of the enterprises. For this reason, the economic responsibilities of these enterprises entail defining and assigning well such resources that include technological, financial, and other essential resources. Several measures are used for evaluating the organizational performance of the enterprises and being consistently profitable could be considered as one of them. This is absolutely does not mean that making as much as profit is the main and only concern of these for-profit enterprises but there are other nonfinancial and perceptual measures that should be also notably considered.

5.3.2 Legal Responsibilities of Enterprises

According to Table 5.1., there is a positive significant relationship between the legal responsibilities adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises operating in diverse economic sectors in Yemen. The value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .272 (p -value $\leq .05$) which renders the relationship to be a positive weak correlation according to Cohen (1988).

Accordingly, the findings from this study justify the fact that if the legal responsibilities of CSR adopted by different for-profit enterprises in Yemen are high, then the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises will be positively improved. The legal responsibilities are concerned with the advantageous and disadvantageous commitments imposed on different enterprises by the society's law and regulations that these organizations operate in (Carroll *et al.*, 2010). This finding concerning the legal responsibilities in this study opposes the obtained results of the research conducted by Akanbi *et al.* (2012) who claim that there is no main and interaction effect of legal corporate social responsibility on the organizational

performance. On the other hand, they mention that the legal corporate social responsibility is a predictor of the organizational performance. The research of those scholars was conducted in an African Bank and the elements of the sample were employees who work in this bank. However, the current study tackles—as one of its main parts—the influence of legal responsibilities of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance in for-profit public and private enterprises in the Yemeni society. Hence, the sample's element is the enterprise or the organization and this could make an essential difference in the obtained results for the correlation and regression analyses compared with the obtained results by Akanbi *et al.* (2012). The same scholars argue also that the legal responsibility of CSR is a predictor of the organizational performance of the enterprise that they conducted their study in (i.e., the African bank) which is not in parallel with the findings of the current study.

For rightfully fulfilling the legal responsibilities of enterprises, these enterprises must perform their duties and activities in line with local Yemeni laws and regulations. They should also seriously avoid any kind of legal infringements or violations that could jeopardize their image in the society. Legal responsibilities are essential for the institutional work that enterprises make efforts to preserve and follow which impacts their reputation and goodwill in the society. Moreover, the weak legal performance that the enterprises might have could negatively influence their relationship with government and their relationship with the customers themselves. The process of bargaining social norms and mores existed in the Yemeni society itself for acquiring organizational goals should be carefully considered and dealt by these for-profit public and private enterprises since this process has its undesirable effects and consequences. The definition of a successful enterprise as the one that fulfills its legal obligations is one of the accepted definitions by the Yemeni for-profit enterprises. Besides, for-profit

public and private enterprises should be aware that legal responsibilities are important and accordingly they need experts to deal with. Legal situations of the enterprises should be also maintained and monitored by managers occasionally since condoning such issues could have deleterious effects on the enterprise itself and on its position in the market. Measuring the organizational performance of the enterprise is attained by complying with the Yemeni laws and regulations which ensure being in the safe side and having less legal troubles and lawsuits. The fact that corporate integrity and ethical behaviors transcend over the process of compliance with laws should be a major concern for these enterprises that want to maintain high legal responsibilities. It is good to adhere to all laws and regulations but adhering beside them to other ethics and morals is more acceptable and more appreciated by government and by the individuals comprising the Yemeni society.

5.3.3 Ethical Responsibilities of Enterprises

According to Table 5.1., there is a positive significant relationship between the ethical responsibilities adopted by both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises operating in various Yemeni economic sectors. The value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .327 ($p\text{-value} \leq .05$) which renders the relationship to be a positive moderate correlation according to Cohen (1988).

Accordingly, the findings from this study justify the fact that if the ethical responsibilities of CSR adopted by different for-profit enterprises in Yemen are high, then the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises will be positively enhanced. Carroll (1991) states: “The ethical responsibilities of a business embody those standards, norms, or expectations that reflect a concern for what consumers,

employees, shareholders, and the community regard as fair, just, or in keeping with the respect of protection of stakeholders' moral rights" (p. 41). The finding concerning the ethical responsibilities in this study is in parallel with the obtained results of the research conducted by Akanbi and Ofoegbu (2012) who contend that there is a positive association between ethical corporate social responsibility and the organizational performance. The same scholars found also that the ethical responsibility of CSR is a predictor of the organizational performance of the enterprise that they conducted their study in which opposes the finding of the current study.

In this regard, the ethical responsibilities of the enterprises are extremely important since these responsibilities are related to both the individual's behavior and the organizational behavior of these enterprises. Performing ethically as enterprises according to the social norms and other societal mores should be in line with what the Yemeni society expects and anticipates. The for-profit public and private enterprises operate to gain and increase profit in a tolerated and supportive Yemeni society with adhering to laws at the same time is essential for these enterprises. Nevertheless, adopting ethical responsibilities when dealing with this society is something more important and has more transcendent meanings for these enterprises. When for example advertising of products and services in the Yemeni society, these enterprises should exactly offer in reality what the consumers have viewed and experienced in advertisements themselves. Any deviations from these enterprises about their products and services could have unconstructive effects since the level of consumers' perceptions would be less than their level of expectations which could lead to dissatisfaction. Moreover, the advertisements themselves should respect all societal norms and mores subsisting in the Yemeni society. Caring more about minorities in the Yemeni society is a pivotal issue that for-profit enterprises are obliged to highly consider. Those

minorities could include women, handicapped individuals, and non-Yemeni foreigners. Those minorities have the right to work, purchase, practice daily typical activities, and live like other individuals who normally reside in the Yemeni society. Enterprises must avoid discrimination and underestimation against those minorities and should pay a great attention for the possible ways to satisfy their needs through offered services and products and through responsibly applying other ethical responsibilities towards them.

For-profit enterprises could be defined as successful when they fulfill their ethical and moral responsibilities in their respective societies. An enterprise without ethical responsibilities is like a face without emotional expressions which beautify it and render it more acceptable in the eyes of others. On the other hand, being reputable for having ethical responsibilities in the society and working on improving the enterprise's image could form an actual competitive advantage for any enterprise in any society through having a high percentage of sales and a wide market share. The process of bargaining social norms and ethics for reaching the organizational objectives is existent among the for-profit enterprises but discouraging it would be a better way for having more satisfied customers in the Yemeni society. Although this kind of bargaining is somewhat hidden and performed inside the enterprise itself, being ethically a responsible enterprise could ensure considerably minimizing it. For-profit enterprises are expected to be more mature and experienced when dealing with the Yemeni society and this includes not bargaining societal norms and ethics for making advantages related to the organizational goals. As a managerial and ethical act, whistle blowing is expected to be encouraged in all management levels of the for-profit enterprises. This ethical act ensures more levels of transparency and institutional work inside the enterprises themselves. Moreover, protecting whistle blowers is expected to be applied in these enterprises in case they have any kind of litigations or other types of detriments. Caring also about fulfilling all

tax obligations to the Yemeni government is a major concern of all for-profit enterprises for its importance and relationship with the healthy financial progress of these enterprises. Any failure concerning this issue could jeopardize these enterprises and would create other intricate managerial and legal consequences.

5.3.4 Philanthropic Responsibilities of Enterprises

According to Table 5.1., there is a positive significant relationship between the philanthropic responsibilities adopted by both for-profit public and private enterprises as a whole entity and the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises operating in numerous Yemeni economic sectors. The value of the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is .375 ($p\text{-value} \leq .05$) which renders the relationship to be a positive moderate correlation according to Cohen (1988). Besides, the philanthropic responsibilities have an influence among other types of CSR's responsibilities on the nonfinancial organizational performance ($\beta = .225$, $p\text{-value} \leq .05$) at a 95% confidence level. This means also that the enterprises' philanthropic responsibilities explained approximately 15.6% of the variance in the nonfinancial organizational performance (i.e., the dependent variable).

Accordingly, the findings from this study justify the fact that if the philanthropic responsibilities of CSR adopted by different for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen are high, then the nonfinancial organizational performance of these enterprises will be positively developed. Philanthropic or discretionary responsibilities of enterprises are about their activities which are in line with the society's anticipations from them to be good corporate citizens (Carroll, 1991). The finding concerning the philanthropic responsibilities in this study is in line with the obtained results of the

research conducted by Akanbi and Ofoegbu (2012) who contend that philanthropic corporate social responsibility is a predictor of the organizational performance.

Taking into consideration acting in line with the society's expectations concerning philanthropic and charitable activities is present moderately in for-profit enterprises and should be present in the future. The Yemeni society expects the for-profit enterprises to have more voluntary activities that contribute in supporting and helping this society without waiting for any financial or economic returns. The process of acting philanthropically and voluntarily by a Yemeni for-profit enterprise is similar to the acts of a typical human and this embodies the real meanings for the enterprise of being a good corporate citizen. Encouraging managers and typical employees to work in for-profit public and private enterprises to do voluntary and charitable activities is more than welcomed by the Yemeni society. These enterprises are required to have all their employees in different managerial levels accustomed to usual philanthropic and voluntary practices which would increase their internal responsibilities and increase at the same time the overall philanthropic responsibilities of these enterprises.

One of the philanthropic responsibilities of enterprises is about fostering academic and educational entities that include public and private universities, community colleges, schools, and other institutes in Yemen. The students belong to these entities are numbered in thousands or more and having a positive image in the mentalities of those students about the enterprises' philanthropic responsibilities could be affirmative for these for-profit enterprises and for their prospective objectives in the Yemeni market. In this way, successful enterprises could be defined as the ones which fulfill their philanthropic responsibilities. These responsibilities are diverse and include charitable, voluntary, and also discretionary ones which enterprises should be aware of and practice

them periodically. Also, monitoring any opportunities in the Yemeni society that could improve the for-profit enterprises' capabilities concerning helping in solving social problems is a positive issue that is expected to be considered among their regular philanthropic responsibilities and voluntary activities. The projects which could improve the quality of life—such as projects concerning health, education, and means of support—are also expected to be adopted voluntarily by for-profit enterprises in Yemen. These enterprises should be aware that they should offer philanthropic responsibilities in return for the considerable financial benefits that they acquire from the society. Hence, projects philanthropically directed to support financially healthy centers, orphanages, or hospitals are highly rewarded and appreciated by the individuals of the Yemeni society and failing in supporting these projects could have disadvantageous results. Through philanthropic and voluntary behaviors, an enterprise could measure its organizational performance. Managers should be aware that the expected tangible outcomes through adopting and supporting such philanthropic responsibilities are majorly caused by supporting intangible activities related to philanthropic responsibilities of the enterprises. Besides, preserving a regular policy for augmenting charitable and voluntary activities over time is advantageous for these for-profit enterprises. Offering charitable activities in specific seasons or occasions could be good but administratively organizing such activities and adding them to the annual financial budgets of these enterprises is the exceptional thing. Managers should be aware that philanthropic responsibilities could be institutionally planned and applied according to a palpable policy which ensures their efficiency and effectiveness in the society that they are applied and adopted in.

5.3.5 The Adoption of CSR Generally in SOEs and Private Enterprises

According to Table 5.1. concerning the results of the study's tested hypotheses, there is no significant difference between the SOEs and the private enterprises operating in diverse economic sectors in Yemen in the level of adopting the concept of CSR generally as a periodic activity. The value of the difference was statistically insignificant [$t(101) = 1.16$, $p\text{-value} = .249 \geq .05$] between for-profit enterprises (Mean = 3.77, S.D. = 1.146) and private enterprises (Mean = 4.04, S.D. = 1.041). This reflects the fact that both for-profit public and private enterprises have no significant difference in the overall embracement of CSR activities in Yemen.

In this regard, the obtained results from this study show that roughly half of the respondents (i.e., 42 percent of them) who represent their for-profit public and private enterprises consider that adopting periodically at least one type of the activities concerned with the social responsibility in the Yemeni society as an important issue for them. This reflects the importance of the CSR's activities among these enterprises and the importance of adopting and implementing at least one social responsibility from time to time in the society. The concept of CSR becomes day after another a major concern for many for-profit enterprises in different Yemeni economic sectors. This is due to the augmented level of awareness that middle- and top-level management have about CSR and about its impact on financial and nonfinancial organizational performance. Corporate social responsibility—as a central strategic and marketing concept—contributes affirmatively in the success of any enterprise adopting it seriously and professionally. Those representatives of these for-profit public and private enterprises are aware that CSR is part of the success and prosperity of their enterprises through different means. They know that CSR could be efficiently exploited to maximize the gained profits through responsibly monitoring and fulfilling honestly their

economic and financial obligations. They are knowledgeable that CSR could be competently exploited to improve the enterprises' legal positions in the Yemeni society and to decrease the number of litigating lawsuits against their enterprises. This could be achieved through strictly following and applying their legal responsibilities and keeping transparent relationships with all various partners in the society. Moreover, those representatives of the for-profit public and private enterprises are aware that CSR could be exploited to ethically and fairly spreading societal positive norms and mores anticipated by all the enterprise's stakeholders in the Yemeni society. Also, they realize that CSR could be well exploited to enhance the enterprise's image in the Yemeni society through implementing charitable and philanthropic initiatives.

On the contrary, this study has demonstrated that there is no significant difference between SOEs (i.e., for-profit public enterprises) and private enterprises in the level of adopting the concept of CSR in general. It is important to mention that the body of the literature tackles the concept of CSR widely in private enterprises and stresses that CSR is essential for various organizations operating in private sector. Conversely, CSR adopted and recognized by the public organizations and especially the SOEs is slightly tackled by this literature and this shows that CSR still a vague managerial concept in the public sector. Only few scholars have tackled the CSR adoption in the public sector and the role that governments could play towards such concept (Amba-Rao, 1993; De Bernardis, Maiolini, & Braccini, 2010; Finskas, 2007; Hinz, 2009).

From this point and despite the anticipations of the current study's researcher on having a significant difference between for-profit public and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting periodically CSR concept in Yemen, the obtained results show that the difference is almost insignificant. This finding could be attributed to several managerial

and social reasons. One of these reasons is concerned with the convergent level of awareness in both types of for-profit enterprises (i.e., SOEs and private) about the importance of CSR concept and about adopting it. Many representatives of the private enterprises included in the sample of this study have worked in for-profit public enterprises and vice versa. Those top- and middle-level managers have the same affirmative impression about CSR and about its positive outcomes. Accordingly, they espouse the concept of CSR and work to exploit it at any place they work in. Another justification for this insignificant difference is about the fact that the intention in both types of for-profit enterprises in adopting CSR concept is related with the potential positive marketing and strategic outcomes that this concept has. Managers are aware that the Yemeni society is driven by social issues that are included in the ethical and philanthropic responsibilities of CSR. Sometimes, those managers exploit these social issues for the benefit of their enterprises in both for-profit entities and this could make no significant difference in the level of adopting CSR. At the end, the managers in any for-profit enterprise have similar marketing and strategic intentions and in a small society like the Yemeni one, strategic and marketing plans seem very alike.

5.4 Theoretical Implications

This study has showed that the relationship between the CSR's four components (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) and the nonfinancial organizational performance is moderated or weak according to the type of the social responsibility that the enterprise frequently adopts and practices. Moreover, the study has confirmed that the nonfinancial organizational performance of for-profit public and private enterprises operating in Yemeni economic sectors can be predicted by two main components of CSR, namely, the economic and philanthropic responsibilities of these enterprises. According to Lee (2008), many scholars have not expressed or validated the

relationship between CSR and organizational performance. This is due to the diverse definitions of the two concepts in the literature and also the difficulty in empirically measuring them. Many studies tackled this relationship but with majorly focusing on the financial aspects of the organizational performance, namely, the objective organizational performance (Akanbi & Ofoegbu, 2012; Aupperle, Carroll, & Hatfield, 1985; Becchetti, Di Giacomo, & Pinnacchio, 2005; Bird, Casavecchia, & Reggiani, 2006; Campbell, 2007; Carter, 2005; Griffin & Mahon, 1997; Harrison & Freeman, 1999; Margolis & Walsh, 2003; McGuire, Sundgren, & Schneeweis, 1988; Park, 2010; Paskert, 2008; Quazi & Richardson, 2012; Roman, Hayibor, & Agle, 1999; Vollono, 2010; Wissink, 2012). The majority of those researchers found out that there is a significant relationship between CSR and the organizational performance.

Among those scholars who examined the influence of CSR's four components on the nonfinancial organizational performance are Akanbi and Ofoegbu (2012) who claim that "the findings of the study revealed that the dimensions of corporate social responsibility have effect on organizational performance" (p. 374). Furthermore, the same researchers state: "the four dimensions of corporate social responsibility used in this study were predictors of organizational performance" (p. 382). These findings are consistent with the findings of this study concerning the significant relationship between the dependent variable and the four components of the independent variable. Also, the findings are partially consistent with the findings of this study since only the economic and philanthropic components of CSR are predictors for the nonfinancial organizational performance.

On the other hand, this study has demonstrated that there is a small difference in the mean values and variances resulted from the analysis of the level of adopting the

concept of CSR in general as a periodic activity between SOEs (i.e., for-profit public enterprises) and private enterprises in Yemen. However, this difference is insignificant and this shows that this level of adopting CSR on both types of for-profit enterprises is comparable and has at the same time similar traits.

5.5 Managerial Implications

The concept of CSR has several components and these components need to be periodically monitored and devoted to the benefit of society and enterprises. Top-, middle-, and even lower-level employees should know about CSR and about its expected affirmative impact on the organizational performance and on the overall success of their enterprises. Paying more attention for economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities by employees and managers of diverse Yemeni enterprises can help in enhancing the financial situations of these enterprises and the Yemeni society at large. Hence, CSR becomes day after another a pivotal concern for many enterprises that want to endure in developed and developing societies.

5.5.1 Economic Responsibilities

The economic responsibilities of enterprises are essential for their endurance and continuity in societies. These enterprises are for-profit and have several shareholders and owners that should be considered highly. Therefore, these enterprises have economic responsibilities towards those shareholders including maximizing profit and accordingly capitalizing on their wealth (Carroll *et al.*, 2009).

In this respect, the found results of this study show that the majority of respondents who represent their for-profit enterprises have a high concern about the issue that their enterprises are committed to being as profitable as possible. This reflects the high concern of these enterprises on having more satisfied stakeholders and especially

shareholders or owners. It reflects also the enterprises' high concern about fulfilling at the same time the main objective of any for-profit enterprise, namely, profit maximization. Many respondents representing their for-profit enterprises believe that maintaining a strong competitive position in the Yemeni market is highly important. Enterprises are highly aware of the cutthroat competition that they encounter in the Yemeni market. This market is a market with an oligopolistic structure in which a few number of competitors exists with high-imposed barriers to enter the market by other strong sellers. Due to the nature of these enterprises and being operating in a country like Yemen, the most important issue for them is to have a robust competitive position in the market and to accordingly improve their market share and their overall sales.

Based on the results that the enterprises' representatives expressed through their responses, nearly more than half of them are very concerned with ensuring to maintain a high level of operating efficiency. Accordingly, maintaining a high level of operational efficiency largely entails maintaining a high level of the ratio between the inputs and the outputs of the enterprises. This means that these enterprises work hardly to gain high profits, customer satisfaction, and innovation (i.e., the outputs) through managing well their various types of expenditures, shareholders, and labor force, namely, the inputs. It is obvious that through gaining high outputs that include high levels of customer satisfaction and innovation by these enterprises, the nonfinancial organizational performance will absolutely be improved. Moreover, a major portion of the enterprises' respondents has a concern about defining a successful enterprise as the one which is consistently profitable. It seems that those enterprises' representatives do not extremely care about linking successful enterprises with having steadily and constantly profits. They are aware to a certain point that profits are not the only causes that make enterprises to be successful. The representatives of these enterprises are aware that there

are other elements that could make a successful enterprise and especially in a country like Yemen. These elements should not be economic or financial but they could belong to other unexpressed and intangible categories related to the society and the life of the individuals in this society.

Roughly, half of the for-profit enterprises' representatives are exceptionally concerned with monitoring new opportunities which can enhance their enterprises' financial health. Some of these opportunities subsist inside the enterprises and the others subsist outside the boundaries of the enterprises. For example, some of these opportunities include hiring experts with high financial experiences, having regular and well prepared financial statements and budgets, keeping adequate amounts of operating reserves for emergency cases, and working with robust and secure accounting systems. Accordingly, the respondents are aware of these financial needs which will ensure that their enterprises' financial health will be improved through any new opportunities in the Yemeni society. Similarly, the obtained results of this study revealed that nearly half of the enterprises are concerned about exerting an effort in efficiently allocating the different available types of resources. These enterprises competently work towards having any adequately possible and efficient organizational resources including human, technological, financial, and physical resources. They also consider other scarce and limited organizational resources which contribute in enhancing their market share and their direct sales. These resources are available from the society itself and contribute in enhancing the organizational performance of these enterprises.

Furthermore, a small portion of the enterprises believes that it is important to view consistent profitability as a useful measure of the organizational performance. This finding reflects the enterprises' attitude towards evaluating their organizational

performance not only through sheer and steady margins of profits and sales but also through measuring other indicators. These indicators could include other social, economic, legal, or even discretionary issues that these enterprises view as beneficial in evaluating their objective and subjective organizational performance. In addition, nearly half of the enterprises included in this study express their concern about pursuing only those opportunities which provide the best rate of return (i.e., the amount of income generated or lost by an investment). When enterprises are partially concerned with improving only their rates of return, it shows their intention in pursuing other opportunities which enhance their overall organizational performance. Obviously, improving financial rates are important for any enterprise but beside these rates other aspects related to society should be also considered and this is the view that these enterprises expressed concerning this item in this study.

It is important to mention that the for-profit public and private enterprises are considerably concerned with their overall economic responsibilities of CSR in the Yemeni society. This undoubtedly reflects the importance of these responsibilities especially towards the for-profit enterprises' various stakeholders existing in the Yemeni society.

5.5.2 Legal Responsibilities

The responsibilities of enterprises include also legal aspects in which enterprises are operate in the society in accordance with subsisting laws, regulations, and rules. These legal behaviors stemming from the enterprises legal responsibilities are expected by individuals of the society and also by the government (Carroll *et al.*, 2009).

In this regard, the obtained results of this study show that the majority of respondents who represent their for-profit enterprises have a high concern about the issue that their

enterprises should perform in a manner consistent with expectations of the government and the law in Yemen. This reflects the extreme concern of these enterprises on following the law and implementing other government regulations as required. It reflects also the enterprises' high concern about avoiding any kinds of legal violations or infringements that government would not anticipate from a for-profit public or private enterprise. Many respondents representing their for-profit enterprises believe that being committed to abiding laws and regulations as enterprises operating in the Yemeni market is extremely important. Enterprises are exceptionally aware of the serious consequences that could be caused due to any kinds of infringements. Some of these consequences could be very deleterious and could have serious negative effects on the enterprises. Accordingly, the commitment for abiding the laws is understood by these enterprises as a must especially if these enterprises have steady institutional actions and intend to live along in the market.

Based on the results that the enterprises' representatives expressed through their responses, they highly consider legal responsibilities of their enterprises are being seriously fulfilled. This reflects the level of maturity that these enterprises possess when dealing with laws and other legal regulations. They are highly aware that dealing slightly with these laws and regulations could jeopardize their existence in the market. Among the negative consequences of such ignorance are distorting the image of the enterprises in society, lessening the customers' loyalty, augmenting turnover rates, losing the market share, and other deleterious and detrimental effects. As a result, enterprises work hardly and critically to carry out their legal responsibilities and this issue was very clear through the responses of their representatives.

In this way, nearly half of the enterprises' respondents have a high concern about preventing social norms from being compromised in order to achieve the enterprise goals. It seems that those enterprises' representatives extremely care about social norms prevailed in the Yemeni society and extremely care about the sensitive effects that these social norms could have on the enterprises. These social norms (i.e., moral or legal rules) should not be bargained by the enterprises for having any kind of financial gains. Enterprises are aware that in a society like Yemen, playing with any type of social norms should be cautiously performed due to the structure and diversity of this society. They are also aware that illiteracy and other radical dogmas are deep-rooted in the Yemeni society and they form a major social norm for many individuals living in the same society. These issues accordingly are responsively treated by these enterprises without taking the risk in meeting halfway them with the intention of fulfilling any other organizational objectives.

Roughly, half of the for-profit enterprises' representatives are concerned with defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its legal obligations. Most of these enterprises hire lawyers and legists who operate and deal with the legal situations of these enterprises in accordance with the Yemeni laws and regulations. Moreover, many enterprises care about having convenient legal situations in the society which help in enhancing their images among customers and among other government entities. Besides, being successful enterprises due to fulfilling all required legal obligations would create a competitive advantage for these enterprises in the Yemeni market. Similarly, the obtained results of this study revealed that nearly half of the enterprises are highly concerned about providing goods and services which at least meet the minimal legal requirements. This could be attributed to the Yemeni legislations and acts which care about the quality and type of provided products and services by various

SOEs and private enterprises. Sometimes, some of these legislations are not fully applied or followed by the Yemeni for-profit enterprises but this would not be a reason for those enterprises to lose the desire in not legally providing such acceptable quality for these goods and services for the society. This issue plainly reflects the high level of social and legal responsibility that these enterprises possess towards their customers in Yemen.

Furthermore, half of the enterprises believe that it is extremely important to view compliance with the law as a useful measure of the organizational performance. This finding reflects the enterprises' attitude towards evaluating their organizational performance through strictly following Yemeni laws, regulations, and other rules. Enterprises perform this rigorous attitude due to their belief that both the society and the government expect such attitude from them and expect them to also pursue adhering to such praised act as a usual behavior. All these activities ensure improvements in the organizational performance of these enterprises and this is highly understood by them. In addition, a major portion of the enterprises included in this study is extremely concerned with recognizing that corporate integrity and ethical behavior go beyond mere compliance with laws and regulations. In this regard, diverse for-profit enterprises are highly aware that following strictly laws and regulations is not enough for having adequate legal responsibilities of CSR. They are interested also in applying more norms and morals which transcend the process of implementing laws and regulations. According to their responses, these enterprises are also greatly interested in applying and practicing other ethical norms and behaviors when dealing with customers, government, and other elements of the Yemeni society.

It is significant to state that the SOEs and private enterprises in Yemen seem to be considerably concerned with their overall legal responsibilities of CSR. This obviously reflects the level of compliance and adherence to different laws, regulations, and rules applied in the Yemeni society by these for-profit enterprises.

5.5.3 Ethical Responsibilities

Although enterprises have legal responsibilities and care about rightfully fulfilling them, other responsibilities that transcend laws and regulations must also be maintained. These responsibilities are the ethical ones which include norms, mores, and other societal values. Different stakeholders are concerned with ethical responsibilities and anticipate for-profit public and private enterprises to implement them morally, justly, and fairly (Carroll *et al.*, 2009).

In this way, the results obtained from this study revealed that more than half of the respondents who represent their for-profit enterprises have a high concern about the issue that their enterprises should perform in a manner consistent with expectations of societal mores and ethical norms in Yemen. This reflects the exceptional concern of these enterprises on adhering to the conventional societal mores and ethical norms while performing their business and corporate activities. It reflects also the enterprises' extreme concern about avoiding any types of ethical deviations that society would not anticipate from them. Enterprises in Yemen are aware that Yemeni society still believes in the essential roles of the ethics and mores in steering its daily activities. Accordingly, these enterprises operate according to this fact and try to fulfill ethically the expectations of the Yemeni society.

A significant portion of the respondents representing their for-profit enterprises believes that advertising about goods and services in an ethically fair and responsible manner is

extremely important. These enterprises are aware of the structure of the Yemeni society and also aware of the mentality of the Yemeni consumers. Enterprises know that their created advertisements broadcast in different media and shown in main streets and markets should be consistent with the Yemeni ethical norms and societal mores. For example, these advertisements about enterprises' services and products should be fairly disseminated in different places containing various groups of people. Also, these advertisements should care about the ethical contents and messages delivered to consumers. The role of the government in this respect is to monitor and control such ethical contents but the enterprises should internally maintain a high level of awareness and concern about how they ethically advertise their services and products in the Yemen society and this was shown through their responses in this study.

Based on the results that the enterprises' representatives expressed through their responses, a major portion of them have a high concern about avoiding discrimination against women as minorities in the society. This reflects the high level of maturity that these enterprises possess when dealing with issues concerning the Yemeni woman either as a customer or as an employee. The Yemeni women represent a minority in the Yemeni society as customers and as employees and having such remarkable level of awareness from these enterprises towards them is something remarkable. The enterprises know that nearly half of the Yemeni population consists of females and exploiting such sector is strategically a major concern for any for-profit enterprise in Yemen. Accordingly, enterprises focus now in eschewing any kind of discrimination against women as expected consumers for their services and products in the future. These enterprises also try to avoid such discrimination through hiring female employees and assigning them in top- and middle-level managerial positions. Such ethical behaviors and acts from these enterprises would enhance their image in the society

especially among females and this would create a competitive advantage for those for-profit enterprises.

Furthermore, nearly half of the enterprises' respondents are extremely concerned with defining a successful enterprise as the one which fulfills its ethical and moral responsibilities. Yemen as an Arabic and Muslim country has many ethical and moral norms that every enterprise should respect and work in line with to be successful. Adherence to such fact would be also a competitive advantage for these enterprises that want to vie ethically and responsibly in the Yemeni market. At the same time and through expressing such attitude by these enterprises, more successful enterprises are existent and will exist in the Yemeni market for their faithful obligations and industrious efforts in implementing their activities more ethically and morally.

Roughly, half of the for-profit enterprises' representatives are concerned with monitoring new opportunities which can enhance the enterprise's moral and ethical image in society. This concern has several aspects of importance for these enterprises. In marketing and strategic management, enhancing various facets of the enterprise in society could create a competitive advantage for this enterprise. One of these facets is the corporate image which could improve the sales of the corporate and its market share or conversely could damage its reputation and make this enterprise incurs continuous losses. It seems that these enterprises are aware of these strategic and marketing concepts. Hence, they work in accordance with them trying hardly to keep enhancing their images which will contribute in augmenting their reputation and their market share in the Yemeni society.

Moreover, the obtained results of this study revealed that nearly half of the enterprises are highly concerned about avoiding compromising societal norms and ethics in order to

achieve goals. Social norms and ethics should be an essential part of the organizational behavior in which enterprises adopt and operate within the society. It seems that for-profit enterprises are knowledgeable about the fact that these societal norms and ethics should not be bargained for acquiring any tentative organizational goals. This reflects the experience that these enterprises have about the Yemeni society and the Yemeni market. It reflects also the social and ethical concern of these enterprises which can differentiate between practices and behaviors that could achieve organizational goals from others that cannot at all.

Furthermore, a small portion of the enterprises believes that it is important to encourage the act of whistle blowing at any corporate level. This finding reflects the enterprises' attitude towards this act which is encouraged by some enterprises and discouraged by others. The low rate that this item obtained in this study among enterprises reflects the unawareness of these Yemeni enterprises for such behavioral and ethical issue. Enterprises seem to roughly and indolently encourage such act performed by their employees, namely, the whistle blowers. On the other hand, it seems that these enterprises know about the consequences of such issue which entails ethical and legal aspects such as lawsuits, protection of whistle blowers, scandals, and other aspects. For these reasons, other enterprises considerably discourage such issue and reject it. This ethical issue is related to the organizational culture and behavior in which employees are encouraged or discouraged to report about misconducts or any other infringements that could lead to undesirable havoc inside the enterprise. Accordingly, only some of the Yemeni for-profit enterprises encourage whistle blowing as an ethical responsibility at any managerial level. Conversely, other for-profit enterprises either are not aware of this issue or just eschewing it for several reasons discussed previously.

A major portion of the representatives of the enterprises included in this study is extremely concerned with fulfilling all tax obligations of their respective enterprises. These enterprises extensively know that fulfilling all tax obligations is the main essential factor for their continuity in the market and in the whole society. The government and the individuals of the society expect these enterprises to ethically operate and ethically settle all required tax obligations in return for making proper profits and gaining other financial and economic benefits. The for-profit enterprises show through this item their exceptional concern about taxes and this reflects plainly their ethical endeavors towards avoiding any lawsuits or grievances related to tax which could jeopardize their trades and also their image in the Yemeni society.

It is noteworthy to state that the private enterprises and SOEs in Yemen give the impression to be considerably concerned with their overall ethical responsibilities of CSR. This palpably reflects the enterprises' level of awareness for the importance of having ethics, morals, and all other ethical responsibilities as serious obligations towards the Yemeni society.

5.5.4 Philanthropic Responsibilities

The enterprises' philanthropic responsibilities are related to the charitable, voluntary, benevolent, and discretionary responsibilities that an enterprise has in the society. This kind of responsibilities is optional not compulsory and is voluntary not required by the law. Among the types of philanthropic responsibilities are donations of products, services, and cash, also volunteerism of employees and managers as well as supporting society free at large (Carroll *et al.*, 2009). Besides, most of the charitable activities in some countries like Yemen are embedded in the philanthropic responsibilities and many

enterprises do not mention these activities for the public due to considering fulfilling them as a spiritual or religious issue.

In this manner, the obtained results of this study revealed that nearly half of the respondents who represent their for-profit enterprises have a concern about performing in a manner consistent with the philanthropic and charitable expectations of society in Yemen. This reflects the concern of these enterprises on being good corporate citizens in the Yemeni society through adopting charitable and philanthropic beliefs and actions. The act of being a good corporate citizen includes for example fulfilling all tax obligations, participating in the rights of expressing independent and open opinions, and also involving in lobbying and other governance-related actions. It reflects also the enterprises' concern about supporting and fostering their society with possible charitable tangible and intangible donations. Roughly, half of the respondents representing their for-profit enterprises believe that participating as managers and employees in voluntary and charitable activities within their local communities is important. It seems that for-profit enterprises are partially concerned about encouraging and pushing their managers and employees to be voluntarily active in their communities. These enterprises care more about functional throughput extracted from the efforts of those middle- and lower-level subordinates at work. Through the responses of the enterprises included in the sample of this study, it was clear that bringing up the concept and feeling of dedicating a portion of the employees' time in charitable and voluntary activities is still unattained clearly and practically in these enterprises.

A rational portion of the for-profit enterprises considers that providing assistance to private and public educational institutions is important. This could be justified as the

intention of these enterprises in fulfilling charitable and philanthropic responsibilities for society and at the same time in gaining other advantageous marketing gains. Enterprises are aware that having an affirmative image among a pivotal and effective sector of the society (i.e., female and male students of schools, universities, community colleges, and other educational and academic institutes) can ensure boosting sales and accordingly capitalizing on periodic profits. Besides, the overall reputation of these enterprises—which have philanthropic responsibilities on academic and educational entities—could be improved to contribute in enhancing their market share in the Yemeni market. However, not all enterprises have the same level of adoption for this item (i.e., adopting philanthropic responsibilities on academic and educational entities) and this reflects the unawareness of this marketing issue among these hesitant and indolent Yemeni for-profit enterprises.

Based on the results that the enterprises' representatives expressed through their responses, they are to some extent concerned with defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its philanthropic and charitable responsibilities. Many other enterprises have less concern about relating a successful enterprise in the Yemeni society with being philanthropic and charitable. This could be attributed to the unawareness about volunteerism and philanthropy especially among various for-profit and private enterprises in Yemen. It is obvious to notice that enterprises sampled in this study have less attention to philanthropic responsibilities and they clearly understand that being successful does not necessarily entail being charitable and philanthropic in the society.

In this regard, roughly more than half of the enterprises' respondents consider monitoring new opportunities which can enhance their enterprises' abilities to help solve social problems as important. It seems that those enterprises' representatives are

somewhat concerned about solving social problems in the Yemeni society and that they have more interests in other issues. Solving social problems is the responsibility of the government authorities but in a country like Yemen for-profit public and private enterprises could have a hand in successfully solving these problems. This does not mean that these enterprises should spot all new opportunities and take the initiative for solving social problems hoping that this action could contribute in improving their abilities in this regard. Critical and serious social problems such as pollution, poverty, or unemployment need these enterprises to contribute philanthropically in solving them without expecting to have any financial or economic outcomes in return. This could make many for-profit enterprises to be lethargic in acquiring more abilities regarding solving social problems in a society like the Yemeni one.

In this way, less than half of the for-profit enterprises' representatives are moderately concerned with assisting voluntarily those projects which enhance a community's quality of life. These projects are concerned with pivotal and fundamental related issues to humans living in their communities such as health and livelihood. The representatives of the for-profit enterprises represented in this sample have moderate concern about such projects which care about contributing philanthropically in enhancing the quality of life of the Yemeni society and of its female and male members. As discussed in previous items concerning the philanthropic responsibilities of for-profit enterprises, it is apparent that these enterprises have less attention towards such responsibilities and their associated projects. The dominant culture of these enterprises is among the main factors contributing in such ignorance for these essential voluntary responsibilities. In general, this culture stems from the founder of the enterprise and is imparted to all levels of management in the enterprise itself. It could be also due to the type of education and customs that employees embrace and use for their daily life. Accordingly,

many projects which help in improving the community's quality of life—such as projects concerning health, education, and means of support—are in many cases disregarded by these enterprises and this causes deteriorating for the quality of life in the Yemeni society.

Similarly, the obtained results of this study revealed that less than half of the enterprises are quite concerned about viewing philanthropic behavior as a useful measure of the organizational performance. It is palpable that many enterprises are concerned about measuring their organizational performance through tangible concrete measures. These measures could be financial, economic, legal, or even managerial. Philanthropic responsibilities and adhering to them is viewed by these for-profit enterprises as an extra or secondary measure which has no direct impact on the performance of these enterprises. The explanation of this inhibitive attitude from these enterprises towards using discretionary behavior in evaluating their organizational performance could stem from several reasons. Among these reasons are the perplexed construction of the Yemeni society itself, the level of education for the enterprise's members, the level of culture for the enterprise's members, the level of awareness among the enterprise's members about philanthropy and volunteerism principles, and on top of that the economic situations of this society. Furthermore, half of the enterprises' representatives believe that it is important to maintain a policy of increasing charitable and voluntary efforts over time. This finding reflects the enterprises' intention towards having an institutional arranged policy that adopts and stresses on rising related activities to the charitable and voluntary efforts over time. Enterprises in this point could have another way of thinking concerning the institutional activities that organize and increase any prospective philanthropic responsibilities through a well-planned course of action. This could be an achievement for these enterprises which adopt well-designed voluntary

activities and philanthropic responsibilities which could have positive impacts on their image and reputation in the Yemeni society in the recent future.

It is substantial to mention that the SOEs and private enterprises in Yemen appear to be moderately concerned with their overall philanthropic responsibilities of CSR. This can be attributed to the fact that the philanthropy and volunteerism are still marginal concepts in the Yemeni society. In this way, adopting successfully these concepts by for-profit public and private enterprises in Yemen requires an integration process from the government, the private sector, and also the nongovernmental sector.

5.6 Limitations of the Research

Through reading the different chapters comprising this study, it can be noticed that the researcher has offered empirical findings concerning the relationship between corporate social responsibility and nonfinancial organizational performance of for-profit public and private enterprises operating in diverse economic sectors in Yemen. Another notable empirical finding was about the difference in adopting generally the concept of CSR between SOEs and private enterprises as a periodic institutional activity. One of the major limitations of this study—that should be considered—is about the respondents themselves who are the representatives of the for-profit public and private enterprises. Due to the fact that the primary data were collected from those respondents, potential personal preferences could be obtained in their responses. These personal preferences could be affected by the respondents' educational backgrounds, social propensities, and personal experiences about the different variables measured in this study. This issue was notable during the process of collecting the questionnaires where several respondents had no sufficient details about the components of CSR and about their pivotal functions in the society.

Another second major limitation of this study was about not using the financial and objective measures for assessing the organizational performance. This was due to the sensitivity of the financial information that many for-profit public and private enterprises could reject to provide or reveal. This information could include reviewing annual reports for these enterprises which would create a big problem for any researcher. It was obvious that many for-profit enterprises have real annual reports revealed only for shareholders and other specific entities whereas announced annual reports are no more than modified reports with partial trivial data. Accordingly and for making this study more realistic in a Third World country like Yemen, using financial or objective measures for measuring the organizational performance of these for-profit enterprises was squarely eschewed—although they are more precise and practical—and they were replaced with the nonfinancial and perceptual measures.

A third limitation was concerned with the process of gathering the questionnaires from the randomly selected for-profit public and private Yemeni enterprises comprising the sample of this study. It is an issue that should be considered by other researchers who plan and intend to conduct studies or researches in Yemen. It is clear that a major portion of these enterprises demonstrate a palpable reluctance towards a researcher especially those researchers who tackle sensitive and social issues in the Yemeni society. The level of awareness in these reluctant enterprises concerning academic researching process is still clearly shallow and discouraging. For example, many of those researchers had terrible time waiting for more than 10 days for a questionnaire to be answered and in several cases they could eventually receive an empty or half-finished questionnaire. Hence, a researcher in Yemen should expect to encounter a harsh and frustrating environment for conducting social field studies and researches. Thence, it will be practical to hire a female eloquent helper for the process of

disseminating the questionnaires among respondents and for easily convincing those respondents to shortly fill the questionnaires and return them fully replied in the same day.

A final limitation of the study was related to the sample nature in which more than 100 for-profit public and private enterprises were included from both public and private sectors in Yemen. This made the range of the sample vast but with many diverse enterprises that are partially or entirely involved in CSR activities. In addition, the number of the operating successful SOEs (i.e., for-profit public enterprises) specifically in the sample and generally in Yemen is still very limited. Furthermore, the lack of using proper control variables in the study contributed in the difficulty of assigning which for-profit enterprise should be seriously considered in the sample when tracing the effects of CSR on the nonfinancial organizational performance.

5.7 Recommendations

The researcher of this study has suggested several recommendations that are preferable to be considered among interested academic researchers and other managers of for-profit enterprises. The most essential and major recommendation of this study should be directed to the for-profit public enterprises in Yemen. These SOEs should profoundly review their social responsibilities and try to relate them more with the nonfinancial (i.e., perceptual) organizational performance and not caring only about relating CSR to the sheer objective aspects of their organizational performance. It is notable to say that Yemeni for-profit enterprises have less intention to apply an institutional work that pays a great attention to the social responsibility and its various components. The nature of the government activities with their bureaucratic and other tedious routines and red tapes creates a major obstacle towards adopting CSR and activating it constructively in

the society. For-profit public enterprises are recommended to be more serious when dealing with their society and being highly aware that they should be the ideal for other private enterprises in adopting all related aspects of a widely essential concept such as CSR.

The role of the Yemeni government—either as for-profit enterprises or as typical ministries operating in the society—concerning corporate social responsibility should be activated and enhanced for the benefit of the entire society. Yemeni government is recommended to gradually adopt and implement well-planned policies that encourage all for-profit enterprises (i.e., public and private) to have social responsibilities as a periodic institutional activity that is joined to their annual financial budgets and also their published annual reports. Thence and to stress on this point, it is important to mention here that the government of the United Kingdom has dedicated a whole minister for managing the related issues of CSR. This minister is responsible for managing all business cases related to CSR and also coordinating the government activities related to CSR encouraging and raising in all sizes enterprises (Finskas, 2007). Accordingly, the officials of the Yemeni government should be aware that CSR is a vital strategic and futuristic issue that helps in socially elevating different economic, legal, ethical, philanthropic, and also humane aspects in the society.

Hence, it is recommended that the Yemeni government should pay a considerable attention to the economic social responsibilities through having more real and constructive partnership with the private sector concerning all social issues that enhance the quality of life in the Yemeni society. The Yemeni government also should pay a considerable attention to the legal social responsibilities through seriously and persistently applying laws and regulations on all for-profit enterprises and ensuring that

offered services and products by these enterprises meet the expected and satisfactory legal requirements. Moreover, the Yemeni government should pay a considerable attention to the ethical social responsibilities through objectively and honestly collecting all required tax obligations from all for-profit enterprises and through eradicating all concealed and unethical activities and behaviors related to different types of tax evasion. Furthermore, the Yemeni government should pay a considerable attention to the philanthropic social responsibilities through fostering, inciting, and instilling the lofty meanings of volunteerism and philanthropy in society at large. Besides, the Yemeni government should pay a considerable attention to the humane social responsibilities through sensibly and spiritually dealing with all individuals and entities comprising the enterprises' stakeholders with responsibly caring about all humans and nonhumans in the whole society.

Another recommendation is palpably aimed at different private enterprises and especially large ones in Yemen. These enterprises should pay a great attention to CSR and its fruitful long-term advantages through several means. These enterprises are advised to establish independent units for managing all related issues to CSR and its periodic activities. Besides, dedicating a portion of these private enterprises' annual budgets for implementing the activities of CSR could have many positive impacts on them and on the whole society. According to McWilliams *et al.* (2001), they argue that numerous large firms have dedicated CSR departments for managing related CSR concerns. They claim that larger enterprises will provide more CSR activities over smaller firms (i.e., SMEs) due to the fact that the products or services of these larger enterprises can be differentiated. Hence, Yemeni large enterprises should adopt several periodic CSR activities in the society and not implementing only seasonal and annual charitable activities and consider them as full social responsibilities towards their

society. Charitable, benevolent, and other spiritual or religious responsibilities—such as donations, endowments, and alms—only represent a limited portion of the overall social responsibilities that should be considerably offered to the society. In fact, these for-profit enterprises pretend to offer valuable charitable responsibilities to the society but in reality these offered donations and alms are not well employed or disseminated since the situations of the Yemeni society are not improved but conversely become worse over time. For these reasons, a person apparently could notice that many Yemenis are still living in downtrodden situations and have a little chance to perceive the expected economic desirable effects of a pivotal concept like CSR. Consequently, these private enterprises are recommended to be aware to the essential differences between these charitable responsibilities and other different aspects of CSR that extremely could influence the quality of life in the Yemeni society at large.

5.8 Future Researches

Through inspecting the available body of literature concerning CSR and its components, a researcher could have partial difficulties in finding authenticated and original resources of papers or other academic researches (i.e., Master's theses and doctoral dissertations) tackling the issue of CSR in public sector and especially in SOEs. This could be attributed to the fact that not all nations have successful state-owned enterprises that care greatly about adopting CSR attributes and activities in their societies. Hence, future researches should focus on exploring more the potential relationship between entities operating in the public sector and CSR activities. This could include exploring more about the potential effects that CSR could have on the activities of different public enterprises and organizations operating in Yemen—as a Third World country—and exploring more about the factors that could make public organizations think seriously to adopt CSR attributes and activities periodically.

Furthermore, other future researches could include conducting a comparative analysis about the level of adopting CSR activities in different types of organizations operating in Yemen (i.e., SOEs, private, and nongovernmental). This could shed light on the most successful type of organizations among the three mentioned types that actually and persistently adopts CSR and works on making it as an institutional periodic activity and behavior inside the organization itself. Studying curiously and thoroughly the nature of the relationship that could subsist between an organization that adopts successfully CSR with its various components in a Third World country like Yemen and the type of this organization could have a major contribution to the existent literature concerning CSR adoption in developing countries. This would be also a main concern for many researchers and scholars inside and outside Yemen who have interests in empirical studies related to diverse social issues and especially CSR.

Moreover, it is beneficial for additional future researches to tackle the influence that CSR could have on different managerial issues in Yemen. This could include studying the relationship between CSR as independent variable with other various dependent variables such as transparency, productivity, public policy, strategic planning, leadership, organizational behavior, organizational culture, strategic management, and strategic marketing. Adding more variables—such as control, mediator, or moderator variables—could be very helpful for having more detailed and precise results concerning the relationships that CSR could have with each one of these different dependent variables included in prospective future researches which could reveal more empirical explanations about the reality of CSR in a developing country like Yemen.

5.9 Conclusion

The current conducted study examined the influence of CSR with its four components (i.e., economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities) as the independent variable on the nonfinancial organizational performance as the dependent variable in the for-profit public and private enterprises operating in different economic sectors in Yemen. The study also aimed at finding if there is a significant difference between SOEs and private enterprises concerning the level of adopting in general CSR as a periodic institutional activity. The study used a quantitative research method in which 103 for-profit Yemeni public and private enterprises were surveyed to empirically investigate the assigned hypotheses and research questions contained in this study. The obtained results collected through the 40-question questionnaire revealed that the four components of CSR have positive significant relationships with the nonfinancial organizational performance when measured separately in private enterprises and in both SOEs and private enterprises as a whole entity. On the contrary, the four components of CSR have insignificant influence on the dependent variable, namely, the nonfinancial organizational performance, when measured separately in only the for-profit public enterprises. Besides, there was insignificant difference in the level of adopting CSR generally between SOEs and private enterprises in Yemen as a periodic institutional activity.

Through the different stages required for conducting this study, any researcher would have a considerable debate existed among diverse researchers and scholars in the literature concerning the definitions of CSR and its different dimensions. Among the contributions that this study offers are: (i) tackling objectively the relationship between CSR and the nonfinancial or perceptual organizational performance; (ii) clarifying palpably for Yemeni executives, managers, officials, and even typical subordinates

operating in Yemen that CSR—to a considerable extent—is more than only a charitable or benevolent activity; (iii) tackling the concept of CSR with its four categories in different Yemeni state-owned enterprises as for-profit public entities; and (iv) offering a personal theoretical contribution for a new definition of CSR that could be joined to the copious definitions of this concept available in the body of literature. Accordingly, the researcher of this study suggests a definition for CSR that could be an object of interest for different researchers and scholars in the academia. This postulated definition can define CSR as follows:

CSR is the social responsibility of various for-profit and nonprofit organizations that involves the reciprocal relationship between these organizations and their stakeholders including shareholders, government, NGOs, and society at large as the core stakeholders. These social responsibilities have several types including economic, legal, ethical, philanthropic, and also humane responsibilities. The economic responsibilities are more concerned with shareholders, the legal responsibilities are more concerned with the state's legislative and statutory laws, the ethical responsibilities are more concerned with customers through finished products and services, the philanthropic responsibilities are more concerned with local communities and charities, and the humane responsibilities are more concerned with all members and entities belonging to the stakeholders of a business at large as humans and even as nonhumans.

Once more and relating to the role of the Yemeni government concerning CSR and its adoption by different for-profit and nonprofit entities operating in the society, the concept of CSR in Yemen is still in its primitive stage and needs to be more responsibly considered and discussed in different public and private media and press through a direct support from the Yemeni government itself. The Yemeni government should have serious steps and procedures for rendering these for-profit and nonprofit entities in the society to positively adopt CSR and participate effectively in enhancing the quality of life of the Yemeni society. Losing strength and power as a government in pushing these organizations to participate seriously in CSR's activities in the society could make them behave irresponsibly and care only about having the maximum portion of available profits, disseminating insignificant charitable donations, and doing no more

for the society. Holding effective conferences and workshops concerning CSR and its influence on strategy and enhancing the overall situations of the society is something essential and productive. The Yemeni government is also required to enact additional and modern laws and regulations that organize and monitor the activities of CSR in various for-profit and nonprofit public and private organizations and at the same time penalize those who evade following such laws. This also includes stressing on relating social responsibility with transparency through including transparently CSR activities in all published annual reports of every for-profit and nonprofit enterprise in Yemen. To conclude, the concept of CSR is vital for all members and entities comprising the society (i.e., stakeholders) and having an organized and planned integration among all these components would create the desired enduring prosperity and welfare.

Furthermore, the limitations of this study include having potential personal preferences among respondents who represent their enterprises concerning the influence of CSR with its four components on the nonfinancial organizational performance. Moreover, using subjective or perceptual measures for assessing the organizational performance forms another limitation for this study. In addition, another limitation is related to having many diverse for-profit public and private enterprises with multiple commercial and economic activities in the sample of the study.

One of the future researches suggests exploring more about the expected relationship between entities operating in the public sector and CSR activities with its four components. Another future research is concerned with focusing on conducting comparative analysis about the level of adopting CSR activities in different types of organizations operating in Yemen such as SOEs, private, and nongovernmental for having a close look about which type is more successful in adopting this concept and

why. As a last suggestion for future researches, studying empirically CSR as an independent variable could be done with other managerial dependent variables such as transparency, organizational culture, public policy, strategic planning, strategic management, strategic marketing, and others for having vast and detailed knowledge about the influence that CSR could have with each one of those dependent variables.

Ultimately, this study has seriously recommended for-profit public enterprises in Yemen to considerably review their aspects of social responsibilities and activating them and try to relate these activities with the nonfinancial organizational performance. This type of organizational performance includes supporting innovation, elevating quality of offered products and services, having positive communication between management and staff, caring more about possible ways for increasing the customers' satisfaction, and other related issues. The study also recommended that the Yemeni government should work effectively to formulate well-planned CSR policies, enact extra and contemporary laws and regulations concerning CSR activities, and painstakingly incite all for-profit and nonprofit entities to seriously adopt CSR activities and accordingly contribute in improving the entire Yemeni society. As a last recommendation that this study suggests, the Yemeni large for-profit enterprises should adopt several periodic CSR activities in the society and not being only content with implementing seasonal charitable activities from time to time. This would greatly contribute in enhancing the reputation and image of these enterprises in the whole society and could also contribute in having a more prosper Yemeni society with more convenient and satisfied individuals.

REFERENCES

- Akanbi, Paul Ayobami, & Ofoegbu, Onyema Eugene. (2012). *Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Bank Performance in Nigeria*. Journal of US-China Public Administration, Vol. 9 No. 4, pp. 374-383.
- Al-Abbasi, Basem M. (2011). *Corporate Social Responsibility in Yemen: A Case of Taiz Industrial Zone* (Master's thesis). University of Essex, Essex Business School, United Kingdom.
- Al-Hamdi, Fuad M. (2003). *Marketing Dimensions of Corporate Social Responsibility and its Effects on Customer Satisfaction* (Doctoral dissertation). Al-Mustansiriya University, Faculty of Management and Economics, Baghdad, Iraq.
- Al-Hamdi, Fuad M., & Ja'abil, Majid M. (2008). *The Extent of Managers' Perception Concerning the Concept of Corporate Social Responsibility and its Resulted Activities*. An analytical study about the managers' opinions working in sampled industrial organizations in Yemen. College of Administrative Sciences, University of Dhamar, Yemen.
- Al-Kumaim, Fuad M. (2006). *Social Responsibility of Governmental Officers in Yemen* (Master's thesis). Al-Nailain University, College of Higher Education, Republic of Sudan.
- Allen, Richard S., Dawson, Gail, Wheatley, Kathleen, & White, Charles S. (2008). *Perceived diversity and organizational performance*. Employee Relations, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 20-33.
- Amba-Rao, Sita C. (1993). *Multinational Corporate Social Responsibility, Ethics, Interactions and Third World Governments: An Agenda for the 1990s*. Journal of Business Ethics, 12, pp. 553-572.
- Aupperle, K.E., Carroll, A. B., & Hatfield, J.D. (1985). *An empirical investigation of the relationship between corporate social responsibility and profitability*. Academy of Management Journal, Vol. 28 No. 2, pp. 446-63.
- Azzellino, Dayner. (2011). *The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility Policy on Manufacturing Firm Productivity in Trinidad and Tobago* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3487590.
- Bacha, Eliane. (2010). *The relationships among organizational performance, environmental uncertainty, and employees' perceptions of CEO charisma*. Journal of Management Development, Vol. 29 No. 1, pp. 28-37.
- Banerjee, S. Bobby. (2007). *Corporate Social Responsibility: The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly*. Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar Publishing, Inc.

- Becchetti, Leonardo, Di Giacomo, Stefania, & Pinnacchio, Damiano. (2005). *Corporate Social Responsibility and Corporate Performance: Evidence from a Panel of US Listed Companies*. CEIS Tor Vergata-Research Paper Series, Vol. 26 No. 78, pp. 1-56.
- Bird, Ron, Casavecchia, Lorenzo, & Reggiani, Francesco. (2006). *Corporate Social Responsibility and Corporate Performance: Where to Begin?* University of Technology, Sydney; Bocconi University, Milan; EFM Codes: 210, 750.
- Boulay, David A. (2008). *An Exploration of The Relationships among Organizational Size, Flexible Work Practices, Training, and Organizational Performance Using the 2002 National Organizations Survey* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3300125.
- Brigham, Eugene F., & Ehrhardt, Michael C. (2005) *Financial Management: Theory and Practice*. Mason, OH: South-Western Cengage Learning.
- Campbell, John L. (2007). *Why would corporations behave in socially responsible ways? An institutional theory of corporate social responsibility*. *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 32 No. 3, pp. 946-967.
- Carroll, Archie B. (1979). *A three-dimensional conceptual model of corporate social performance*. *Academy of Management Review*, 4, pp. 497-505.
- Carroll, Archie B. (1991). *The pyramid of corporate social responsibility: toward the moral management of organizational stakeholders*. *Business Horizons*, July–August, 34, pp. 39-48.
- Carroll, Archie B. (1994). *Social Issues in Management Research: Experts' Views, Analysis, and Commentary*. *Business & Society*, Vol. 33 No. 1, pp. 5-29.
- Carroll, Archie B. (1999). *Corporate Social Responsibility: Evolution of a Definitional Construct*. *Business & Society*, Vol. 38 No. 3, pp. 268-295.
- Carroll, Archie B. (2000). *Ethical Challenges for Business in the New Millennium: Corporate Social Responsibility and Models of Management Morality*. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 33-42.
- Carroll, Archie B. (2004). *Managing ethically with global stakeholders: A present and future challenge*. *Academy of Management Executive*, Vol. 18 No. 2, pp. 114-120.
- Carroll, Archie B. (2008). *A history of corporate social responsibility: concepts and practices*. *The Oxford Handbook of Corporate Social Responsibility*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 19-46.
- Carroll, Archie B., & Buchholtz, Ann K. (2009) *Business & Society: Ethics and Stakeholder Management* (7th ed.). Mason, OH: South-Western Cengage Learning.

- Carroll, Archie B., & Shabana, Kareem M. (2010). *The Business Case for Corporate Social Responsibility: A Review of Concepts, Research and Practice*. International Journal of Management Reviews, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 85-104.
- Carroll, G. R., & Hannan, M. T. (2000). *The Demography of Corporations and Industries*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Carter, Craig R. (2005). *Purchasing social responsibility and firm performance: The key mediating roles of organizational learning and supplier performance*. International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management, Vol. 35 No. 3, pp. 177-194.
- Carton, Robert B. (2004). *Measuring Organizational Performance: An Exploratory Study* (Doctoral dissertation). The University of Georgia, Athens: Georgia.
- Carton, Robert B., & Hofer, Charles W. (2006). *Measuring organizational performance: Metrics for entrepreneurship and strategic management research*. Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar Publishing, Inc.
- Certo, Samuel C., & Certo, S. Trevis. (2009). *Modern Management: Concepts and Skills* (11th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Chajnicki, Gregory M. (2007). *Characteristics of Learning Organizations and Multi-Dimensional Organizational Performance Indicators: A Survey of Large, Publicly-Owned Companies* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3266083.
- Chan, Simon C.H., & Mak, Wai-ming. (2012). *High performance human resource practices and organizational performance: The mediating role of occupational safety and health*. Journal of Chinese Human Resource Management, Vol. 3 No. 2, pp. 136-150.
- Christiansen, Hans. (2013). *Balancing Commercial and Non-Commercial Priorities of State-Owned Enterprises*. OECD Corporate Governance Working Papers, No. 6, OECD Publishing.
- Coakes, Sheridan J., & Steed, Lyndall. (2005). *SPSS Version 12.0 for Windows: Analysis without Anguish* (1st ed.). Milton, New South Wales: John Wiley & Sons Australia, Ltd.
- Cohen, Jacob W. (1988). *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed.). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Crowther, David, & Aras, Güler. (2008). *Corporate Social Responsibility*. Ventus Publishing ApS. Retrieved February 19, 2013, from <http://www.bookboon.com>.
- Dahlsrud, Alexander. (2006). *How Corporate Social Responsibility is Defined: An Analysis of 37 Definitions*. Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management, Published online in Wiley InterScience, (www.interscience.wiley.com), DOI: 10.1002/csr.132.

- Davis, Keith. (1975). *Five Propositions for Social Responsibility*. Business Horizons, Vol. 18 No. 3, pp. 19-24.
- De Bernardis, L., Maiolini, Riccardo, & Braccini, A.M. (2010). *Corporate Social Responsibility in Private and Public Sector: Sustainability of Business versus Effectiveness of Action*. Published in the Proceedings of the XXXIII Convegno AIDEA, 21st-22nd October, Milan, Italy.
- Delaney, John J., & Huselid, Mark A. (1996). *The Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Perceptions of Organizational Performance*. Academy of Management Journal, Vol. 39 No. 4, pp. 949-969.
- Dollinger, Marc J., & Golden, Peggy A. (1992). *Interorganizational and Collective Strategies in Small Firms: Environmental Effects and Performance*. Journal of Management, Vol. 18, pp. 695-715.
- Duarte, Ana Patrícia, Mouro, Carla, & Das Neves, José Gonçalves. (2010). *Corporate social responsibility: mapping its social meaning*. Management Research: The Journal of the Iberoamerican Academy of Management, Vol. 8 No. 2, pp. 101-122.
- Epstein, Edwin M. (1987). *The corporate social policy process: Beyond business ethics, corporate social responsibility, and corporate social responsiveness*. California Management Review, Vol. 29 No. 3, pp. 99-114.
- Esa, Elinda, & Ghazali, Nazli A. M. (2012). *Corporate social responsibility and corporate governance in Malaysian government-linked companies*. Corporate Governance, Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 292-305.
- European Communities Commission. (2001). *Promoting a European Framework for Corporate Social Responsibilities*. Green Paper COM (2001) 366, Final Edition, European Commission, Brussels.
- Finskas, Heidi. (2007). *Corporate Social Responsibility in a governmental perspective: An analysis of public policies for CSR in Finland* (Master's thesis). Institute for Political Science, University of Oslo, Norway.
- Freeman, R. Edward. (1984). *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Boston, MA: Pitman.
- Freeman, R. Edward, Harrison, J., Wicks, A., Parmer, B., & De Colle, S. (2010). *Stakeholder Theory: The State of the Art*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Forester, Brooke E. (2009). *The Social Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility: A Case Study* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3373992.
- Gao, Yongqiang. (2011). *CSR in an emerging country: a content analysis of CSR reports of listed companies*. Baltic Journal of Management, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 263-291.

- Garriga, Elisabet, & Melé, Domènec. (2004). *Corporate Social Responsibility Theories: Mapping the Territory*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 53, pp. 51-71.
- Gavrea, Corina, Ilieș, Liviu, & Stegorean, Roxana. (2011). *Determinants of Organizational Performance: The Case of Romania*. *Management & Marketing, Challenges for the Knowledge Society*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 285-300.
- Griffin, Jennifer J., & Mahon, John F. (1997). *The corporate social performance and corporate financial performance debate*. *Business and Society*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp. 5-31.
- Guest, David E., & Peccei, Riccardo. (2001). *Partnership at Work: Mutuality and the Balance of Advantage*. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, Vol. 39 No. 2, pp. 207-236.
- Hamon, Timothy T. (2003). *Organizational Effectiveness as Explained by Social Structure In a Faith-Based Business Network Organization* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3082870.
- Hancott, Daren E. (2005). *The Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Performance in the Largest Public Companies in Canada* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3159704.
- Harrison, Jeffrey, & Freeman, R. Edward. (1999). *Stakeholders, Social Responsibility, and Performance: Empirical Evidence and Theoretical Perspectives*. *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 42 No. 5, pp. 479-485.
- Haynes, Barry P. (2007). *An Evaluation of Office Productivity Measurement*. *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 144-155.
- Henri, Jean-François. (2004). *Performance Measurement and Organizational Effectiveness: Bridging the Gap*. *Managerial Finance*, Vol. 30 No. 6, pp. 93-123.
- Hinz, Florian. (2009). *Corporate Social Responsibility in Chinese state-owned enterprises: An analysis of CSR practices among China's largest SOEs* (Master's thesis). School of Economics and Management, Department of Economics, Lund University. Retrieved June 23, 2013, from <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/1497052/file/1973581.pdf>
- Ho, Li-An. (2008). *What affects organizational performance?: The linking of learning and knowledge management*. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol. 108 No. 9, pp. 1234-1254.
- Ibodullayevna, Shakhnoza A. (2011). *Factors Influencing Brand Loyalty among Mobile Phone Users* (Master's thesis). Universiti Utara Malaysia, College of Business, Malaysia.

- Jones, Thomas M. (1995). *Instrumental Stakeholder Theory: A Synthesis of Ethics and Economics*. The Academy of Management Review, Vol. 20 No. 2, pp. 404-437.
- Kaplan, Robert S., & Norton, David P. (1996). *The Balanced Scorecard: Translating Strategy into Action*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- Katou, Anastasia A. (2012). *Investigating reverse causality between human resource management policies and organizational performance in small firms*. Management Research Review, Vol. 35 No. 2, pp. 134-156.
- Keinert, Christina. (2008). *Corporate Social Responsibility as an International Strategy*. Leipzig, Germany: Physica-Verlag Heidelberg.
- Kolb, Robert W. (2008). *Encyclopedia of Business Ethics and Society*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques* (2nd ed.). Daryaganj, New Delhi: New Age International (P) Ltd., Publishers.
- Kowalski, P., Büge, M., Sztajerowska, M., & Egeland, M. (2013). *State-Owned Enterprises: Trade Effects and Policy Implications*. OECD Trade Policy Papers, No. 147, OECD Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5k4869ckqk71-en>
- Kuo, Tsung-Hsien. (2011). *How to improve organizational performance through learning and knowledge?* International Journal of Manpower, Vol. 32 No. 5, pp. 581-603.
- Lee, Jiman, & Lee, Deog-Ro. (2009). *Labor-management partnership at Korean firms: Its effects on organizational performance and industrial relations quality*. Personnel Review, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 432-452.
- Lee, Min-Dong P. (2008). *A review of the theories of corporate social responsibility: Its evolutionary path and the road ahead*. International Journal of Management Reviews, Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 53-73.
- Leitão, João, & Franco, Mário. (2009). *Non-Economic Organizational Performance of SMEs: Is there a Rationale for a Cognitive Entrepreneur?* Proceedings of the 4th EDP Workshop-European Doctoral Programme (EDP) in Entrepreneurship and Small Business, 2-3 April of 2009, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, España.
- Lin, Chin-Yen, & Kuo, Tsung-Hsien. (2007). *The mediate effect of learning and knowledge on organizational performance*. Industrial Management & Data Systems, Vol. 107 No. 7, pp. 1066-1083.
- Lin, Li-Wen. (2010). *Corporate Social Responsibility in China: Window Dressing or Structural Change*. Berkeley Journal of International Law, Vol. 28 No. 1, Art. 3, pp. 1-36.

- Ling, Yap Lang. (2011). *The Relationship between Leader's Emotional Intelligence and Job Satisfaction at INTEL Malaysia* (Master's thesis). Universiti Utara Malaysia, College of Business, Malaysia.
- Lusthaus, Charles, Adrien, Marie-Hélène, Anderson, Gary, & Carden, Fred. (1999). *Enhancing Organizational Performance: A Toolbox for Self-assessment*. Ottawa, ON: International Development Research Centre.
- MacCarthaigh, Muiris. (2009). *The Corporate Governance of Commercial State-owned Enterprises in Ireland*. Institute of Public Administration. Dublin: Ireland, Future Print.
- Margolis, Joshua D., & Walsh, James P. (2003). *Misery Loves Companies: Rethinking Social Initiatives by Business*. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 48, pp. 268-305.
- McClerklin, Andre. (2013). *Making Sense of Corporate Social Responsibility from a Nonprofit-Centric Perspective* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3555045.
- McGuire, Jean B., Sundgren, A., & Schneeweis, T. (1988). *Corporate Social Responsibility and Firm Financial Performance*. *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 31 No. 4, pp. 854-872.
- McWilliams, Abigail, & Siegel, Donald. (2001). *Corporate social responsibility: A theory of the firm perspective*. *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 26 No. 1, pp. 117-127.
- Moideenkutty, Unnikammu, Al-Lamki, Asya, & Murthy, Y. Sree Rama. (2011). *HRM practices and organizational performance in Oman*. *Personnel Review*, Vol. 40 No. 2, pp. 239-251.
- Moura-Leite, Rosamaria C., & Padgett, Robert C. (2011). *Historical background of corporate social responsibility*. *Social Responsibility Journal*, Vol. 7 No. 4, pp. 528-539.
- Muijs, Daniel. (2004). *Doing Quantitative Research in Education with SPSS* (1st ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Munilla, Linda S., & Miles, Morgan P. (2005). *The Corporate Social Responsibility Continuum as a Component of Stakeholder Theory*. *Business and Society Review*, Vol. 110 No. 4, pp. 371-387.
- Naji, Mansour A. (2010). *Corporate Social Responsibility of Arabian Companies: A Comparative Study of YCGSI and YCIC in Yemen*. *Asian Journal of Development Matters*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 112-115.
- Ntoumanis, Nikos. (2001). *A Step-by-Step Guide to SPSS for Sport and Exercise Studies* (1st ed.). New York, NY: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

- Ohlrich, Keri. (2011). *Analyzing Corporate Social Responsibility's Impact on Employee Attraction and Retention with a Focus on Generation Y* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3481200.
- Okoye, Aadaeze. (2012). *Exploring the relationship between corporate social responsibility, law and development in an African context: Should government be responsible for ensuring corporate responsibility?* International Journal of Law and Management, Vol. 54 No. 5, pp. 364-378.
- Park, Ji Eun. (2010). *Exploring the effect of corporate social responsibility on firm performance: Antecedent, mediator and moderators* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3404328.
- Paskert, James M. (2008). *The impact of corporate social responsibility practices on corporate financial performance and consumer loyalty* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3340809.
- Pedersen, Esben Rahbek. (2006). *Making Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Operable: How Companies Translate Stakeholder Dialogue into Practice*. Business and Society Review, Vol. 111 No. 2, pp. 137-163.
- Phillips, Lynn W. (1981) *Assessing Measurement Error in Key Informant Reports: A Methodological Note on Organizational Analysis in Marketing*. Journal of Marketing Research, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 395-415.
- Private Enterprise. (2007). *Microsoft® Student with Encarta Premium 2008* [DVD]. Redmond, WA: Microsoft Corporation, 2007.
- Porter, Michael E., & Kramer, Mark R. (2006). *Strategy and society: the link between competitive advantage and corporate social responsibility*. Harvard Business Review, December 2006, Retrieved July 22, 2013, from <http://www.hbr.org>
- Powell, Thomas C. (1992). *Organizational Alignment as Competitive Advantage*. Strategic Management Journal, Vol. 13 No. 2, pp. 119-134.
- Quazi, Ali, & Richardson, Alice. (2012). *Sources of variation in linking corporate social responsibility and financial performance*. Social Responsibility Journal, Vol. 8 No. 2, pp. 242-256.
- Rahman, Shafiqur. (2011). *Evaluation of definitions: Ten dimensions of corporate social responsibility*. World Review of Business Research, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 166-176.
- Roman, Ronald M., Hayibor, Sefa, & Agle, Bradley R. (1999). *The relationship between social and financial performance: Repainting a portrait*. Business and Society, Vol. 38 No. 1, pp. 109-125.

- Said, Samah M. (2011). *The Possibility of Applying Accountability of CSR in Industrial Private Enterprises in Yemen: Field Study Applied in Taiz Governorate* (Master's thesis). College of Administrative Sciences, Aden University, Yemen.
- Schwartz, Mark S., & Carroll, Archie B. (2003). *Corporate Social Responsibility: A Three-Domain Approach*. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, Vol. 13 No. 4, pp. 503-530.
- Sekaran, Uma. (2003). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach* (4th ed.). New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Sharhan, Ahmed A. (2009). *The social responsibility of Sana'a University's students and its relationship with their psychological health* (Master's thesis). Sana'a University, Faculty of Literature, Psychology Section, Yemen.
- Spitzer, Dean R. (2007). *Transforming Performance Measurement: Rethinking the Way We Measure and Drive Organizational Success*. New York, NY: AMACOM Books.
- Stepanenko, Ievgeniia. (2012). *Corporate Social Responsibility in Ukraine* (Master's thesis). KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden. Retrieved July 15, 2013, from <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kth:diva-102383>
- Talbot, Colin. (2010). *Theories of Performance: Organizational and Service Improvement in the Public Domain*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press Inc.
- Tan, Gilbert, & Komaran, Raj. (2006). *Perceptions of Corporate Social Responsibility: An empirical study in Singapore*. The 13th Annual International Conference on Advances in Management, June 26, 2006, Singapore.
- Thomas, Adèle. (2012). *Governance at South African State-Owned Enterprises: What Do Annual Reports and the Print Media Tell Us?* *Social Responsibility Journal*, Vol. 8 No. 4, pp. 448-470.
- Tuan, Luu T. (2012). *Corporate Social Responsibility, Ethics, and Corporate Governance*. *Social Responsibility Journal*, Vol. 8 No. 4, pp. 547-560.
- Venkatraman, N., & Ramanujam, V. (1986a). *Measurement of Business Economic Performance: An Examination of Method Convergence*. *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 13 No. 1, pp. 109-22.
- Venkatraman, N., & Ramanujam, V. (1986b). *Measurement of Business Performance in Strategy Research: A Comparison of Approaches*. *The Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 11 No. 4, pp. 801-814.
- Verbenko, Olena I. (2011). *Corporate Social Responsibility* (Doctoral dissertation). UMI No. 3460248.

- Visser, W., Matten, D., Pohl, M., & Tolhurst, N. (2010). *The A-Z of Corporate Social Responsibility*. The Atrium, Southern Gate, Chichester, West Sussex, UK: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Vogel, David. (2005). *Is There a Market for Virtue? The Business Case for Corporate Social Responsibility*. California Management Review, Vol. 47 No. 4, pp. 19-45.
- Vollono, Robert J. (2010). *Doing Well by Doing Good: The Empirical Relationship Between Corporate Social Responsibility and Financial Performance* (Master's thesis). UMI No. 1475162.
- Wissink, Rutger. (2012). *A Test of the Virtuous Cycle of Corporate Social Responsibility: Testing the Relationship between Corporate Social Performance and Corporate Social Performance* (Master's thesis). Business administration, University of Twente, Netherlands. Retrieved March 15, 2013, from <http://purl.utwente.nl/essays/61472>
- Wood, Donna J. (1991). *Corporate Social Performance Revisited*. The Academy of Management Review, Vol. 16 No. 4, pp. 691-718.
- Wood, Donna J. (2010). *Measuring Corporate Social Performance: A Review*. International Journal of Management Reviews, Vol. 12, pp. 50-84., DOI: 10.1111/j.1468-2370.2009.00274.x
- Zu, Liangrong. (2009). *Corporate Social Responsibility, Corporate Restructuring, and Firm's Performance: Empirical Evidence from Chinese Enterprises*. Heidelberg: Berlin, Springer-Verlag.

APPENDIX A
ENGLISH VERSION OF THE STUDY'S INSTRUMENT

**CENTER FOR GRADUATE STUDIES
OPEN UNIVERSITY MALAYSIA
MALAYSIA**

OPEN UNIVERSITY
UNIVERSITI TERBUKA
MALAYSIA

No. | | |

Dear Respondent:

An academic study is conducted by the researcher entitled "*The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Nonfinancial Organizational Performance in For-Profit Public and Private Enterprises in Yemen.*" This study represents the Master's Project required for graduation with a Master's degree in Business Administration.

Accordingly, the researcher hopes that you will reply all the questions included in this questionnaire of the study and importantly avoid missing any question. The researcher ensures that your replies will be kept extremely confidential and that they will be only used for the sheer scientific and academic purposes of this study.

Dear Respondent,

In advance, the researcher highly appreciate your interest in participating in this study and in dedicating a part of your valuable time for replying its questionnaire's questions. The obtained results through this questionnaire will be the cornerstone for acquiring the expected scientific and researching outcomes which will be beneficial for both the researcher and other interested individuals in academic, managerial, and social fields inside and outside Yemen.

Thank you again for your kind cooperation.

The Researcher:

Eyad N. Al-Samman

A candidate for Master of Business Administration,

Open University Malaysia

Contact Information:

• E-mail: eyadnalsamman@oum.edu.my

A Questionnaire about the Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Nonfinancial Organizational Performance in For-Profit Public and Private Enterprises in Yemen.

First Section: Demographic Information on Respondents and their Enterprises

• **Gender:** Male Female

• **Age of Respondent:**
 Under 25 years 25 to 34 years 35 to 44 years
 45 to 54 years 55 to 64 years Above 64 years

• **Level of Education:**
 High School Graduate Diploma after the High School Bachelor's Degree
 Master's Degree Doctoral Degree
 Other (Please, mention here):

• **Current Position:**
 CEO (Chief Executive Officer) General Manager Consultant
 Department Manager Section Head
 Other (Please, mention here):

• **Type of the Enterprise:**
 Private Enterprise Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)
 Other (Please, mention here):

• **Nature of the Enterprises' Activity:**
 Private Service Sector Private Manufacturing or Product Sector
 Public Service Sector Public Manufacturing or Product Sector
 Other (Please, mention here):

• The Enterprise's Date of Foundation: (.....)

• Total Number of the Enterprise's Employees in 2013: (.....)

Second Section: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

No.	Item	Extremely Important	Important	Do not Know	Not Important	Extremely Not Important
First Part: The Enterprise's Economic Responsibilities						
1	Being committed to being as profitable as possible	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	Maintaining a strong competitive position	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Ensuring a high level of operating efficiency is maintained	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Second Section: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)						
No.	Item	Extremely Important	Important	Do not Know	Not Important	Extremely Not Important
4	Defining a successful firm as the one which is consistently profitable	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5	Monitoring new opportunities which can enhance the organization's financial health	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6	Allocating organizational resources as efficiently as possible	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7	Viewing consistent profitability as a useful measure of corporate performance	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8	Pursuing only those opportunities which provide the best rate of return	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Second Part: The Enterprise's Legal Responsibilities						
1	Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and the law	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	Being committed to abiding by laws and regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Fulfilling seriously the legal responsibilities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4	Preventing social norms from being compromised in order to achieve corporate goals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5	Defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its legal obligations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6	Providing goods and services which at least meet minimal legal requirements	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7	Viewing compliance with the law as a useful measure of corporate performance	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8	Recognizing that corporate integrity and ethical behavior go beyond mere compliance with laws and regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Third Part: The Enterprise's Ethical Responsibilities						
1	Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of societal mores and ethical norms	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	Advertising goods and services in an ethically fair and responsible manner	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Avoiding discriminating against women	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4	Defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its ethical and moral responsibilities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2						

Second Section: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)						
No.	Item	Extremely Important	Important	Do not Know	Not Important	Extremely Not Important
5	Monitoring new opportunities which can enhance the organization's moral and ethical image in society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Avoiding compromising societal norms and ethics in order to achieve goals	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Do not discouraging 'whistle blowing' at any corporate level	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	Fulfilling all corporate tax obligations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fourth Part: The Enterprise's Philanthropic Responsibilities						
1	Performing in a manner consistent with the philanthropic and charitable expectations of society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Participating as managers and employees in voluntary and charitable activities within their local communities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Providing assistance to private and public educational institutions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Defining a successful firm as the one which fulfills its philanthropic and charitable responsibilities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Monitoring new opportunities which can enhance the organization's ability to help solve social problems	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Assisting voluntarily those projects which enhance a community's 'quality of life'	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Viewing philanthropic behavior as a useful measure of corporate performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	Maintaining a policy of increasing charitable and voluntary efforts over time	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fifth Part: The Level of Adopting the Concept of CSR Generally						
1	Adopting periodically at least one type of the activities concerned with the corporate social responsibility by the enterprise in the Yemeni society	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Third Section: Nonfinancial Organizational Performance

No.	Item	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Your enterprise has the ability to provide customers with high quality products or services	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	Your enterprise does its best to develop new products or services	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Your enterprise has multiple recruiting strategies to attract talented employees	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4	Your enterprise provides well-designed wellness programs to retain employees	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5	Your customers are satisfied with your enterprise's service quality and efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6	Your enterprise facilitates management to effectively utilize employees with task-related resources in order to help employees to complete their jobs	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7	Your enterprise values the interactions between management and staff	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8	Your enterprise values the interactions among staff members	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Thank you for your time and for your kind cooperation ...

APPENDIX B
ARABIC VERSION OF THE STUDY'S INSTRUMENT

OPEN UNIVERSITY
UNIVERSITI TERBUKA
MALAYSIA

مركز الدراسات العليا
الجامعة الماليزية المفتوحة
ماليزيا

الرقم: | | |

أخي المشارك / أختي المشاركة ...

السلام عليكم ورحمة الله وبركاته ...

يجري الباحث دراسة بعنوان: "تأثير المسؤولية الاجتماعية للمؤسسات على الأداء المؤسسي غير المالي في الجهات الربحية الحكومية والخاصة في الجمهورية اليمنية"، وذلك استكمالاً لمتطلبات الحصول على درجة الماجستير في مجال إدارة الأعمال. وعليه، نرجو منكم التكرم بالإجابة على جميع الأسئلة الموجودة في هذا الاستبيان وعدم إغفال أي سؤال لأهمية ذلك للباحث، ونؤكد لكم أن إجاباتكم سوف تظل سرية للغاية ولن يتم استخدامها إلا في مجال هذه الدراسة لأغراض علمية وأكاديمية بحتة.

أخي المشارك / أختي المشاركة ...

نشكر لكم مسبقاً اهتمامكم بالمساهمة معنا وتكريس جزء من وقتكم الثمين للمشاركة في هذا الاستبيان والتجاوب مع جميع فقراته والذي سَتبني عليه نتائج علمية وبحثية يستفيد منها الباحث وكذا غيره من المهتمين في المجالات الأكاديمية والإدارية والاجتماعية في المجتمع اليمني.

لكم خالص الشكر والتقدير ،،،

الباحث/ إياد السمان
الجامعة الماليزية المفتوحة

معلومات التواصل مع الباحث:

• البريد الإلكتروني: eyadnalsamman@oum.edu.my

استبيان حول تأثير المسؤولية الاجتماعية للمؤسسات على الأداء المؤسسي غير المالي في الجهات الربحية الحكومية و الخاصة في الجمهورية اليمنية

القسم الأول: المعلومات العامة عن المشاركين وعن مؤسساتهم

• النوع: ذكر أنثى

• الفئة العمرية:
 (أ) أقل من ٢٥ سنة (ب) ٢٥ - ٣٤ سنة (ج) ٣٥ - ٤٤ سنة
 (د) ٤٥ - ٥٤ سنة (هـ) ٥٥ - ٦٤ سنة (و) أكبر من ٦٤ سنة

• المركز الوظيفي:
 (أ) رئيس أو مدير عام المؤسسة (ب) مدير إدارة بالمؤسسة
 (ج) أخرى (الرجاء التحديد):

• المؤهل العلمي:
 (أ) ثانوية عامة (ب) دبلوم بعد الثانوية العامة (ج) بكالوريوس
 (د) ماجستير (هـ) دكتوراة
 (و) أخرى (الرجاء التحديد):

• نوع المؤسسة:
 (أ) مؤسسة خاصة (ب) مؤسسة حكومية (ج) مؤسسة مختلطة
 (د) أخرى (الرجاء التحديد):

• طبيعة نشاط المؤسسة:
 (أ) قطاع خدمي خاص (ب) قطاع إنتاجي خاص
 (ج) قطاع خدمي حكومي (د) قطاع إنتاجي حكومي
 (هـ) قطاع خدمي مختلط (و) قطاع إنتاجي مختلط
 (ز) أخرى (الرجاء التحديد):

• سنة تأسيس المؤسسة (بالتقويم الميلادي): (.....)

• إجمالي عدد الموظفين في المؤسسة في العام ٢٠١٣م: (.....)

القسم الثاني: المسؤولية الاجتماعية للمؤسسات

رقم	الفقرة	مهم جداً	مهم	لا أدرى	غير مهم	غير مهم إطلاقاً
المحور الأول: المسؤوليات الاقتصادية للمؤسسة						
١	الالتزام بتحقيق أرباح للمؤسسة كلما أمكن ذلك	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٢	الحفاظ على مركز تنافسي قوي للمؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٣	التأكد بأن هناك مستوى عالٍ من الكفاءة التشغيلية يتم المحافظة عليه في المؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				

القسم الثاني: المسؤولية الاجتماعية للمؤسسات						
رقم	الفقرة	مهم جداً	مهم	لا أدري	غير مهم	غير مهم إطلاقاً
٤	القيام بتعريف المؤسسة الناجحة بأنها تلك المؤسسة الرابحة على الدوام	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٥	ملاحظة ومراقبة الفرص الجديدة التي تعمل على تحسين الأوضاع المالية للمؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٦	تحديد الموارد المؤسسية بشكل فعال كلما أمكن ذلك	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٧	اعتبار أن مبدأ الربحية الثابتة للمؤسسة يمثل مقياس ومؤشر مفيد للأداء المؤسسي	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٨	مواصلة العمل فقط مع الفرص التي تُزود المؤسسة بالمعدل الأفضل للعوائد	<input type="checkbox"/>				
المحور الثاني: المسؤوليات القانونية للمؤسسة						
١	أداء المهام المتعلقة بالمؤسسة بشكل منسجم طبقاً للقانون	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٢	الالتزام باتباع القوانين والأنظمة الأخرى	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٣	القيام بشكل جدي بتنفيذ المسؤوليات القانونية للمؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٤	منع استغلال المبادئ الاجتماعية من أجل تحقيق أهداف المؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٥	القيام بتعريف المؤسسة الناجحة بأنها تلك المؤسسة التي تنجز التزاماتها القانونية	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٦	تزويد المجتمع بمنتجات وخدمات ينطبق عليها الحد الأدنى من الاحتياجات القانونية المنصوص عليها	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٧	اعتبار أن مبدأ الامتثال للقانون يمثل مقياس ومؤشر مفيد للأداء المؤسسي	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٨	إدراك أن التكامل المؤسسي والسلوك الأخلاقي يفوق مجرد الامتثال للقوانين والأنظمة الأخرى	<input type="checkbox"/>				
المحور الثالث: المسؤوليات الأخلاقية للمؤسسة						
١	أداء المهام المتعلقة بالمؤسسة بشكل منسجم مع توقعات الأعراف الاجتماعية وكذا المبادئ الأخلاقية المتعارف عليها	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٢	الإعلان عن المنتجات والخدمات بطريقة أخلاقية مسؤولة وعادلة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٣	القيام بتجنب التمييز ضد المرأة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٤	القيام بتعريف المؤسسة الناجحة بأنها تلك المؤسسة التي تنجز مسؤولياتها الأخلاقية	<input type="checkbox"/>				

القسم الثاني: المسؤولية الاجتماعية للمؤسسات						
الرقم	الفقرة	مهم جداً	مهم	لا أدري	غير مهم	غير مهم إطلاقاً
٥	ملاحظة ومراقبة الفرص الجديدة التي تعمل على تحسين الصورة الأخلاقية للمؤسسة في المجتمع	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٦	تجنب استغلال المبادئ والأخلاقيات الاجتماعية من أجل تحقيق أهداف المؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٧	عدم إعاقة أو تعطيل مبدأ نقل الأخبار والتبليغ عما يتناقله ويفعله الموظفون في كافة المستويات الوظيفية في المؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٨	تسوية وإنهاء كل الالتزامات المتعلقة بالضرائب على المؤسسة	<input type="checkbox"/>				
المحور الرابع: المسؤوليات الطوعية للمؤسسة						
١	أداء المهام المتعلقة بالمؤسسة بشكل منسجم مع التوقعات الطوعية والخيرية للمجتمع	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٢	مشاركة المدراء والموظفين العاملين بالمؤسسة في الأعمال والأنشطة الخيرية والتطوعية داخل مجتمعاتهم المحلية	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٣	توفير المساعدة للمعاهد والمؤسسات التعليمية الخاصة والحكومية	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٤	القيام بتعريف المؤسسة الناجحة بأنها تلك المؤسسة التي تنجز مسؤولياتها الطوعية والخيرية	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٥	ملاحظة ومراقبة الفرص الجديدة التي تعمل على تحسين قدرات المؤسسة في المساعدة على حل المشاكل الاجتماعية	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٦	القيام تطوعياً بالمساعدة في دعم المشاريع التي تُسهم في تحسين نوعية المعيشة في المجتمع	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٧	اعتبار أن السلوك الطوعي يمثل مقياس ومؤشر مفيد للأداء المؤسسي	<input type="checkbox"/>				
٨	المحافظة على سياسة معينة تعمل على زيادة الجهود الخيرية والتطوعية مع مرور الوقت	<input type="checkbox"/>				
المحور الخامس: تبني مفهوم المسؤولية الاجتماعية بشكل عام						
١	قيام المؤسسة بتبني نوع واحد على الأقل من الأنشطة المتعلقة بالمسؤولية الاجتماعية في المجتمع وبشكل دوري	<input type="checkbox"/>				

القسم الثالث: الأداء المؤسسي غير المالي

لا أوافق بشدة	لا أوافق	محايد	أوافق	أوافق بشدة	الفقرة	ترتيب
<input type="checkbox"/>	تمتلك المؤسسة القدرة على تزويد زبائنها وعملائها بمنتجات أو خدمات عالية الجودة	١				
<input type="checkbox"/>	تعمل المؤسسة جاهدة على ابتكار منتجات أو خدمات جديدة	٢				
<input type="checkbox"/>	تمتلك المؤسسة استراتيجيات توظيف متعددة تعمل من خلالها على جذب الموظفين الموهوبين للعمل لديها	٣				
<input type="checkbox"/>	تعمل المؤسسة على توفير برامج مدروسة ومصممة ببراعة تعمل من خلالها على الاحتفاظ بموظفيها	٤				
<input type="checkbox"/>	عملاء وزبائن المؤسسة راضون عن مستوى جودة وفعالية المنتجات أو الخدمات المقدمة لهم	٥				
<input type="checkbox"/>	تعمل المؤسسة على تسهيل مهام هيئتها الإدارية للاستفادة من الموظفين ذوي المهام المرتبطة بموارد المؤسسة وذلك حتى تساعد هؤلاء الموظفين على إنجاز أعمالهم	٦				
<input type="checkbox"/>	تُثمن وتُقدّر المؤسسة التواصل والتعاون المتبادل بين الإدارة والموظفين	٧				
<input type="checkbox"/>	تُثمن وتُقدّر المؤسسة التواصل والتعاون المتبادل بين الموظفين أنفسهم	٨				

شكراً لوقتكم ولتعاونكم معنا بإجاباتكم على أسئلة الاستبيان كاملة ...

APPENDIX C
STATISTICAL REPORTS FOR ANALYSES USING SPSS

Frequencies

Statistics

		Gender	Age of Respondents	Level of Education	Current Position	Type of Enterprise
N	Valid	103	103	103	103	103
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		.92	2.84	3.02	3.76	1.30
Median		1.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	1.00
Mode		1	3	3	4	1
Std. Deviation		.269	.926	.671	.965	.461
Minimum		0	1	1	1	1
Maximum		1	5	5	5	2

Statistics

		Nature of Enterprise's Activity	Enterprise's Date of Foundation	Total No. of Employees in 2013
N	Valid	103	103	103
	Missing	0	0	0
Mean		1.95	4.27	2.50
Median		2.00	4.00	2.00
Mode		1	6	1
Std. Deviation		1.033	1.579	1.614
Minimum		1	0	1
Maximum		4	6	7

Frequency Table

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	8	7.8	7.8	7.8
	Male	95	92.2	92.2	100.0
	Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Age of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Under 25 years	4	3.9	3.9	3.9
25 to 34 years	36	35.0	35.0	38.8
35 to 44 years	40	38.8	38.8	77.7
45 to 54 years	18	17.5	17.5	95.1
55 to 64 years	5	4.9	4.9	100.0
Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Level of Education

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High School Graduate	4	3.9	3.9	3.9
Diploma after the High School	6	5.8	5.8	9.7
Bachelor's Degree	81	78.6	78.6	88.3
Master's Degree	8	7.8	7.8	96.1
Doctoral Degree	4	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Current Position

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid CEO	6	5.8	5.8	5.8
General Manager	8	7.8	7.8	13.6
Consultant	3	2.9	2.9	16.5
Department Manager	74	71.8	71.8	88.3
Section Head	12	11.7	11.7	100.0
Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Type of Enterprise

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Private Enterprise	72	69.9	69.9	69.9
Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)	31	30.1	30.1	100.0
Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Nature of Enterprise's Activity

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Private Service Sector	47	45.6	45.6	45.6
Private Manufacturing or Product Sector	24	23.3	23.3	68.9
Public Service Sector	22	21.4	21.4	90.3
Public Manufacturing or Product Sector	10	9.7	9.7	100.0
Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Enterprise's Date of Foundation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Before 1940	3	2.9	2.9	2.9
From 1940 to 1950	6	5.8	5.8	8.7
From 1951 to 1960	3	2.9	2.9	11.7
From 1961 to 1970	14	13.6	13.6	25.2
From 1971 to 1980	27	26.2	26.2	51.5
From 1981 to 1990	22	21.4	21.4	72.8
From 1991 to 2002	28	27.2	27.2	100.0
Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Total No. of Employees in 2013

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid From 50 to 250	41	39.8	39.8	39.8
From 251 to 500	19	18.4	18.4	58.3
From 501 to 1000	12	11.7	11.7	69.9
From 1001 to 3000	20	19.4	19.4	89.3
From 3001 to 5000	5	4.9	4.9	94.2
From 5001 to 10000	4	3.9	3.9	98.1
More than 10000	2	1.9	1.9	100.0
Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Bar Chart

Reliability - Economic Responsibilities

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	103	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	103	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.701	8

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Eco1	4.68	.675	103
Eco2	4.81	.525	103
Eco3	4.53	.607	103
Eco4	4.06	.838	103
Eco5	4.47	.639	103
Eco6	4.35	.667	103
Eco7	4.00	.970	103
Eco8	3.73	1.059	103

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Eco1	29.94	9.761	.470	.657
Eco2	29.82	10.250	.498	.661
Eco3	30.09	10.708	.282	.693
Eco4	30.56	8.974	.502	.645
Eco5	30.16	9.701	.525	.648
Eco6	30.27	10.278	.345	.682
Eco7	30.62	9.394	.313	.698
Eco8	30.89	8.841	.355	.692

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
34.62	12.198	3.493	8

Reliability - Legal Responsibilities

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	103	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	103	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.803	8

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Leg1	4.71	.588	103
Leg2	4.64	.669	103
Leg3	4.65	.622	103
Leg4	4.18	1.046	103
Leg5	4.16	.826	103
Leg6	4.31	.852	103
Leg7	4.40	.796	103
Leg8	4.50	.752	103

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Leg1	30.84	13.407	.621	.772
Leg2	30.91	13.179	.576	.774
Leg3	30.90	13.990	.441	.792
Leg4	31.37	11.294	.575	.775
Leg5	31.40	11.634	.730	.746
Leg6	31.24	13.656	.325	.812
Leg7	31.16	13.289	.431	.794
Leg8	31.05	12.988	.530	.779

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
35.55	16.426	4.053	8

Reliability - Ethical Responsibilities

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	103	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	103	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.737	8

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Eth1	4.42	.761	103
Eth2	4.54	.711	103
Eth3	4.48	.726	103
Eth4	4.39	.689	103
Eth5	4.43	.553	103
Eth6	4.30	.861	103
Eth7	3.57	1.134	103
Eth8	4.74	.523	103

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Eth1	30.45	9.975	.554	.685
Eth2	30.32	10.063	.587	.681
Eth3	30.39	10.593	.444	.708
Eth4	30.48	10.291	.554	.688
Eth5	30.44	11.268	.442	.712
Eth6	30.56	10.190	.416	.714
Eth7	31.29	10.150	.246	.775
Eth8	30.13	11.464	.417	.717

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
34.86	13.217	3.635	8

Reliability - Philanthropic Responsibilities

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	103	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	103	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.894	8

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Phi1	3.95	.933	103
Phi2	3.73	1.040	103
Phi3	3.83	1.014	103
Phi4	3.48	1.110	103
Phi5	3.74	.960	103
Phi6	3.84	1.017	103
Phi7	3.70	1.056	103
Phi8	3.66	.996	103

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Phi1	25.97	30.303	.668	.882
Phi2	26.19	29.844	.625	.886
Phi3	26.10	30.677	.563	.891
Phi4	26.45	28.132	.736	.875
Phi5	26.18	30.289	.646	.883
Phi6	26.08	29.112	.719	.877
Phi7	26.22	28.567	.740	.874
Phi8	26.26	29.548	.692	.879

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
29.92	38.033	6.167	8

Reliability - Nonfinancial Organizational Performance

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	103	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	103	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.864	8

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
NFOP1	4.68	.509	103
NFOP2	4.48	.608	103
NFOP3	4.15	.785	103
NFOP4	4.01	.923	103
NFOP5	4.30	.712	103
NFOP6	4.23	.717	103
NFOP7	4.37	.792	103
NFOP8	4.27	.854	103

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
NFOP1	29.81	16.570	.367	.870
NFOP2	30.01	15.696	.474	.862
NFOP3	30.34	13.756	.683	.839
NFOP4	30.48	12.742	.721	.835
NFOP5	30.18	14.701	.576	.852
NFOP6	30.25	14.230	.667	.842
NFOP7	30.12	13.457	.734	.833
NFOP8	30.21	13.425	.671	.841

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
34.49	18.350	4.284	8

Factor Analysis - Corporate Social Responsibility

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.796
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1521.072
	df	496
	Sig.	.000

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Eco1	1.000	.775
Eco2	1.000	.811
Eco3	1.000	.748
Eco4	1.000	.678
Eco5	1.000	.704
Eco6	1.000	.649
Eco7	1.000	.702
Eco8	1.000	.699
Leg1	1.000	.822
Leg2	1.000	.715
Leg3	1.000	.720
Leg4	1.000	.750
Leg5	1.000	.739
Leg6	1.000	.632
Leg7	1.000	.628
Leg8	1.000	.727
Eth1	1.000	.723
Eth2	1.000	.814
Eth3	1.000	.714
Eth4	1.000	.727
Eth5	1.000	.691
Eth6	1.000	.671
Eth7	1.000	.699
Eth8	1.000	.700
Phi1	1.000	.707
Phi2	1.000	.708
Phi3	1.000	.585
Phi4	1.000	.727
Phi5	1.000	.762
Phi6	1.000	.714
Phi7	1.000	.769
Phi8	1.000	.700

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Factor Analysis - Nonfinancial Organizational Performance

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.829
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	364.979
	df	28
	Sig.	.000

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
NFOP1	1.000	.820
NFOP2	1.000	.452
NFOP3	1.000	.603
NFOP4	1.000	.659
NFOP5	1.000	.505
NFOP6	1.000	.587
NFOP7	1.000	.782
NFOP8	1.000	.758

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Correlations between CSR and NFOP in Both SOEs and Private Enterprises

Correlations

		Eco_CSR	Leg_CSR	Eth_CSR	Phi_CSR
NFOP	Pearson Correlation	.360**	.272**	.327**	.375**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.005	.001	.000
	N	103	103	103	103

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations between CSR and NFOP in Private Enterprises

Correlations

		Eco_CSR	Leg_CSR	Eth_CSR	Phi_CSR
NFOP	Pearson Correlation	.414**	.352**	.368**	.463**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002	.001	.000
	N	72	72	72	72

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations between CSR and NFOP in SOEs (For-Profit Public Enterprises)

Correlations

		Eco_CSR	Leg_CSR	Eth_CSR	Phi_CSR
NFOP	Pearson Correlation	.279	.115	.265	.273
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.129	.537	.150	.138
	N	31	31	31	31

**Correlations:
 CSR and Nonfinancial Organizational Performance of Both SOEs
 & Private Enterprises as a Whole Entity (including all other inter-correlations)**

Correlations

		NFOP	Eco_CSR	Leg_CSR	Eth_CSR	Phi_CSR
NFOP	Pearson Correlation	1	.360**	.272**	.327**	.375**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.005	.001	.000
	N	103	103	103	103	103
Eco_CSR	Pearson Correlation	.360**	1	.351**	.311**	.320**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.001	.001
	N	103	103	103	103	103
Leg_CSR	Pearson Correlation	.272**	.351**	1	.584**	.394**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.000		.000	.000
	N	103	103	103	103	103
Eth_CSR	Pearson Correlation	.327**	.311**	.584**	1	.523**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.001	.000		.000
	N	103	103	103	103	103
Phi_CSR	Pearson Correlation	.375**	.320**	.394**	.523**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.000	.000	
	N	103	103	103	103	103

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression

Variables Entered/Removed^b

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Phi_CSR, Eco_CSR, Leg_CSR ^a , Eth_CSR	.	Enter

a. All requested variables entered.

b. Dependent Variable: NFOP

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.466 ^a	.218	.186	3.866

Model Summary^b

Model	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.218	6.815	4	98	.000	2.151

a. Predictors: (Constant), Phi_CSR, Eco_CSR, Leg_CSR, Eth_CSR

b. Dependent Variable: NFOP

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	407.328	4	101.832	6.815	.000 ^a
	Residual	1464.400	98	14.943		
	Total	1871.728	102			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Phi_CSR, Eco_CSR, Leg_CSR, Eth_CSR

b. Dependent Variable: NFOP

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.623	4.768		2.857	.005
	Eco_CSR	.296	.120	.242	2.470	.015
	Leg_CSR	.033	.120	.031	.277	.782
	Eth_CSR	.136	.141	.116	.965	.337
	Phi_CSR	.156	.075	.225	2.095	.039

a. Dependent Variable: NFOP

Frequencies - Variances of Public and Private Enterprises

Type of Enterprise = Private Enterprise

Statistics^a

Overall adoption of CSR as a pr

N	Valid	72
	Missing	0
Mean		4.04
Std. Deviation		1.041
Variance		1.083

a. Type of Enterprise = Private Enterprise

Type of Enterprise = Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)

Statistics^a

Overall adoption of CSR as a pr

N	Valid	31
	Missing	0
Mean		3.77
Std. Deviation		1.146
Variance		1.314

a. Type of Enterprise = Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)

T-Test - Difference between SOEs and Private Enterprises in Adopting CSR

Group Statistics

Type of Enterprise	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity Private Enterprise	72	4.04	1.041	.123
Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)	31	3.77	1.146	.206

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity	Equal variances assumed	1.263	.264	1.160	101	.249	.267	.231	-.190	.725
	Equal variances not assumed			1.116	52.283	.269	.267	.240	-.213	.748

Means - Measuring the Effect Size through Eta-squared

Report

Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity

Type of Enterprise	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Private Enterprise	4.04	72	1.041
Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)	3.77	31	1.146
Total	3.96	103	1.075

ANOVA Table

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity * Type of Enterprise	Between Groups (Combined)	1.550	1	1.550	1.346	.249
	Within Groups	116.294	101	1.151		
	Total	117.845	102			

Measures of Association

	Eta	Eta Squared
Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity * Type of Enterprise	.115	.013

Frequencies of Main Variables

Statistics

		NFOP Mean	EcoCSR_ Mean	LegCSR_ Mean	EthCSR_ Mean	PhiCSR_ Mean
N	Valid	103	103	103	103	103
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.3107	4.3277	4.4442	4.3580	3.7403
Std. Deviation		.53547	.43658	.50661	.45443	.77089
Minimum		2.88	2.13	2.38	2.00	1.00
Maximum		5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00

Frequency Table

NFOP_Mean

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.88	2	1.9	1.9	1.9
	3.00	1	1.0	1.0	2.9
	3.25	3	2.9	2.9	5.8
	3.38	1	1.0	1.0	6.8
	3.50	2	1.9	1.9	8.7
	3.63	5	4.9	4.9	13.6
	3.75	4	3.9	3.9	17.5
	3.88	5	4.9	4.9	22.3
	4.00	11	10.7	10.7	33.0
	4.13	8	7.8	7.8	40.8
	4.25	3	2.9	2.9	43.7
	4.38	9	8.7	8.7	52.4
	4.50	10	9.7	9.7	62.1
	4.63	9	8.7	8.7	70.9
	4.75	10	9.7	9.7	80.6
	4.88	5	4.9	4.9	85.4
	5.00	15	14.6	14.6	100.0
	Total	103	100.0	100.0	

EcoCSR_Mean

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.13	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	3.38	3	2.9	2.9	3.9
	3.50	2	1.9	1.9	5.8
	3.63	3	2.9	2.9	8.7
	3.75	5	4.9	4.9	13.6
	3.88	2	1.9	1.9	15.5
	4.00	3	2.9	2.9	18.4
	4.13	9	8.7	8.7	27.2
	4.25	9	8.7	8.7	35.9
	4.38	21	20.4	20.4	56.3
	4.50	13	12.6	12.6	68.9
	4.63	18	17.5	17.5	86.4
	4.75	4	3.9	3.9	90.3
	4.88	7	6.8	6.8	97.1
	5.00	3	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	103	100.0	100.0	

LegCSR_Mean

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.38	2	1.9	1.9	1.9
	3.13	1	1.0	1.0	2.9
	3.25	1	1.0	1.0	3.9
	3.63	2	1.9	1.9	5.8
	3.75	3	2.9	2.9	8.7
	3.88	3	2.9	2.9	11.7
	4.00	8	7.8	7.8	19.4
	4.13	6	5.8	5.8	25.2
	4.25	8	7.8	7.8	33.0
	4.38	7	6.8	6.8	39.8
	4.50	12	11.7	11.7	51.5
	4.63	11	10.7	10.7	62.1
	4.75	13	12.6	12.6	74.8
	4.88	12	11.7	11.7	86.4
	5.00	14	13.6	13.6	100.0
	Total	103	100.0	100.0	

EthCSR_Mean

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2.00	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	2.88	1	1.0	1.0	1.9
	3.25	1	1.0	1.0	2.9
	3.50	1	1.0	1.0	3.9
	3.63	2	1.9	1.9	5.8
	3.75	1	1.0	1.0	6.8
	3.88	2	1.9	1.9	8.7
	4.00	11	10.7	10.7	19.4
	4.13	11	10.7	10.7	30.1
	4.25	10	9.7	9.7	39.8
	4.38	13	12.6	12.6	52.4
	4.50	20	19.4	19.4	71.8
	4.63	10	9.7	9.7	81.6
	4.75	3	2.9	2.9	84.5
	4.88	6	5.8	5.8	90.3
	5.00	10	9.7	9.7	100.0
	Total	103	100.0	100.0	

PhiCSR_Mean

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.00	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	1.50	1	1.0	1.0	1.9
	2.00	1	1.0	1.0	2.9
	2.25	1	1.0	1.0	3.9
	2.38	3	2.9	2.9	6.8
	2.50	2	1.9	1.9	8.7
	2.63	1	1.0	1.0	9.7
	2.75	2	1.9	1.9	11.7
	2.88	3	2.9	2.9	14.6
	3.00	3	2.9	2.9	17.5
	3.13	4	3.9	3.9	21.4
	3.25	7	6.8	6.8	28.2
	3.38	3	2.9	2.9	31.1
	3.50	3	2.9	2.9	34.0
	3.63	6	5.8	5.8	39.8
	3.75	2	1.9	1.9	41.7
	3.88	8	7.8	7.8	49.5
	4.00	17	16.5	16.5	66.0
	4.13	8	7.8	7.8	73.8
	4.25	5	4.9	4.9	78.6
	4.38	7	6.8	6.8	85.4
	4.50	3	2.9	2.9	88.3
	4.63	3	2.9	2.9	91.3
	4.75	2	1.9	1.9	93.2
	4.88	2	1.9	1.9	95.1
	5.00	5	4.9	4.9	100.0
	Total	103	100.0	100.0	

Frequencies - Overall Adoption of CSR in Public and Private Enterprises

Type of Enterprise = Private Enterprise

Statistics^a

Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity

N	Valid	72
	Missing	0
Mean		4.04
Std. Deviation		1.041
Minimum		1
Maximum		5

a. Type of Enterprise = Private Enterprise

Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity^a

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Absolutely Not Important	2	2.8	2.8	2.8
	Not Important	6	8.3	8.3	11.1
	Do not Know	7	9.7	9.7	20.8
	Important	29	40.3	40.3	61.1
	Extremely Important	28	38.9	38.9	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

a. Type of Enterprise = Private Enterprise

Type of Enterprise = Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)

Statistics^a

Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity

N	Valid	31
	Missing	0
Mean		3.77
Std. Deviation		1.146
Minimum		2
Maximum		5

a. Type of Enterprise = Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)

Overall adoption of CSR as a periodic institutional activity^a

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not Important	8	25.8	25.8	25.8
	Important	14	45.2	45.2	71.0
	Extremely Important	9	29.0	29.0	100.0
Total		31	100.0	100.0	

a. Type of Enterprise = Public Enterprise (State-Owned Enterprise)

